

**ECONOMIC VALUATION AND RISK PERCEPTIONS OF WATER-
RELATED ECOSYSTEM SERVICES IN PRA AND DENSU RIVER
BASINS IN GHANA**

BY

SALISU MUSTAPHA

10807466

**THIS THESIS IS SUBMITTED TO THE UNIVERSITY OF GHANA,
LEGON, IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF REQUIREMENTS FOR THE
AWARD OF DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY DEGREE IN APPLIED
AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS AND POLICY**

**DEPARTMENT OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS AND
AGRIBUSINESS, COLLEGE OF BASIC AND APPLIED SCIENCES,
UNIVERSITY OF GHANA, LEGON**

DECEMBER, 2023

DECLARATION

This thesis is the result of a study undertaken by Salisu Mustapha in the Department of Agricultural Economics and Agribusiness, University of Ghana, under the supervision of Dr. Yaw Osei-Asare, Dr. Francis Amevenku, and Dr. John Baptist D. Jatoe. It has never been submitted in whole or in part for any degree in this University or elsewhere. References to other people's work have been duly acknowledged.

.....

Salisu Mustapha
(Student)

14-12-23

Date

.....

Dr. Yaw Osei-Asare
(Major Supervisor)

20/12/2023

Date

.....

Dr. Francis Amevenku
(Co-supervisor)

10-12-23

Date

.....

Dr. John Baptist D. Jatoe.
(Co-supervisor)

20/12/2023

Date

ABSTRACT

Ecosystem services play significant roles in human life by providing food, aesthetics, economic opportunities, and climate regulation. The general objective of this study, therefore, was to determine the economic value of water-related ecosystem services associated with the Pra and Densu River basins in Ghana, as well as the perception of risks by households in both basins. This study contributed to this body of literature using results from a discrete choice experiment analysis of 1000 respondents (500 from each basin) selected using multistage sampling. The two basins were purposively selected due to evidence of deterioration of the river basins. The basins were then stratified into three (3) and five (5) in Densu and Pra respectively based on the regional administrative boundaries. To select the number of districts where respondents were to be sampled, a 90% confidence level and a 10% margin of error were applied on *Raosoft* online sample size calculator, resulting in the selection of 15 districts (out of 18 districts) and 36 (out of the 68 districts) in the Densu and Pra basins respectively. Districts and respondents were selected using simple random sampling. The number of districts and respondents was determined based on the population distribution during the 2021 population census, where regions and districts with a large population had more respondents proportional to the size of the population. The data was collected by well-trained and experienced enumerators using the KoboToolbox open-source data systems. The results revealed that respondents had little appreciation for the limits of nature based on the New Ecological Paradigm (NEP) scale. Illegal mining was also perceived to be the activity with the highest rating in risk perception. Finally, respondents were willing to pay between a minimum of GHS 29.17 (equivalent to US\$ 2.43) and a maximum of GHS 151.61 (equivalent to US\$ 12.63) per household per month in order to get improvements in water-related ecosystem services. Based on the results of the study, it is recommended that the National Commission for Civic Education should strengthen

education to enhance environmental awareness and also reduce activities that pose a risk to the river basins and the environment.

DEDICATION

This project work is dedicated to the loving memory of my beloved father, Sheikh Mustapha Baba, Bawku, and my mother, Hajia Amina Ustarz Jibreel.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This study was only successful with the input, support, criticisms, and encouragement from many people and institutions. First, I would like to extend my gratitude to the almighty Allah for his mercy in granting me good health and strength to complete this study successfully.

I would like to acknowledge the tremendous support, guidance, criticisms, and feedback from my supervisors, Dr. Yaw Osei-Asare, Dr. Francis Amevenku, and Dr. John Baptist D. Jatoe. In that same category and deserving of much appreciation is Dr. Marianne Zandersen (Aarhus University, Denmark) for her priceless contribution towards the success of this study.

The financial contribution from The Danish International Development Agency (DANIDA) under the Building Climate Resilience into Basin Water Management (CREAM) project has made this study and my academic journey possible and easy. I acknowledge the institutional support from Aarhus University (Roskilde, Denmark), the Water Research Institute (WRI) of the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), and the Department of Agricultural Economics and Agribusiness (DAEA) of the University of Ghana.

Moreover, I would like to acknowledge the following for making time to proofread my work and give me feedback: Mr. Tijani Inusah Iddrisu (lecturer, University for Development Studies), Dr. Adinan Bahahudeen Shafiwu (lecturer, University for Development Studies), and others that have contributed in diverse ways to make this thesis complete. The contribution of my trusted and well-trained enumerators and the respondents across the districts must be noticed, as the study could only have been with quality data.

The spiritual support and motivation from my family, friends and loved ones have also contributed significantly towards achieving this milestone.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Contents

DECLARATION	i
ABSTRACT	ii
DEDICATION	iv
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	v
TABLE OF CONTENTS	vii
LIST OF FIGURES/MAPS	x
LIST OF TABLES	xi
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	xii
CHAPTER ONE	1
INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Background	1
1.2 Problem Statement and Research Questions	4
1.3 Objectives of the Study	9
1.5 Hypotheses of the Study	10
1.6 Relevance of the Study	11
CHAPTER TWO	13
LITERATURE REVIEW	13
2.1 Introduction	13
2.2 The Concept of Ecosystem Services	13
2.3 Water-Related Ecosystem Services	15
2.4 Review of Relevant Concepts and Discrete Choice Experiment Issues	17
2.4.1 Identification and Description of Attributes	17
2.4.2 Design of Choice Experiments	18
2.4.2.1 Orthogonal Full Factorial Designs	19
2.4.2.2 Orthogonal Fractional Factorial Designs	20
2.4.3 Model Estimation for Choice Experiments	20
2.4.4 Welfare Measures for Marginal Effects in Choice Experiments	21
2.5 Theoretical Review	21
2.5.1 Consumer Theory	21
2.5.2 Theory of Welfare Change	23
2.5.3 The Theory of Value-Belief-Norm (VBN)	26

2.6 Economic Valuation of Environmental Services and Goods	27
2.7 The New Ecological Paradigm (NEP) Scale as a Measure of Environmental Assessment (EA)	28
2.8 Pro-Environmental and Socio-Cultural Viewpoints of the NEP Concept	31
2.9 Empirical Review	33
2.9.1 Discrete Choice Experiments and Willingness to Pay (WTP) for Ecosystem Services	34
2.9.2 Non-Monetary Payment Vehicles in Valuation Studies	41
2.9.3 The New Ecological Paradigm (NEP)	44
2.9.4 Relationships between NEP Scales and Sociodemographic Characteristics	46
2.9.5 Measurement of Risk Perceptions	47
2.9.6 Risk Research in the Water Sector	49
2.9.7 Factors that Influence Risk Perception	50
2.9.8 Sociodemographic Factors Influencing Risk Perceptions	53
CHAPTER THREE	56
RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	56
3.1 Introduction	56
3.2 Study Areas	56
3.2.1 Pra Basin	56
3.2.2 Densu Basin	57
3.3 Sources and Types of Data	58
3.4 Sampling and Sample Size	59
3.5 Conceptual Framework Underlying the Valuation and Risk Perceptions of WES in the Pra and Densu Basins	67
3.6 Theoretical Framework Underlying the Study of the Two Basins	69
3.6.1 Marginal willingness to pay (MWTP)	73
3.7 Measurement of Variables	75
3.7.1 Risk perceptions and Environmental Awareness of Respondents	75
3.7.2 New Ecological Paradigm (NEP) Scales	76
3.8 Research Design Adopted for this Study	76
3.9 Design of the Choice Experiment	78
3.9.1 Identification and selection of Attributes and their Levels	78
3.9.2 Questionnaire Development	79
3.9.3 Generation of Choice Cards	79
3.10 Data Analysis	81
CHAPTER FOUR	82

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS	82
4.1 Introduction	82
4.2 Sociodemographic Profile of Respondents	82
4.3 Environmental Awareness of Respondents	86
4.3.1 Distribution of Environmental Awareness of Respondents	87
4.3.2 Determinants of Environmental Awareness	93
4.4 Respondents' Perceptions of Risk Items	95
4.4.1 Distribution of Respondents' Perceptions of Risk Items	95
4.4.2 Factor Analysis of Respondents' Perception of Risks	100
4.5 Preference and willingness to pay for water-related ecosystem services	101
4.6 Effect of Change in the Payment Vehicle on Preference and Willingness to Pay	110
CHAPTER FIVE	118
SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	118
5.1 Summary of Major Findings	118
5.2 Conclusions of the study	123
5.3 Recommendations of the study	124
5.4 Suggestions for Further Studies	125
REFERENCES	127
Appendix A: Questionnaire	149
Section A: State and Frequency of Ecosystem Services	150
Section B: Risks and Concern on Water-Related Ecosystem Services	151
Section C: Choice Experiment	153
Section D: Socio-Demographic Information	160
Section E: Farming and Fishing Activities	161
Section F: Physical, Social and Financial Assets	162
Section G: Household Water Use and Sources	164
Section H: Risk Profile, Environmental Attitudes and Belief	165
Appendix B: Choice Experiment Design	169
Appendix D: Supplementary Results of NEP Scale and Risk Perception Estimates	170
Appendix E: Supplementary Results of the Preference and Payments for WES	172
Table E2: Results of Random Parameter Model	174

LIST OF FIGURES/MAPS

Figure 3.1: Map of Pra River Basin	57
Figure 3.2: Map of Densu River Basin	58
Figure 3.3: Conceptual Framework Underlying the Study of the Two Basins.....	69
Figure 3.3: Example of Choice card (Money payments in GHS).....	77
Figure 3.4: Example of Choice card (Time payments in Labour days).....	80
Figure 4.1: Mean NEP Scores.....	88
Figure 4.2: NEP Scores for Ecocentric Variables.....	90
Figure 4.3: NEP Scores for Anthropocentric Variables.....	91

LIST OF TABLES

Table 3.1: Summary of Sample Size across Basins	59
Table 3.3: Distribution of the sample in Pra Basin	64
Table 3.3: Attributes and Level used in the choice experiment.....	78
Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics of respondents	83
Table 4.2A Description of the revised NEP scale.....	86
Table 4.2.B: Frequency distribution and mean NEP scores per basin.....	92
Table 4.2.C: Results of Confirmatory Factor Analysis	93
Table 4.2.D: Determinants of Environmental Awareness (NEP).....	95
Table 4.3.A: Mean Risk Scores	97
Table 4.3.B: Distribution of Risk Perception Scores.....	99
Table 4.4: Results of Factor Analysis	101
Table 4.5 (A) Results of the Mixed Logit Model for Preference for Water-Related Ecosystem Services.....	102
Table 4.6 Sociodemographic and Environmental Determinants of Preference for Water-Related Ecosystem Services.....	108
Table 4.7A: Results of the Mixed Logit Model for Preference for Water-Related Ecosystem Services (Time Payment).....	111
Table 4.8: Monetised Equivalence of Time.....	115
Table 4.9: Shadow Wage Rate of Respondents in the Basins	117
Table E1: Results of Multinomial Regression Results	172

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AIC	Akaike Information Criterion
ASC	Alternative Specific Constant
BES	Benefit from ecosystem Services
BIC	Bayesian Information Criterion
CC	Climate Change
CICES	Common International Classifications for Ecosystem Services
CREAM	Building Climate Resilience into Basin Water Management
CS	Compensation Surplus
CSM	Contingent Valuation Method
CV	Compensating Variation
DANIDA	Danish International Development Agency
DCE	Discrete Choice Experiment
DSP	Dominant Social Paradigm
EA	Environmental Attitudes
EC	Environmental Concern
ES	Ecosystem Services
EU	European Union
EV	Equivalent Variety
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation
GSS	Ghana Statistical Service
IIA	Independence from Irrelevant Alternatives
IPBES	Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
MA	Millennium Assessment

MDC	Multinomial Discrete Choice
MEA	Millennium Ecosystem Assessment
MWTP	Marginal Willingness to Pay
MWTW	Mean Willingness to Work
NEP	New Ecological Paradigm
NEA	National Ecosystem Assessment
PES	Payment for Ecosystem Services
PR	Perceived Risk
SD	Standard Deviation
SHS	Senior High School
TEEB	The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity
UK	United Kingdom
UNCEEA	The UN Committee of Experts on Environmental-Economic Accounting
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation
US	United States
USEPA	United States Environmental Protection Agency
VBN	Value Belief Norm
Voc	Vocational school
WEIRD	Western, Educated, Industrialized, Rich and Democratic
WES	Water-Related Ecosystem Services
WRC	Water Resources Commission
WRM	Water Resource Management
WTP	Willingness to pay
WWAP	World Water Assessment Programme

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Water resources are paramount for natural ecosystems and global socio-economic and environmental wellbeing (Sharma, Rasul, & Chettri, 2015; Davivongs, Yokohari & Hara, 2012). Developing countries, in particular, benefit from the development opportunities that water can provide, as it is crucial for poverty reduction and economic growth (World Water Assessment Programme, 2012; Wasambo, 2011). However, countries that rely heavily on agriculture as their primary economic activity are particularly vulnerable to the unpredictability of water resources in terms of timing and location (Wasambo, 2011). Unfortunately, many developing African countries are currently experiencing water scarcity due to a rapid increase in water demand resulting from population growth and economic expansion, leading to the depletion of this vital resource (Chiluwe & Nkhata, 2014).

Water scarcity is not peculiar to Africa, as global estimates show that 3.6 billion individuals are exposed to water scarcity, with further increases expected to hover between 4.8 and 5.7 billion people by 2050 (Li, Zhang & Shi, 2019).

Water stress is predicted to affect more than 30 countries by 2025, and by 2050, population growth, industrialization, and rising water consumption will have already impacted two thirds of the world's population (Gosain, Sandhya, & Debajit, 2006). Humans completely rely on healthy water ecosystems, which offer many life-supporting services, including aesthetic appeal. Such services are in high demand and often lead to fish stock depletion in particular and agricultural land in general (Coates, Pert, Barron, Muthuri, Nguyen-Khoa, Boelee, & Jarvis, 2013; Millennium Ecosystem Assessment [MEA], 2005). Many ecosystems have been

degraded to the point of tipping (extinction) (The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity [TEEB], 2010). The timing of tipping points remains uncertain, necessitating precautionary measures to preserve ecosystems, prevent habitat degradation, and prevent species extinction. Recognising these services and their importance for human wellbeing and economic activity is critical to preventing further degradation. The values of ecosystem services have been recognised in various governmental decision-making processes. Recently, there has been growing policy and legislative recognition for valuing ecosystem services.

Consequently, policy space and legislation have launched investigations to analyse and include the value of ecosystem services in the planning process. Recognising these qualities could aid in conservation efforts (TEEB, 2010). Members of the European Union, for example, are required to make ecosystems and ecosystem services an integral part of policy development (European Union Parliament, 2012).

Estimating ecosystem service values is often limited by the methods used to define the values, resulting in partial assessments that may not fully represent the concerns of all beneficiaries (Martín-López, 2014). To overcome this limitation, experts recommend a combination of interdisciplinary approaches and methods of valuation to enable better-informed decisions regarding ecosystem service management (Lusardi et al. 2020).

There has been considerable growth in ecosystem services valuations in the last few decades owing to growing awareness of the loss of ecosystem benefits resulting from poor management of the environment (Borges & Machado, 2012). Assessment of ecosystem services meant to inform planning and management of the environment has advocated for incorporating diverse socio-cultural and ecological values (Cusens, Barraclough, & Måren, 2023; Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services [IPBES], 2012; The UN Committee of Experts on Environmental-Economic Accounting [UNCEEAA], 2014).

Ecological values are defined as how a service contributes to the ecosystem's health and are measured by indices such as diversity and resilience (Daly, Baetens, & De Baets, 2018; De Groot, Fisher, Christie, Aronson, Braat, Gowdy, & Neuville, 2010).

According to World Water Assessment Programme [WWAP] (2018), water demand has been increasing at approximately 1% per year worldwide, and this demand will continue to rise due to changing consumption patterns and population growth (Pandya & Sharma, 2020). Studies regularly predict a gap between water supply and demand, which is projected to be further widened by climate change in many regions (Martínez-Valderrama et al. 2023).

Rivers and river systems are a vital water source for billions of people worldwide and are crucial in supplying irrigation water and urban water supplies (Yoshikawa et al. 2013). Despite this, river management has traditionally focused on a limited range of values, such as hydropower, navigation, and water supply for cities, industry, and agriculture, representing only a small part of the complete spectrum of river values. Scientists have used ecosystem service concepts and approaches to account for other river benefits, such as biodiversity conservation, flood regulation, and recreation. The importance of the benefits necessitates that their values must be fully integrated into policy considerations (Drupp et al., 2018).

Consequently, natural ecosystems containing water resources worldwide are considered critical socioeconomic and environmental commodities (Sharma, Rasul, & Chettri, 2015; Davivongs, Yokohari, & Hara, 2012). As Wasambo (2011) reported, water, especially in developing countries, could boost economic development. It is also worth noting that water supplies are critical to poverty alleviation and economic progress (Tropp, 2015; World Water Assessment Programme, 2012). Invariably, these agriculture-based economies are particularly vulnerable to water scarcity (Chiluwe & Nkhata, 2014). Water shortages have become a major issue in many of these emerging countries in Africa (Li, Zhang, & Shi, 2019).

Ghana's Densu and Pra River basins have been designated as environmentally rich (Schep, Guzmán, Van Beukering, De Moel, Eiselin, Ayesu, Ansah, 2016). The basins contribute appreciably to the country's socioeconomic and cultural development (Adjei et al. 2019; Antwi-Agyakwa, 2014; Anornu, Kabo-bah, & Anim-Gyampo, 2012; Amoako, Karikari, Ansa-Asare, & Adu-Ofori, 2010). These include supporting domestic, irrigation, and industrial activities in the country. They are key to the supply of fresh water for the people who live along their watersheds, which cut across urban townships like Accra (40% of a population of 3.2 million) and Koforidua (1.7 million people). The basins also support the livelihoods of residents via mining, irrigated agriculture, bottled water manufacture, and other industrial activities (Water Resources Commission [WRC], 2012).

Ironically, these basins are being degraded due to deforestation, agricultural and pastoral practices, and unregulated mining activities (Bessah et al. 2021). Agricultural activities, especially by commercial farmers, within the basins are causing problems related to water quality and quantity (Zakari, 2012; Amoako, Karikari, Ansa-Asare, & Adu-Ofori, 2010). River basins are being severely impacted by human activity, which is causing water resources and ecosystem services to disappear (Akurugu et al. 2022).

1.2 Problem Statement and Research Questions

Human activities pose significant risk to the supply of ecosystem services in general, and in particular, water-related ecosystem services. Ecosystem services are heavily impacted by human activities like unsustainable agricultural practices, deforestation, illegal mining, sand mining, and improper waste disposal (Sharma & Sharma, 2019). According to Enming, Yi, Zhiyun, and Hua (2014), these activities may result in increased water yield, phosphorus and

nitrogen load but decreased carbon storage, habitat quality, and soil erosion control. The structure and function of the ecosystem have been significantly transformed, and the supply of services has decreased, as a result of overgrazing, urbanisation, and degradation of grasslands, wetlands, and other high-intensity human activities (Darvill and Lindo, 2016).

The gap between ecosystem services and human needs is increasing due to societal and economic growth. Prior to 2005, 60% of world's ecosystem services declined (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005), but since then, population and economic growth have significantly increased, causing ecosystem degradation. Population and economic growth have led to ecosystem degradation and reduced supply of critical services like water quality, erosion control, carbon sequestration, and biodiversity, necessitating efficient management (Grêt-Regamey & Weibel, 2021; Menbere & Menbere, 2018; Abebe, Seyoum, & Feyssa, 2014).

Meanwhile, demand for especially provisioning services for domestic, irrigation and industrial use is expected to increase simultaneously (Salman & Martinez, 2015; United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation [UNESCO], 2012). Climate change is also expected to increase further the demand for regulating and maintenance services. The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (2005) suggests that ecosystems are rapidly changing to increase resources like food, water, fibre, and energy, such as fuelwood and hydropower.

The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (2005) links agricultural growth to degraded water ecosystem services, citing intensification and expansion as contributing factors (Martin-Ortega, Ferrier, & Gordon, 2015). Africa's three billion hectares are divided into nine percent for crop production, 22% forested, and 30% for pastures and meadows (Food and Agriculture Organisation [FAO], 2011). The remaining parts of the continent are made of built-up structures, settlements, and vegetated and barren lands. Land for agriculture (comprising land

for crops, permanent pastures, and meadows) has increased by 11% in Africa compared to 54% in Asia over the past 50 years (FAO, 2011).

Despite low adoption of agricultural inputs, particularly in Africa, certain practices have exposed ecosystem services to risks that threaten their sustainability. Practices such as indiscriminate pesticide use, agricultural waste disposal, fertiliser application, and commercial fishing pose some risks to water ecosystems (Shefali et al., 2022). The quality and quantity of water resources significantly impact fish stock, crop output, biodiversity, and biological resource viability (FAOWATER, 2009). In light of the above, the security of global freshwater supplies is a pressing issue, necessitating a re-evaluation of water resource management for a sustainable future. Societies must consider water's multiple values and incorporate them into their management (Martin-Ortega, Ferrier, & Gordon, 2015).

On the national level, Densu and Pra basins face serious pressures from humans and climate variabilities. Continuous degradation of water resources, coupled with increasing climate change, has serious consequences for WES and, consequently, the wellbeing of humans (Baudron & Giller, 2014). Recent studies on the status of water bodies in Ghana show impairment in the two basins, especially in Pra, (Darko et al. 2021). These affected the ecosystem services supplied by the rivers. For example, a study in the Densu basin showed severe impairment in locations due to agriculture, industrialisation, and urbanisation (Ayertey, 2013). The resultant effect is impairment of ecosystem services such as water quality, fish catches, and quantity of fresh water. If not regulated, this situation could worsen.

A number of environmental and social challenges affect Ghana's Pra and Densu basins, such as the dangers associated with small-scale mining, illegal mining, and the mining of coastal sediments (Nti et al. 2023; Darko et al. 2021; Jonah, Adams, Aheto, Jonah, & Mensah, 2017;

Bansah, 2016). These human activities have led to significant degradation of the river basins, affecting the supply of water-related ecosystem services in the two basins.

Erosion has become a major issue of concern, especially in the Densu basin. The main factor contributing to the high rates of erosion along the 25 km in the coastal area of the Central region between 2005 and 2012, according to Jonah et al. (2015), was coastal sediment mining. Tipper-truck-based sand miners caused a loss of 285,376 m³ of sand from the coastal area of the Cape Coast in 2012. Only a few areas of Ghana's coastline showed stability or accretion between 1885 and 2002, with the majority of the coast retreating (Boateng, 2012).

The process of gold mining heavily relies on hazardous substances like cyanide and mercury, which upset the natural equilibrium by harming habitats, biodiversity, water bodies and health of humans (Guimaraes, Betancourt, Miranda, Barriga, Cueva, & Betancourt, 2011). Water resources are vulnerable to pollution from gold mining cyanide, acid mine drainage, heavy metals, and mercury (Martinez-Alier, 2002). Concerns about the illegal activities have long been voiced by researchers and policy makers, but attempts to address the somewhat irreversible effects have unintentionally stagnated (Hilson, 2000).

The water quality of Ghana's Densu and Pra basins has suffered greatly as a result of illegal mining, especially small-scale and artisanal mining (Darko, Karikari, Duah, Akurugu, Mante, & Teye, 2023; Mensah, Mahiri, Owusu, Mireku, Wireko, & Kissi, 2015). High concentrations of turbidity, colour, and total suspended solids have been the result, along with the presence of contaminants like iron and mercury (Darko et al., 2023). High concentrations of these elements in the environment due to the use of toxic elements in gold extraction processes have negative health effects, including fluorosis, intellectual disability, and cardiovascular diseases (Kazapoe, 2021).

In addition, pollution, deforestation, and unsustainable farming practices are contributing to the degradation of the Densu, an essential urban water source; resulting in high turbidity and nutrient loads (Attua, Ayamga, & Pabi, 2014; Amoako, Karikari, Ansa-Asare, & Adu-Ofori, 2010). Many issues with water quality and quantity are being brought about by the actions of farmers, particularly large-scale commercial farmers in the river's catchment, who use a lot of fertiliser and other chemicals in their operations. Due to increased industrialisation, intensification of agricultural practices, and growing population densities, the Densu River is currently among the most polluted rivers in the nation (Duncan, Oti, & Potakey, 2019; WRC, 2003).

The ignorance of the impoverished and illiterate regarding the cumulative effects of their actions on the environment frequently encourages negative human practices. One major problem is the lack of strong legal frameworks and rights for communities (Armah, et al 2013), coupled with ineffective enforcement of environmental laws and the poor interagency coordination (Jonah, Adams, Aheto, Jonah, & Mensah, 2017) exacerbates the problems.

The intricacy of those negative practices, and inadequacies in policy implementation have impeded the government's ability to address these issues (Kervankiran et al 2016). A multifaceted strategy will be needed to address these problems, including increased regulation enforcement, sustainable mining methods, and community involvement in decision-making.

Addressing perceptions of individuals is crucial to effectively address the problems connected to water quality and ecosystem services. Policymakers and researchers must engage effectively when public behaviour changes are required to manage water resources (Larson, Stoeckl, Neil, & Welters, 2013).

Efforts are being made globally to determine the economic values of ecosystems services in order to implement conservation strategies and improve decision making regarding the efficient use of water and encouraging public participation in water governance (Young & Loomis, 2014). Despite the importance of the Densu and Pra basins in Ghana in the supply of ecosystem services that support the socioeconomic and cultural growth and development of the country (Antwi-Agyakwa, 2014; Anornu, Kabo-bah, & Anim-Gyampo, 2012; Amoako, Karikari, Ansa-Asare, & Adu-Ofori, 2010), to the best of my knowledge, the economic value of water-related ecosystem services supplied by the two basins has not been studied.

The facts above underscore the following research questions: What is level of environmental awareness and views of respondents in the Pra and Densu basins? What are their perceptions about activities that pose risk to the basins? Are respondents willing to pay for essential water-related ecosystem services (flood control, erosion control, surface water quality, fish abundance and species, and cultural services)? Does preference and willingness to support payments for water-related ecosystem services differ based on the payment vehicle?

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to determine the economic value of Water-related ecosystem services associated with the Pra and Densu River basins in Ghana, as well as the perception of risks by households in both basins.

The specific objectives are:

1. Explore the environmental awareness and views of respondents.

2. Examine the respondents' perception of the risks of human activities to the water environment.
3. Estimate the preference for and value of prioritised water-related ecosystem services (flood control, erosion control, surface water quality, fish abundance and species, and cultural services).
4. Examine the change in preference and value as a result of the change in payment vehicle for ecosystem services.

1.5 Hypotheses of the Study

Stemming from the objectives as mentioned above, the following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. H₀: Respondents' sociodemographic characteristics do not influence their environmental awareness.

H₁: Respondents' sociodemographic characteristics influence their environmental awareness.

2. H₀: Respondents are not willing to pay for improved levels of water-related ecosystem services (flood control, erosion control, surface water quality, fish abundance and species, and cultural services).

H₁: Respondents are willing to pay for improved levels of water-related ecosystem services (flood control, erosion control, surface water quality, fish abundance and species, and cultural services).

3. H₀: Using labour days does not result in higher WTP for water-related ecosystem services (WES)

H₁: Using labour days will result in higher WTP for water-related ecosystem services (WES)

1.6 Relevance of the Study

This study seeks to contribute to the knowledge foundation and ability needed to integrate climate change (CC) and residents' perspectives into Water Resource Management (WRM) of Densu and Pra basins to improve resilience to climate change, living standards, water, food, and energy security, as well as conservation of the environment. For a successful policy design and execution, multidisciplinary knowledge is essential (United Kingdom National Ecosystem Assessment [UK NEA], 2011). This study should make available information to integrate into WRM issues related to agricultural extension policies to ensure the sustainable use of our water resources. The output will also directly contribute to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals, particularly goals 1 (no poverty), 6 (clean water and sanitation), and 13 (climate action).

Secondly, this study seeks to create an information pool to improve upon the valuation of water-related resources and the services that result from them to make ecosystem management much easier. Water supply and quality policy can have enormous economic implications for individuals, communities, farms, and businesses. Water is being allocated to fewer valuable uses in many parts of the world, water quality is declining, groundwater basins are overexploited, water-related ecosystem services are underserved, and floods and droughts are wreaking unduly heavy tolls on life and property. Moreover, increased water demand and

increased variability in water supply are expected if climate change projections are accurate (Young & Loomis, 2014). Future population growth, combined with climate change, is anticipated to exacerbate existing water resource management issues. As a result, understanding the economic values of water in alternative uses will be increasingly vital for water managers and government agencies in order to make the most of limited water resources, i.e., efficiently distribute available water to maximise its value to society.

Finally, policymakers or regulators can take advantage of farmers' shared perceptions by directing extension activities towards ES that are already well-known socially and economically (Brooks, Smith, Holland, Poppy, Eigenbrod, 2014). On the other hand, when respondents' views do not match the literature on valuation and risk perceptions, extension programmes can be directed by policies to close knowledge gaps and maximise resource use. Increased qualitative research on farmer attitudes will better inform both of these avenues.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter reviews literature relevant to the study. The section starts with a review of concepts of ecosystem services, water-related ecosystem services (WES), and discrete choice experiments. The section also reviews theoretical and empirical literature to give a proper foundation for the study.

2.2 The Concept of Ecosystem Services

There has been a recent surge in the concept and importance of ecosystem services (ES) among environmentalists and policymakers (Costanza, D'Arge, de Groot, Farber, Grasso, Hannon, Limburg, & Naeem et al., 2017). The advantages that come from ecosystems that improve human well-being in all spheres of life are known as ES (MEA, 2005; TEEB, 2010). Despite significant advancements in developing and implementing the ES framework for ecosystem-based management (EBM), much debate on the best approach to ES assessment and the development of a comprehensive framework is still ongoing. To expand on the MEA and TEEB definitions of ES and emphasise transdisciplinary knowledge for understanding the connections between people and nature, the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) maintains the "nature's contributions to people" concept (Remoundou, Diaz-Simal, Koundouri, & Rulleau, 2015).

To measure and evaluate ES, there is a need to propose a system of classification. MEA, TEEB, and IPBES have proposed the creation of these classification systems. The Common International Classifications for Ecosystem Services (CICES) has been established as a

reference classification system to facilitate interdisciplinary research by providing a shared language and preventing double counting (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2017). This research adheres to the CICES nomenclature.

Water-related ecosystem services (WES) offer a plethora of advantages that cover the three types of ecosystem services identified by the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) to include provisioning, regulation, and maintenance, as well as cultural services (Haines-Young & Potschin 2017). WES play a critical role in supporting human wellbeing, particularly with about a third of the global population residing along the coast and isolated islands. However, the intensification of human activities places immense pressure on WES, which are open to various related factors of change leading to degradation and loss (de Groot et al., 2010).

According to a study by Villasante, Pita, Rodrigues, Castelao and Pita (2020), and Troell, Joyce, Chopin, Neori, Buschmann, and Fang (2009), several factors are responsible for the deteriorating state of the world's water bodies. These factors include aquaculture development, overfishing, and shipping, which often give rise to land-based activities such as nutrient loading from agricultural activities and urbanisation, as well as globalisation and climate change. These drivers have significantly impacted global fish stocks, which are at risk of collapsing due to anthropogenic factors (Villasante, Pita, Rodrigues, Castelao & Pita, 2020). Since fish provide a significant source of animal protein for over 3.1 billion people, the rising demand for fish is driven by increasing prosperity and population growth, resulting in the rapid expansion of aquaculture as a solution to maintain the provisioning service of natural fishing stocks without compromising their capacity (Troell et al., 2009). However, aquaculture has also become a significant driver of change in water systems.

2.3 Water-Related Ecosystem Services

Water remains an important life-supporting element on the earth and a productive resource for ecosystems (Molles, 2008). Nevertheless, freshwater resources keep dwindling in the wake of ongoing climate change (Mekonnen & Hoekstra, 2016; Collins, Knutti, Arblaster, Dufresne, & Fichefet, et al., 2013). From the perspective of ecosystems, water availability and quality are determined by ecosystem factors such as soil type, flora, and fauna.

The water ecosystem supplies both direct and indirect services for human consumption. In the case of direct services, attention is placed on the services naturally provided by water. That is, drinking, household usage, flood control, checking erosion, and recreation, among others (CICES, 2018; Keeler, Polasky, Brauman, Johnson, & Finlay et al., 2012). The indirect role covers ecosystem services that do not directly emanate from water ecosystems but are critical to the functionality of the ecosystem, and these are soil, vegetation, the availability of animals' support, and the activities of humans, which are all under the control of water (Molles Jr., 2008). The provision of essentials such as food (including fish and fish products), timber, and other raw materials (provisioning ecosystem services) (CICES, 2018). Additionally, water regulates soil processes, temperature, and other biophysical services (Keeler et al., 2012). It is also important to acknowledge the role water plays in cultural values, aesthetics, tourism, recreation, and spirituality (CICES, 2018; Haines-Young & Potschin, 2017).

According to Grizzetti, LanzaNova, Liqueste, Reynaud and Cardoso (2016), pressures on water ecosystems can alter water quantity and quality. When water is scarce or of poor quality, it can significantly impact the overall usability of ecosystems and the delivery of water-related services (Keeler et al., 2012; Brauman, Daily, Duarte, & Mooney, 2007). In areas where water availability has been reduced due to high demand for consumption and irrigation or naturally

low precipitation levels, altered water quantity can substantially affect human welfare (Mekonnen & Hoekstra, 2016; Leemans and Kleidon, 2002).

Numerous water-related services are impacted both directly and indirectly by the amount of water (Brauman, Daily, Duarte, & Mooney, 2007). Water for consumption, irrigation, industrial use, hydropower generation, waste control, flood control, and salinisation prevention are directly affected by water quantity (Karabulut, Egoh, Lanzaova, Grizzetti, & Bidoglio et al., 2016). Moreover, water quantity indirectly affects ecosystem functioning, which subsequently affects other services such as commercial or recreational fishing, local climate regulation, and eutrophication (Grizzetti, Lanzaova, Liqueste, Reynaud, & Cardoso, 2016).

Water quality is a crucial factor affecting water-related ecosystem services (WES) and water quantity (Keeler et al., 2012). Water quality directly impacts various ecosystem services, including water purification, nitrogen removal by micro-organisms, sediment retention by aquatic vegetation, and prevention of soil erosion (Vigiak, Malagó, Bouraoui, Grizzetti, Weissteiner, & Pastori, 2016; Lautenbach, Maes, Kattwinkel, Seppelt, & Strauch et al., 2012). In addition, it indirectly affects other ecosystem services such as water for drinking, waterborne disease prevention, and recreation services (Rankinen, Butterfield, Faneca Sánchez, Grizzetti, & Whitehead et al., 2016; Keeler et al., 2012). In highly urbanised and industrialised areas or intensively farmed land, water quality may be compromised due to the discharge of agrochemicals, putting water-related services under pressure (Carpenter, Mooney, Agard, Capistrano, & Defries et al., 1998). Climate change further exacerbates water quality issues by causing wide disparities in water quantity, higher water temperatures, and increased frequencies of algal blooms (Whitehead, Wilby, Battarbee, Kernan, & Wade, 2009).

2.4 Review of Relevant Concepts and Discrete Choice Experiment Issues

The first step involves the identification of attributes and their levels that define the goods or services being evaluated. This was done through a literature review, expert consultations, focus group discussions, and pilot surveys (Greiner, Bliemer, & Ballweg, 2014). The second step involves selecting an experimental design to generate the choice sets. This can be a full factorial design or a fractional factorial design, depending on the number of attributes and levels involved (Holmes, Adamowicz, & Carlsson, 2017). The third step entails the construction of choice sets by combining the attribute levels selected in the previous step. This step requires careful consideration of the number of choice sets, the number of alternatives in each set, and the experimental design used (Greiner, Bliemer, & Ballweg, 2014).

The fourth step involves the development of a questionnaire to collect data from the respondents. The questionnaire should include the choice sets as well as sociodemographic questions and attitudinal statements that are used to clarify the choice behaviour of the respondents (Holmes, Adamowicz, & Carlsson, 2017). The last step involves estimating the parameters of interest using econometric models. Different models can be used depending on the research questions, the experimental design, and the nature of the data collected (Greiner, Bliemer, & Ballweg, 2014).

2.4.1 Identification and Description of Attributes

In this process, it is imperative that discussions are held with key stakeholders in the study area, such as scientists, resource managers, and potential respondents, to identify attributes that are important to them and also to generate the levels for each of the attributes. During the focus

group discussions, participants are guided to explain the attributes of goods and services that come to mind and that they do not want to lose due to policy implementation.

Attribute levels must be itemised as soon as attributes are finalised. This presents varied challenges, just as in identifying the attributes. The difficulty in stating attribute levels depends on the attributes. Identifying attributes can be straightforward or challenging, such as determining appropriate levels and ranges for improving water species quality.

Moreover, the difficulty in stating the attribute levels is common with price or cost specifications for improving the attributes. Price or cost attributes are a very important component of DCEs as they are the basis for measuring welfare impacts of choices, and as such, accurate prediction of their levels will facilitate econometric model estimation and draw policy-relevant inferences.

2.4.2 Design of Choice Experiments

In DCEs, the challenge lies in determining the number of alternatives in each choice set and the number of respondents to choose from, based on the research context and measured value category. Choice sets should include at least two alternatives, preferably the current state and an alternative indicating improvement from it. Utility changes from baseline conditions are determined by the baseline; most passive-use value studies identify two alternative options because they are compatible with referendum incentives (Carson & Groves, 2007).

The researcher must consider the complexity of the design due to the numerous options and choice sets, as respondents may use shortcuts that do not reflect their genuine preferences. Experimental designs for CEs aim to identify each preference parameter by allocating attribute

levels to alternatives and choice sets. The design should guarantee adequate independent variation among attribute levels, both within and between alternatives, to achieve this goal. If the levels of an attribute are always the same across options, it becomes impossible to determine its effect on responses. Additionally, the design should be statistically efficient to maximise the precision of parameter estimates while minimising errors.

The choice set for a study typically depends on the intricate nature of the set objectives. The researcher is given the chance to select the number of choice sets based on FGD, literature review, questionnaire pretesting, and expert input. The choice set selection depends on the model's degree of freedom and the compatibility of incentives when using multiple choice sets (Carson & Groves, 2007).

The task involves assigning attribute levels to alternatives as the basis for choices and creating sets of options for respondents to choose from (Street & Viney, 2019). Alternatives provided to respondents must have enough variance across attribute levels to allow preference parameters linked to the characteristics to be identified. In most circumstances, it will be difficult to provide all potential combinations of qualities and levels. As a result, experimental design approaches are employed to determine which subsets of the potential combinations perfectly distinguish attribute preferences.

2.4.2.1 Orthogonal Full Factorial Designs

Full factorial designs are complete experimental designs where every attribute and all its corresponding levels are combined (Hensher, Shore, & Train, 2005). The advantage of complete experimental designs is that they ensure all the main and interaction effects of the experiment are orthogonal (statistically independent) and are identified in estimated models.

However, the number of alternatives gets larger as more and more attributes and levels are added. This makes it difficult and time-wasting for respondents.

2.4.2.2 Orthogonal Fractional Factorial Designs

Given that full factorial orthogonal designs become extremely large as the number of attributes and levels increases, fractional factorial design has become the necessary option to reduce the number of designs to be presented to respondents. Using higher-order interaction terms, fractional factorial designs construct simple designs by selecting a few alternatives using the appropriate combination of attributes and levels (Hensher, Shore, & Train, 2005).

Reducing the design size in fractional factorial designs may, however, lead to the omission of some or all interaction terms. Suppose interactions that are important in explaining responses are left out. Utility changes are influenced by the status quo option; however, because of referendum compatibility, studies frequently incorporate two alternative choices, which may introduce bias into preference parameter estimates. Because a fractional factorial design has the potential to produce biased parameter estimates on the main effects and may fail to find significant relationships, it is critical to define which attribute interactions are crucial throughout the survey development design stage.

2.4.3 Model Estimation for Choice Experiments

Following data collection, a random utility model is used to estimate preference parameters. To assess choice data, an increasing prevalence of econometric specifications has been applied. These models frequently differ in how the error term is understood, especially when respondents' preferences are heterogeneous (Hensher, Shore, & Train, 2005).

2.4.4 Welfare Measures for Marginal Effects in Choice Experiments

In choice experiments, the focal point is to determine the welfare impact of variations in the attributes of ecosystem services that are being valued (Pelyukh & Zahvoyska, 2017; Lienhoop & Völker, 2016). To derive these effects, analysts usually use the simplest form of the utility function by assuming constant marginal utility of income. The concentration is usually on discrete choices, implying that welfare measures must be interpreted with caution in some circumstances (Hensher, Shore, & Train, 2005).

2.5 Theoretical Review

2.5.1 Consumer Theory

Dannenberg (2018) noted that consumer theory, which is concerned with understanding how consumer behaviour affects the demand for commodities in the market, was first introduced through Gossen's Law of Consumer Behaviour in 1871. The theory assumes that consumers aim to maximise their utility preferences within their budget constraints, taking into account the prices of the available commodities. The key import of the theory is to determine the consumption possibilities that will enable consumers to achieve the highest level of satisfaction possible given their budget constraints.

Consumer theory, which aims to understand how consumer behaviour affects demand in the market, was first introduced through Gossen's Law of Consumer Behaviour in 1871 (Gorbunov, 2021; Dannenberg, 2018). This theory assumes that individuals have coherent preferences and seek to maximise utility within the constraints of their budget. The assumption

is that there are a finite number of commodities available for purchase, each with specific prices assigned to them (Mas-Colell, Whinston, & Green, 1995).

When examining how people's tastes, preferences, and incomes affect the economy, the consumer theory is a useful tool. Specifically, the theory of customer choice is concerned with analysing consumers' decisions regarding what to buy and how much to spend, taking into account their consumption preferences and budget constraints. This is accomplished by researching how consumers, taking into account their preferences and limited resources, maximise satisfaction from the consumption choices they make (Guagnano, 2001).

The primary actor is the consumer, as in the present situation, a producer may produce a good that they are unable to consume themselves (Falk & Fischbacher, 2006). The models that constitute the consumer theory are employed to analyse theoretically observable demand patterns based on the principle of maximising utility for an individual consumer through optimisation.

According to Andersson et al. (2006), the concept of willingness to pay for water catchment conservation decreases as the minimum payment increases in relation to income levels. The theory suggests that as the level of conservation increases, people will opt for alternative options, which may have detrimental effects on the conserved ecosystem (Nyongesa, Bett, Lagat, & Ayuya, 2016). When the cost of conservation increases without a corresponding reward, there is a decrease in purchasing power, leading to a further decrease in demand, and individuals may choose to forego some conservation activities to maintain their wage levels (Hope, 2006). Furthermore, as individual material resources increase, the demand for more items is realised, suggesting that individual income levels significantly influence their willingness to pay for the conservation of water catchment zones. (Hope, 2006).

Overall, this study supports the consumer theory's behavioural explanation, which posits that all consumers aim to maximise utility through rational behaviour. Neoclassical economists suggest that consumers seek to maximise a utility benefit within the constraints of their limited budget (Hanley, Shogren, & White, 2007). Therefore, consumer theory generates hypotheses about the nature of consumer demand from this behavioural hypothesis.

To enhance the central hypothesis of valuable consumer choice, it is crucial to establish additional assumptions about the specific consumer behaviours when choosing conservation bundles. These behaviours include their willingness to pay for monthly payments, which are relatively strict assumptions that allow for the development of more accurate theories about customer behaviour than weaker assumptions would. Weaker assumptions would fail to provide meaningful predictions of future demand based on experimental data and would, therefore, be less useful in informing conservation efforts (Guagnano, 2001).

2.5.2 Theory of Welfare Change

Adam Smith, an economist, proposed the theory of welfare change in 1776, which includes two key assumptions: the existence of the invisible hand and a fundamental relationship between economic factors. This theory suggests that economic factors swing between low and high returns through the distribution of resources that promote economic wellbeing. Carson and Mitchel (1993) assert that natural resources are valued based on their impact on human welfare to measure their benefits and influences on individual utilities. Changes can affect people's welfare in various ways, such as changes in product costs, factors of production costs, other public goods' quantity and quality, and environmental goods that can endanger livelihoods (Freeman, 2003).

The primary objective of producer strategies is to allocate resources in a way that advances social welfare. Allocative efficiency is regarded as the most appropriate criterion for evaluating welfare in public goods or resource allocation decisions since it ensures that no individual can benefit without causing harm to another. The Pareto improvement principle is the foundation of this concept, stating that the benefits of public intervention outweigh its costs. Perman, R., and Stern (2003) assert that efficient allocations ensure no one benefits without another, while unproductive ones can improve one's welfare without affecting others. The use of a surrogate market can address this issue, but contingent valuation accuracy is often undermined by income effects (Bennett and Blamey, 2001).

Furthermore, the use of the contingent valuation method (CV) as a measure of welfare change can be unreliable due to the greater elasticity of environmental or public goods compared to market products, as noted by Bateman et al. (2002). Hence, a more precise and unambiguous measure of welfare is necessary. To address this issue, Hicks developed four alternative welfare measures as refinements of the standard Marshallian demand functions (Baumol, 1972). These measures, known as Hicksian welfare compensation measures, assume that the consumer's utility level remains unchanged before and after a change in the provision of natural services.

The maximisation problem's duality is defined by the use function given the standard demand function. The individual is expected to minimise consumption while maintaining a certain level of utility. Hicksian demand functions are used to solve minimisation problems, determining quantities purchased at different prices to maintain utility levels (Freeman, 2003). Four alternative welfare measures are based on these functions:

Compensating Variation (CV): This measure is based on price changes at the initial utility level. CV is the compensation required to keep an individual at the initial utility level without the price change, assuming that the maximum willingness to pay decreases. In essence,

Markandya et al. (2002) define the concept of Compensating Variation (CV) as the monetary amount required by a consumer to maintain their utility level when faced with a price increase, at least equal to their willingness to accept (WTA). This is used when determining a compensation scheme at current prices, as it is based on a unique cost baseline.

Equivalent Variation (EV): According to Markandya et al. (2002), the EV welfare measure is defined by changes in prices at the current utility level. When prices decrease, EV is the additional income that a consumer would need to reach the same level of utility that they would achieve with their current income if prices decreased, with the decrease being at least WTA. On the other hand, if prices increase, EV is the amount of money that a consumer would be willing to pay to achieve the same level of utility that they currently have if prices increased. This measure captures the highest WTP of the individual to avoid price increases.

Consumer Surplus (CS): The Consumer Surplus (CS) is a welfare measure defined by changes in quality or quantity at the initial utility level. For an improvement, the CS is the amount of money that must be taken from the consumer's income to maintain their utility level as if there were no maximum willingness-to-pay (WTP) for the environmental change. The CS is the amount given to a customer to maintain their utility level at the same point of usefulness, at least equal to the WTA.

Equivalent Surplus (ESU): The Equivalent Surplus (ESU) refers to the difference that exists relative to the quality or quantity of a good or service that affects an individual's level of utility. In cases of enhancement, ESU is the additional amount that a buyer is willing to pay to maintain the same level of utility in the presence of the change. This is measured by the minimum willingness to accept (WTA) value. In cases of degradation, ESU is the amount that needs to be subtracted from the buyer's income to bring them to the same level of utility as they would have had if the change had not occurred. This is measured by the maximum willingness to pay

(WTP) value to avoid degradation. Markandya et al. (2002) provide a comprehensive explanation of the concept of ESU.

2.5.3 The Theory of Value-Belief-Norm (VBN)

The Value-Belief-Norm (VBN) theory is a comprehensive theory concerning the environment that has been applied to various aspects, including attitudes, behaviour, and risk perception (Slimak & Dietz, 2006). The theory posits that environmental concern is driven by three main factors: (1) values, which are broad guiding principles that people hold, such as altruism or hedonism; (2) beliefs, which are specific beliefs about the environment and the consequences of human actions on the environment; and (3) norms, that are social norms and personal norms that dictate what people believe they should do to protect the environment (Dietz, Fitzgerald, & Shwom, 2005; Stern, 2000).

According to Slimak and Dietz (2006), the VBN theory explains differences in ecological risk perception. The VBN theory combines norm activation theory, personal values theory, and the new ecological paradigm to provide a comprehensive explanation for environmentalism. This integration resulted in a causal relationship between five variables: personal values, a general set of beliefs or worldviews, awareness of consequences, ascription of responsibility, and personal norms for pro-environmental action. Slimak and Dietz (2006) suggested adding spiritual values to the VBN model. Variations in consumer behaviour, support for policies, environmental citizenship, and awareness of the effects of both individual and collective actions have all been explained using the VBN theory (Dietz, Fitzgerald, & Shwom, 2005; Stern, 2000).

The VBN proposed that personal values, the new ecological paradigm, and spiritual beliefs interact to create a new understanding. The Causal model assumes that the perception of risk

will be operationalised through 11 specific ecological risk stressors and is influenced by values and general beliefs about the environment, including spiritual and religious beliefs.

Indeed, social structural influences such as gender, income and educational attainment have been found to have significant effects on risk perception. For example, studies indicated that women were inclined to perceive higher risks than men (Slovic, 1999) and that older individuals may perceive risks as higher than younger individuals (Slovic, 2000). Additionally, education and income have been found to have a positive relationship with risk perception (Flynn, Slovic, & Mertz, 1994). Therefore, it was important to consider those social structural factors when examining environmental risk perception.

2.6 Economic Valuation of Environmental Services and Goods

There is a body of literature that argues it is possible to establish the economic value of environmental goods (Dlamini, 2015). Financial valuation is a measure of the total budget that a person is willing to give up for other goods in the market. People's willingness to pay is a common indicator of welfare; that is, the cost of environmental degradation is equal to the amount of money people are willing to spend on its restoration (Kadekodi, 2001). Valuing natural resources involves assessing society's preferences for public goods and a procedure used to put a monetary value on programme decisions and policy initiatives (Pearce, 1992). The estimation of the value of natural environmental goods has become more critical in recent years, as the government's role in the effective allocation of resources based on demand and population distribution has become significant. According to Navrud, Lindhjem, and Magnussen (2017), essential conservation and sustainable practices for public assets and natural resources are addressed directly when financial values are recognised.

Inadequate market access to environmental goods and services often leads to mismanagement and inefficient allocation of resources, as the value of these goods remains unrevealed (Kadekodi, 2001). Even when markets do exist, inefficiencies may persist due to externalities associated with ecosystem products that cannot be assigned by the markets themselves, especially when property rights are not clearly established (Haab & Mc Connell, 2002). In order to handle externalities and guarantee appropriate management, public goods like natural resources must have monetary values attached to them. Because of flaws in the market, prices may not accurately represent society's value of ecosystem services. By assigning monetary values to unmarketed products, environmental valuation techniques seek to determine the value that individuals place on these goods, presuming that consumers are willing to pay for environmental improvements and accept compensation for degradation (Hanley, Shogren, & White, 2007). The revealed preference (indirect) and stated preference (direct) approaches are the two primary types of environmental valuation techniques. The revealed preference approach infers value estimates by utilising market data pertaining to the non-marketed value under consideration while stated preference allows respondents to determine the value of goods (and services) (Turner & Pearce, 1990).

2.7 The New Ecological Paradigm (NEP) Scale as a Measure of Environmental Assessment (EA)

The purpose of the NEP, in the opinion of Dunlap, Van Liere, Mertig, and Jones (2000), is that it evaluates the fundamental beliefs that are indicative of environmental attitudes (EA), as noted in studies by Hawcroft and Milfont (2010). The NEP scale has undergone several modifications and adaptations since its inception, creating various versions in the process (Manoli et al. 2007; Dunlap, Van Liere, Mertig, & Jones, 2000; Dunlap & Van Liere, 1978)

and after being tailored to various philosophies (Atav et al., 2015; Moyano-Diaz and Palomo-Vélez 2014; Ogunbode 2013; Corraliza et al. 2013; Pires et al., 2016). The initial 12-item version has been used along with the revised 15-item version (Dunlap, Van Liere, Mertig, & Jones, 2000), a truncated 6-item version (Dunlap, 2008; Hawcroft & Milfont, 2010), and a version customised for children (Manoli et al., 2007). These adaptations have allowed researchers to study environmental attitudes across a variety of cultural contexts. Additionally, Dunlap et al. (2000) proposed that the NEP scale estimates fundamental beliefs or worldviews that can serve as indicators of EA, a notion that has been supported by subsequent studies (Hawcroft & Milfont, 2010; Schultz, Gouveia, Cameron, Tankha, G., Schmuck, & Franěk, 2005).

In their recent study, Xiao and Buhrmann (2017) presented a multifaceted conceptualisation of the New Ecological Paradigm (NEP) that emphasised consistency and dimensionality. The authors argued that NEP reflects confidence in some economic limitations to growth and the predominance of ecological balance over human power relative to nature and that NEP scaling aims to uncover a wide range of ecological perspectives and environmental issues for assessing environmental concerns on a global level. Furthermore, Xiao and Buhrmann (2017) highlighted the importance of maintaining internal consistency and multidimensionality in NEP scaling to address issues related to conflicting and sample-focused environmental values. López-Bonilla and López-Bonilla (2016) found that ecocentrism and anthropocentrism play a crucial role in NEP conceptualisation. They emphasised the importance of NEP scaling as a novel and advanced tool to measure these conceptualisations in the form of Likert in order to get quick responses without enough thought. The NEP scaling composition was initially based on three categories: balancing nature, growth constraints, and humanitarian priorities over nature.

López-Bonilla and López-Bonilla (2016) described the NEP Scale as consisting of two main directions: ecocentric and anthropocentric views. An ecocentric view is based on the belief that nature has intrinsic value and that individuals recognise the significance of protecting it as a common good. In contrast, an anthropocentric view assumes that humans have the ability to manage nature and mitigate the negative effects of development on it. Their study used a five-point Likert scale for item measurement and Cronbach's alpha for reliability, but its validity was criticised for its lack of uni-dimensionality. Despite this criticism, the NEP scale was found to have a high degree of interrelatedness among its items.

The NEP Scale has been found to be unstable and varying across different contexts, as it is influenced by respondents' sociodemographic variables (Brennan, Binney, Aleti, & Parker, 2014). Furthermore, the validity of the NEP Scale has been criticised for its internal consistency, as measured by Cronbach's alpha, and its consistency over time. The NEP Scale, often considered a reliable and consistent indicator of environmental behaviour change precursors, is not always substantiated (Brennan, Binney, Aleti, & Parker, 2014). Additionally, there is debate regarding the dimensionality of the NEP Scale and its variability based on respondents' socioeconomic status (Brennan, Binney, Aleti, & Parker, 2014).

Despite varying opinions, some research indicates that the 6-, 12-, and 15-item NEP scales are regarded as interchangeable (Dunlap, 2008). A study using the revised NEP Scale in 14 countries found that the scale's reliability varied based on environmental attitudes, with an alpha coefficient ranging from 0.47 to 0.81 (Dunlap, 2008).

In some studies, it was found that the average NEP Scale score ranged from 3.67 (in the United States) to 4.11 (in Canada), indicating that personal values such as universalism and tradition have an impact on environmental attitudes (Dunlap, 2008). Another study reported a

Cronbach's alpha value of 0.61 when testing the reliability of the NEP Scale and suggested a dichotomy between an anthropocentric and a pro-ecological worldview (Dunlap, 2008).

2.8 Pro-Environmental and Socio-Cultural Viewpoints of the NEP Concept

Park et al. (2018) utilised a joint theoretical framework of the "Value-Belief-Norm" and the "Modified-Norm-Activation-Model" to assess the determinants of pro-environmental behavioural intention in the tourism sector. The study found that being proactive, responsible, having social and personal norms, and taking environmental precautions are key attributes that support environmental behaviours based on the NEP theory. The study also used a five-point Likert scale to evaluate item valuation, resulting in a highly predictive integrative model of tourists' pro-environmental intentions. The model suggests that people associate values such as biospheric and altruistic emanating from ecological awareness rather than egoistically attributed benefits such as social power and wealth, to solidify pro-environmental intention among tourists (Park et al., 2018).

Luo and Deng (2008) conducted a study to investigate NEP's measure of the relationship between environmental attitudes and what motivates tourists in China. Their findings indicated that there is a strong association between respondents' demographics and their NEP scores. Individuals who advocate for development limits and environmental concerns are more inclined towards nature-based tourism, promoting environmental education and escape from urban routines. These results align with previous research, which suggests that gender and education are consistent predictors of environmental values and attitudes.

Grůňová, Sané, Cincera, Kroufek, and Hejčmanová (2019) examined pro-environmental attitudes and environmental beliefs using the New Environmental Paradigm (NEP) Scale and argued that it could be valid globally. However, the study suggested that the NEP scaling may

not have universal applicability outside of Western developed countries, as pro-environmental behaviour in Asian communities is often attributed to traditional anthropogenic concerns rather than eco-centric motives. To address this, differentiated subscales were developed to account for cultural differences, and the consistency of the scale was determined using Cronbach's alpha confirmatory factor analysis. The study reported variations in responses to specific items due to differences in features related to culture, religion, and the worldview of humankind's place in nature, as well as a poor appreciation of the impact of humans on the resources of nature. The inconsistency is an indication of a variety of latent dimensions of the sample surveyed and low internal uniformity of the overall NEP scaling (Grůnová et al., 2018).

The NEP conceptualisation and its applicability to environmental attitudes were explored in several studies (Hawcroft & Milfont, 2010; Taskin, 2009). Taskin (2009) examined the "environmental attitudes of high school students in Turkey" and identified the factors influencing these attitudes. The study suggested that incorporating a NEP-driven environmental education model into the curriculum can lead to a shift towards non-materialistic values and increased environmental awareness among students. The use of the NEP Scale was found to be effective in understanding environmental attitudes, even among young students.

To elaborate, the NEP Scale has gained prominence in its measure of the universal frame of beliefs related to environmental attitudes (Dunlap, 2008). Hawcroft and Milfont (2010) emphasised the importance of environmental attitudes (EA) in evaluating nature as favourable or unfavourable, highlighting their critical role in environmental psychology.

Putrawan (2015) examined the New Environmental Paradigm (NEP) and Dominant Social Paradigm (DSP) environmental paradigms. DSP views natural resources as limitless, exploitable for human needs, while NEP acknowledges people's role in ecosystems and finite resources, contrasting with the anthropocentric approach that views resources as finite.

According to NEP, the components of the ecosystem are interrelated, and the destruction of one component can lead to the deterioration of the whole ecosystem. The study highlighted that the NEP consists of five dimensions, which are composed of different items and can be instrumental in reducing the DSP-driven conception and promoting a more positive NEP-driven conception. By adopting a more NEP-driven conception, the goal of achieving sustainable development can be achieved

To summarise, the NEP scale has been widely used to measure environmental attitudes across cultures and continents, with Grůňová, Sané, Cincera, Kroufek, and Hejcmanová (2019) arguing for its validity. However, the authors noted that there are variations in responses based on culture, religion, and perceptions of nature. The NEP scale is an excellent means for making decisions, with variables that support decision-making perspectives, including the manipulation of eco-crises and increased consciousness of global ecological challenges, the development of strong biospheric and altruistic values, the functionality of environmental attitudes as psychological motives, the scoring validity and comparison among varied decision plans, and the wide range of ecological worldviews and environmental values needed to validate plans and decisions of the environment based on NEP scaling worldwide.

2.9 Empirical Review

A number of studies have been conducted on environmental evaluation, including methodologies based on stated preferences aimed at improving the quality of water and the ecology of aquatic regions: rivers (Kataria et al., 2012; Soliño, Joyce, & Alvarez-Farizo, 2013; Metcalfe, Baker, Andrews, Atkinson, Bateman, & Butler et al., 2012; Kataria, 2009) and wetlands (Birol, Karousakis, & Koundouri, 2006). The majority of studies concentrating on

drinking water, such as improvements to domestic water quality, are also available (Day, Bateman, Carson, Dupont, & Louviere et al., 2012; Scarpa et al., 2012), recycling (Hurlimann & Mckay, 2006; Menegaki, Hanley, & Tsagarakis, 2007), household water usage (Fontdecaba, Grima, Marco, Rodero, & Sánchez-Espigares, 2012; Matos, Teixeira, Bento, Varajão, & Bentes, 2014), wastewater treatment (Birol & Das, 2010; Birol, Koundouri, & Kountouris, 2010), the willingness to pay motivated by the occurrence of drought (Hensher, Shore, & Train, 2006, 2005; Windle, Rolfe, & Brouwer, 2009), or the growing literature on improving water quality in developing countries (Tarfasa & Brouwer, 2013), among many others.

2.9.1 Discrete Choice Experiments and Willingness to Pay (WTP) for Ecosystem Services

One of the stated preference methods is the Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE), which is mainly used to capture preferences for a product. Attributes and their levels are combined to create different choices, with respondents selecting their preferred option. Although the method is considered to have a greater perceptive burden, it offers several benefits. Firstly, it indirectly elicits economic values from non-market attributes, minimising strategic responses from respondents. Secondly, it reduces ethical protesting compared to other methods. Thirdly, it has been found to provide more accurate estimates of nonmarket values, with the ability to estimate values for differences in a single attribute or stages of attributes. Fourthly, it also allows for a detailed comprehension of trade-offs between different attributes. Finally, by optimising the use of estimated parameters, experimental design theory improves statistical efficiency, allowing for smaller samples and lower implementation costs (Champ et al., 2017; Hanley, Mourato, & Wright, 2001; van Beukering and Cesar, 2004).

Willingness to pay (WTP) has been utilised both in Ghana and globally in the determination of the economic valuation of various natural resources, including nature parks, wetlands, forest reserves, lands used for agriculture, and marine resources. Oliveira et al. (2020) utilised a choice experiment to understand the community's preferences for managing the growing issue of erosion in Praia da Amorosa, Brazil. The study revealed that respondents preferred solutions to reduce the issue over no action and favoured simpler interventions such as walls and passageways rather than heavy infrastructure such as seawalls. The results also showed preference heterogeneity among the respondents, indicating the need for more flexible and complex models.

Duijndam et al. (2020) sought to determine the Simpson Bay Lagoon's economic worth in the Eastern Caribbean region of Saint Martin. The lagoon has been negatively impacted by a number of environmental problems, including overdevelopment, pollution, and intensive development. Using a choice experiment as part of a larger household survey, the authors found that the environmental state of the lagoon is currently worth approximately US\$12.1 million per year to the residents of Saint Martin. The study also assessed the potential welfare benefits of improving environmental management, considering two scenarios: the installation of a sewage treatment plant and mangrove restoration. Results showed that the economic value would increase to US\$16.5 million a year with the fixing of a plant for the treatment of sewage, to US\$23.0 million per year with mangrove restoration, and to US\$26.3 million per year with the implementation of both measures. In conclusion, the study highlights the potential for improved environmental management to benefit the environment, society, and economy of Saint Martin through enhancing the ecological integrity of the Simpson Bay Lagoon.

In Mida Creek, Kenya, Owuor et al. (2019) conducted a study that employed a deliberative choice experiment to evaluate the value of mangrove biodiversity and ecosystem services. The

study evaluated the non-market mangrove ecosystem's services, including protection against erosion, fish breeding, and biodiversity richness. The method for estimating willingness to pay (WTP) involved utilising volunteer time for mangrove conservation. The results indicate that respondents were ready to offer varying amounts of time per month to preserve different mangrove ecosystem services, such as nursery and breeding ground functions, increased biodiversity richness and abundance, reduction of shoreline erosion, and an increase in student and researcher visits.

In 2020, Chepkwony, Ipara, and Odwori employed the choice experiment approach in their study in Nandi County. The study aimed to provide valuable information for conservationists and policymakers to develop effective measures for the preservation of the wetland, which is home to rare Sitatunga antelopes facing population decline resulting from growing activities of human. The results of the study showed that the average willingness-to-pay by household a year for Kingwal wetland was Ksh. 549,442 (US \$5494.42), with direct benefits contributing the highest monetary value (Ksh. 292,010), followed by indirect benefits (Ksh. 112,561), option benefits (Ksh. 62,649), bequest benefits (Ksh. 26,125), and existence values (Ksh. 56,097). These findings highlight the importance of Kingwal Wetland to the surrounding community and provide insight into the economic value of its ecosystem services (Chepkwony, Ipara, & Odwori, 2020). The study suggested that it is necessary to increase awareness about the economic value of wetland benefits to people. This could be achieved through public education campaigns and the use of media platforms. The findings of the study can assist policymakers and conservationists in making informed decisions on the conservation of Kingwal Wetland and also emphasise the need for proper management practices to maintain its ecological services.

Tan, Lv, Cheng, Wang, Mo, and Xiang (2018) conducted a study aimed at evaluating the economic value of environmental improvements resulting from coastal wetland restoration in the Ximen Island Special Marine Protected Area in China. To achieve this, the researcher employed the discrete choice experiment, a stated preference method, to estimate the welfare changes by providing different coastal wetland restoration scenarios. A sample of 201 respondents was sampled for live interview sessions. The individual utility associated with wetland attributes was estimated using both the conditional logit model and the random parameter logit model.

The findings of the study suggested that the restoration of coastal wetlands would have a positive impact on the environment, as it could enhance the expansion of mangroves and the quality of water and biodiversity. The attribute with the highest marginal willingness to pay value was the mangrove area, indicating that it was the most important attribute that needed consideration in the restoration strategy design. The study calculated the compensating surplus of specified wetland restoration scenarios, which increased from modest to ambitious coastal wetland restoration scenarios. The results of the study provide valuable insights for policymakers in determining the most effective coastal wetland restoration strategy for the Ximen Island Special Marine Protected Area. The findings could also be useful in raising awareness among the local community regarding the economic value of coastal wetland restoration and the need for its conservation. The study contributes to the existing literature on the economic valuation of ecosystem services. It highlights the importance of using stated preference methods, such as the discrete choice experiment, in assessing the economic value of environmental improvements.

In order to determine preferences for various options for managing coastal areas in the Coromandel Peninsula, New Zealand, Matthews et al. (2017) conducted a discrete choice

experiment. The study focused on three attributes: erosion protection, headland development, and expense. Conflicting views between property owners and local government were investigated, with property owners favouring complex coastal defence structures and the local government preferring the preservation of landscapes and recreation activities. The study discovered that, generally speaking, WTP values for different beach attributes were not affected by the size of those attributes. The random parameter logit models indicated significant preference heterogeneity within the sample, highlighting the need to consider the diverse preferences of different groups in coastal management decision-making processes, particularly with regard to beach attributes.

Oduor et al. (2016) used the contingent valuation survey method to estimate the willingness to pay (WTP) for the conservation of Nyando wetlands in the Lake Victoria basin, Kenya, which were facing increasing anthropogenic activities. It was revealed that 83% were willing to pay for wetland conservation, with an aggregated WTP of KES 38 million (US\$ 0.4 million) per year. The study also identified significant determinants of WTP, such as gender, age, household size, and education. The results of this study suggest that local communities value wetland conservation and that policy interventions should consider the determinants of WTP to promote effective conservation efforts.

Similar findings have been reported in other studies, such as those conducted by Czajkowski, Zagórska, Letki, Tryjanowski, and Wąs (2019). Czajkowski, Zagórska, Letki, Tryjanowski, and Wąs (2019) used a contingent valuation method to estimate WTP for the restoration of wetlands in Poland. The study found that respondents were willing to pay a mean WTP of PLN 73.7 (US\$ 19.3) per household per year for wetland restoration.

Remoundou, Diaz-Simal, Koundouri, and Rulleau (2015) conducted a study in Santander, Spain, using a discrete choice experiment to assess the preference for risk management

strategies associated with the coast resulting from climate change. The study focused on two types of climate change effects: (1) flooding and coastal erosion and (2) changes in marine biodiversity and the likelihood of jellyfish blooms caused by rising sea temperatures. The study used a random parameter logit model to analyse the data and found that residents were willing to accept a payment meant to mitigate harmful effects on health and nature. The preferred mitigation measures included beach nourishment and improvements to existing structures to protect the beach.

Ndetewio (2013) suggested that willingness to pay for watershed services could be influenced by family size and the size of inhabitants in the area. Larger families may require more food production and irrigation, leading to a higher willingness to pay among farmers. Ma et al. (2012) noted that farmers' willingness to participate in payment for ecosystem services (PES) programmes depends mainly on their farm and farming characteristics. Farmers with larger plots may be willing to pay more than those with smaller plots. While age was positively related to willingness to pay, it was not a significant predictor. Ma et al. (2012) found that education, household family size, and age of the respondents had negative effects on consumers' willingness to pay for domestic water services in Kelantan, Indonesia. Ogunniyi et al. (2011) found that household income had a negative and significant effect on willingness to pay for improved water quantity.

Gachoki (2010) employed a choice experiment methodology to examine public preferences for wetland attributes in the Olbolosat wetland in Central Kenya. The study discovered that the selection of wetland alternatives was significantly influenced by factors such as farm size, distance from the wetland, household income, and educational attainment. The study suggests including communities in the management of wetlands, regulating land sizes close to fragile

ecosystems, and educating communities on the appreciation of the benefits of the Lake Olbolosat wetland socio-ecological system.

In Poland, Birol, Karousakis, and Koundouri (2006) conducted a study using the CEM to evaluate the advantages of reducing flood risk and determine the value of biodiversity and the demand of local households for recreational activities in the region. The study found that households valued reducing flood risk to a low level the most, followed by recreational activities and biodiversity conservation. These findings provide important insights for the proper management of rivers and policies in the region to ensure they are efficient and effective.

The contingent valuation method was used by Su et al. (2018) to estimate the economic value of ecosystem services in the Xijiang River basin of China. According to the study, households have an average annual willingness to pay of CNY 150; important determinants included water use behaviour, education level, and income.

Studies by Bell, Matthews, and Zhang (2016) and Aguilar, Obeng, Obeng, and Cai (2018) , both stress on the significance of water quality in fostering ecosystem services, with Bell emphasising the role of the WEF Nexus perspective in identifying beneficiaries of improved agricultural practices and Aguilar proposing that PES programmes should be customised to local needs. Both Abebe, Dagnew, Zeleke, Eshetu, and Cirella Abebe (2019) and Chaikaew, Hodges, and Grunwald (2017) investigate the willingness to pay for ecosystem services; Abebe finds that Ethiopian households and organisations have a high level of willingness, while Chaikaew identifies nutrient control as the most crucial service in the Suwannee River Basin. Together, these studies provide credence to the idea that agricultural catchments should be encouraged to provide ecosystem services through policy and financial incentives.

Overall, these studies highlight the importance of considering the preferences of local residents when designing policies for improving water resources. They also provide valuable information on the willingness of households to pay for various water-related ecosystem services, which can be used to influence decisions and policies.

2.9.2 Non-Monetary Payment Vehicles in Valuation Studies

A recent study suggests that in low-income countries, the WTP for environmental protection may be zero due to budget constraints (Kassahun, Jacobsen, & Nicholson, 2020). However, the payment method used to reflect preferences for ecosystem services may not be appropriate for these countries (Kassahun, Jacobsen, & Nicholson, 2020). To address this issue, recent studies have advocated for the usage of non-monetary formats to measure utility in developing countries (Navrud & Vondolia, 2020; Tadesse, Alfnes, Erenstein, & Holden, 2017; Kassahun, Jacobsen, & Nicholson, 2020; Amare et al., 2016; Gibson, Rigby, Polya, & Russell, 2016; Abramson, Becker, Garb, & Lazarovitch, 2011). Ahlheim et al. (2010) argue that using non-monetary payment modes can reduce the proportion of zero bids, protest choices, and the selection of the status quo option in Choice Experiments (CE).

Even though there are difficulties when utilising labour and other non-monetary payment methods as cost contributors in stated preference surveys (Rai & Scarborough, 2015), there is growing interest in the use of non-monetary valuations. Moreover, recent research has shown that incorporating non-monetary values, such as the willingness to provide volunteer labour, can significantly impact the estimated value of ecosystem services. For instance, Vondolia and Navrud (2017) found that permitting respondents to indicate their willingness to accept volunteer labour can increase the estimated value of ecosystem services. Additionally,

depending on the context, respondents may prefer to donate their labour rather than give monetary donations (Alam, 2006; Hung, Loomis, & Thinh, 2007; Vondolia, Eggert, Navrud, & Stage, 2014). In some cases, non-cash payment modes, such as in-kind commodities like rice and beehives, have been used to address the issue of cash constraints (Vondolia & Eggert, 2017).

Studies have repeatedly demonstrated that some groups are more likely to donate labour than money. Households in rural developing areas are more willing to work than to pay for better drinking water quality (Gibson, Rigby, Polya, & Russell, 2016). The discovery that workers in the nonprofit sector are more likely than those in the for-profit sector to donate their labour, as indicated by unpaid overtime, lends more credence to this (Gregg, Grout, Ratcliffe, Smith, & Windmeijer, 2008). Finally, the availability of childcare facilities and regional labour market conditions play a significant role in the willingness of East German women to work compared to West German women (Grundig, 2006). Depending on the context, respondents may prefer giving labour support to monetary donations (Martin-Ortega, Ferrier, & Gordon, 2015).

Contingent valuation studies have explored the use of non-cash payment modes, such as in-kind commodities like rice and beehives, to address cash constraints in low-income communities. Brouwer, Akter, Brander, and Haque (2009) and Fuks (2008) both used the Contingent Valuation (CV) approach to study the impact of in-kind payment modes on willingness to pay for flood control policy in Bangladesh and Brazil, respectively. Brouwer, Akter, Brander, and Haque (2009) found that a combined monetary and non-monetary measure of willingness to pay (WTP) could lower the number of zero bids, while Fuks and Chatterjee (2008) identified several limitations of the CV method in low-income areas. Sehreen, Masud, Akhtar, and Masum (2019), and Navrud, Tuan, and Tinh (2012) also used the CV approach to study willingness to pay for improved water pollution management in Dhaka and the welfare

loss from natural disasters in Vietnam, respectively. Both studies found that socio-economic factors and perception significantly influence WTP.

Similarly, Ando et al. (2020) found that participants in a contingent assessment of stormwater management in two significant U.S. cities voluntarily contributed one-third of the average wage rate. In order to ascertain the preferences of smallholder farmers in developing nations with respect to flood risk mitigation and flood insurance attributes, Vondolia and Navrud (2019) employed a contingent evaluation. They found that non-monetary payment modes, such as labour and harvest payment modes, were equally acceptable to respondents as monetary payment modes. However, the relative scale parameters of non-monetary payment vehicles were lower than those of monetary payment vehicles.

A number of CV studies reveal that the expected willingness to offer labour will likely exceed the WTP. Numerous studies back up the conclusion that people are more willing to give time than money. According to research by Helvoort-Postulart et al (2008), and Liu and Aaker, (2008), the willingness to sacrifice time is on par with, if not greater than, the willingness to pay. Saini and Monga (2007) go on to say that people's willingness to give time is influenced by decision-making, which is more heuristic in this regard. According to Bekkers (2002), volunteering and financial contributions to charities are frequently complementary, with volunteers being more likely to give their time. All of these studies emphasise the value of time as a resource and its potential to make a substantial contribution. Lankia et al. (2014) also found that respondents' WTP was higher in terms of labour than income.

The Contingent Valuation (CV) method is not the only approach to assess preferences regarding ecosystem services. The Choice Experiments (CE) also investigate preferences using non-monetary payment modes (Ando, Cadavid, Netusil, & Parthum, 2020).

Rai and Scarborough (2013) used a two-stage CE to assist respondents in the Chitwan National Park buffer zone in Nepal to indicate their readiness to contribute labour if they are unable to make cash payments. They found that migrants who were male and had attained higher education, as well as households with higher non-farm income, were more likely to choose the monetary payment option. Respondents from the buffer zone or with a larger family were more likely to prefer employment as a source of income.

Non-monetary contributions like volunteer labour have been considered practical for low-income welfare measures (Gibson, Rigby, & Polya, 2016; Echessah, Swallow, Kamara, & Curry, 1997; Vásquez, 2014; Lankia, Neuvonen, Pouta, & Sievänen, 2014; Ando, Cadavid, Netusil, & Parthum, 2020). Research has also shown that willingness to provide labour may exceed willingness to pay, and that income has a negative impact on willingness to provide labour (O'Garra, 2009; Lankia, Neuvonen, Pouta, & Sievänen, 2014). However, it is important to keep in mind that the economic value of labour might be condition-dependent and might not offer a reliable guideline for allocating funding for public projects. Because the economic value of labour days is condition-dependent, Ahlheim et al. (2010) contend that a Vietnam CV survey on labour participation lacks credibility for allocating funds for public projects. Moreover, using a dual cost attribute could affect the interpretation of results, as shown in the study conducted by Rai and Scarborough (Rai & Scarborough, 2015; Rai & Scarborough, 2013).

2.9.3 The New Ecological Paradigm (NEP)

Schultz et al. (2005) and Zhu and Lu (2017) have argued that the psychometric properties of the NEP scale may be less reliable when used in non-WEIRD countries compared to WEIRD countries. Studies conducted in the United States have reported a high level of internal

consistency ($\alpha > 0.80$) when using the NEP scale. In contrast, studies conducted in countries such as Turkey, Brazil, Nigeria, and India have reported lower levels of internal consistency ($\alpha < 0.70$) (Atav et al., 2015; Ogunbode, 2013). The NEP scale's dimensionality has also been found to vary across different samples, and the number of factors differs between WEIRD and non-WEIRD societies (Bechtel et al., 1999; Hawcroft and Milfont, 2010). For instance, Bechtel et al. (1999) reported a bi-factorial structure in a sample of North Americans, whereas Brazilians and Mexicans showed a three-factor solution. Moreover, the NEP scale's positive and negative wording of items has been found to affect its factorial structure. Zhu and Lu (2017) noted that even-numbered items tend to cluster, which can impact the NEP scale's factorial structure in samples from several non-WEIRD countries (Atav et al., 2015; Freire et al., 2013; Moyano-Diaz and Palomo-Vélez, 2014; Zhu and Lu, 2017). These findings suggest that researchers should exercise caution when using the NEP scale in non-WEIRD countries, and further research is necessary to identify ways to enhance its psychometric properties.

The New Ecological Paradigm (NEP) scale is widely used as a measure of environmental awareness, but its internal consistency has been a concern. Rosa et al. (2018) conducted a systematic review and found that the scale's Cronbach's alpha value was below the minimum acceptable level of 0.6 in 12 out of the 14 samples analysed. This low internal consistency may affect the correlation between the NEP scale and pro-environmental behaviours, which is a theoretically related construct. Nonetheless, some studies have reported high internal consistency for the NEP scale, indicating that the values may vary across studies and samples. For example, Dunlap et al. (2000) found a Cronbach's alpha of 0.83 for the full scale, while Harraway et al. (2012) and Noblet et al. (2013) reported high internal consistency values.

2.9.4 Relationships between NEP Scales and Sociodemographic Characteristics

2.9.4.1 Ecological Worldview and Sociodemographic

It has been suggested that the NEP Scale is appropriate for evaluating the relationship between environmental attitude and sociodemographic variables such as gender (La Trobe & Acott, 2000). Studies on gender and environmental attitudes have shown mixed results, with some finding a higher pro-environmental orientation among females compared to males (Hosseinnezhad, 2017; Pienaar et al., 2015) as well as a rejection of an anthropocentric attitude (Halkos & Matsiori, 2017). Nevertheless, some studies have found no significant relationship between gender and NEP endorsement. For example, Ogunbode (2013), Denis and Pereira (2014), and Reyna et al. (2018) reported no association between gender and NEP endorsement.

Indeed, several studies have found that education is positively associated with a pro-ecological worldview, as evidenced by higher NEP scores (Dunlap et al., 2000; Pienaar et al., 2015; Hosseinnezhad, 2017; Reyna et al., 2018; Hawcroft and Milfont 2010). In addition to cultural and demographic factors, academic discipline has also been shown to influence NEP scores. Specifically, studies have found that students in biological sciences tend to have higher NEP scores compared to those in social sciences and humanities (Harraway et al., 2012; Ogunbode, 2013). On the other hand, Denis and Pereira (2014) noted that individuals with lower educational levels rejected the idea of humans having the right to modify the environment and had a better understanding of the fragile balance of nature compared to those with higher educational levels who accepted the reality of the ecological crisis.

Studies have found an inverse relationship between age and pro-environmental attitudes, with older individuals tending to endorse an anthropocentric viewpoint while younger individuals tend to endorse an ecological worldview (Reyna et al., 2018; Denis & Pereira, 2014). However,

Ogunbode (2013) reported no significant difference in NEP scores across different age groups. On the other hand, Pienaar et al. (2015) reported that older respondents exhibited greater environmental concern.

Diamantopoulos et al. (2003) conducted a study that revealed no significant difference in the environmental attitude of individuals with different marital statuses, whether married or single, as well as those without children, those in higher or lower social classes, and those with or without a university degree. Similarly, Denis and Pereira (2014) found no significant impact of marital status and income on the endorsement of NEP.

Hosseinnezhad (2017) reported a positive association between economic properties and environmental attitudes. Similarly, Buttel and Flinn (1978) found a positive association between urban residence and awareness of environmental problems, while family income and occupation of the household head were found to have no influence on awareness of environmental problems.

Therefore, there is an abundance of literature establishing a strong relationship between sociodemographic characteristics and academic discipline on environmental awareness and worldview (NEP) (Hawcroft & Milfont, 2010; Reyna et al., 2018).

2.9.5 Measurement of Risk Perceptions

Risk can be defined as the potential for unintended consequences resulting from an action or event that may have uncertain causes and symptoms (Dizon, 2022). Risk perception, on the other hand, refers to how individuals interpret and integrate sensory information or impressions regarding risks and their consequences. Risk can be viewed differently by experts and non-

experts, with experts defining risk as an estimated average loss per unit of time, while non-experts consider risk a complex and multidimensional phenomenon where subjective expectation of loss plays a significant role (Dizon, 2022). People's evaluation of risk and risk perception are based on values and moral standards. According to Chen, Han, and Wright (2020), individuals tend to ignore undefined hazards if the belief is that they have no effective response, such as unavoidable risks. Environmental risk assessments are concerned with how people evaluate various technical and environmental hazards, respond to environmental risks, and manage risks within social processes. It is essential to understand public perceptions of environmental threats to achieve successful environmental risk management (Blesia, 2021). Higher education plays a crucial role in raising people's awareness of people about environmental issues and promoting long-term behavioural changes (Blesia, 2021).

This study utilised the psychometric paradigm to explore risk perception, building on the existing literature on cognitive risk studies. The perceived risks and benefits of risky activities were measured using rating scales by Fischhoff et al. (1978). In order to provide accurate and valid assessments of perceived risk and benefit for a range of hazards, numerous psychometric scaling techniques have been developed since then. The study emphasised the importance of comprehending risk perception to manage and communicate risks effectively. He argues that it is impossible to predict people's responses to an issue without first understanding how the issue is perceived, as their perceptions shape their opinions and attitudes. Since the pioneering work of Fischhoff et al. (1978), numerous risk scientists have employed the psychometric paradigm to investigate risk judgements in general as well as expert and layperson perceptions of risk in particular.

McDaniels, Axelrod, and Slovic (1995) conducted two influential studies on perceptions of ecological risks among people. The first study, published in 1995, focused on general

perceptions of ecological risks, while their later study in 1997 focused specifically on perceptions of ecological risks to water environments (McDaniels, Axelrod, Cavanagh, & Slovic, 1997). These studies were ground-breaking in that they revealed differences between expert and lay perceptions of ecological risks. Their study found that laypeople's perception of ecological risks was higher than that of experts, a finding that was confirmed by Lazo, Kinnell, and Fisher (2000) in their study on general perceptions of ecological risks.

This paradigm identifies the characteristics of perceived risks that significantly influence overall risk assessment, potentially indicating which risk attributes should be prioritised in environmental education and communication (Hansen & Hammann, 2017). Moreover, the paradigm helps to elucidate differences in perceptions of various groups, highlighting their shared beliefs and misunderstandings. By comparing the environmental risk perceptions of the two groups of students, the study aimed to assess the influence of ecological education on students' risk perceptions and determine the potential value of ecological content in academic programmes.

2.9.6 Risk Research in the Water Sector

Research on the technical assessment of risk in the water sector has primarily focused on public health risks as the most apparent and immediate consequence of deterioration in water quality (Liu, J., Liu, R., Zhang, Z., Cai, Y., & Zhang, 2019). Cantor (2004) offers a thorough analysis of the epidemiologic data, highlighting the difficulties in determining long-term exposures while also verifying the link between specific pollutants and cancer. All of these studies point to the necessity of continued investigation and practical measures to reduce the health hazards brought on by tainted drinking water.

Notably, most published studies on water-related risk assessments have been conducted prior to planning an intervention. Public risk assessments of water quality are crucial for ensuring complementary decisions with technical assessments, implementing policies on risk management, minimising risks, and allocating resources. Understanding how a particular society perceives risk is essential in identifying vulnerabilities related to water occurrences, and appraisals of environmental risks involving all stakeholders are crucial for promoting environmental sustainability (Withanachchi et al., 2018; Larson, Stoeckl, Neil, & Welters, 2013; Dobbie & Brown, 2014; De França Doria, 2010; Le Lay & Piégay, 2013; Lepesteur, Wegner, Moore, & McComb, 2008).

Both Morris (1995), and Crouch, Wilson, and Zeise (1983) draw attention to the possibility of cancer, with Morris highlighting the dangers associated with arsenic and chlorination byproducts in particular. Smeenk (1983) highlights the effects even more on children, who are particularly susceptible because of their higher water intake in relation to body weight.

2.9.7 Factors that Influence Risk Perception

Factors that influence risk perception have been extensively researched and theorised over the years. The psychometric paradigm and cultural theory are among the most well-known theories on risk perception and its predictors (Janmaimool & Watanabe, 2014). It is widely acknowledged that cognitive and emotional processes are necessary in shaping perceptions of risk (De França Doria, 2010). However, these theories have been subject to criticism and modification over time. For example, Sjöberg (2000) has argued that some important predictors are not taken into account by cultural theory or risk perception psychometric techniques, such as community size, education, income, and gender.

The influence of risk factors related to the nature of risks has been examined in several studies. Understanding the technical aspects of a risk can affect individuals' risk perceptions (Larkin, Lucey, & Mulholland, 2013). In the axiomatic risk approach, which considers the perception of risks by individuals to be influenced by the probability of occurrence and the likelihood of a negative outcome, Janmaimool and Watanabe (2014) also noted the influence of the nature of the risk-on-risk perception.

Earlier research on risk perception primarily relied on rational choice models, which assumed that individuals assessed risks by rationally calculating the probability and desirability of different risk outcomes (Slovic et al., 2002; Leiserowitz, 2006). However, recent studies have demonstrated that these models do not entirely explain people's risk perceptions since laypeople often lack the knowledge required to assess risks rationally, including the drivers, probabilities, and consequences associated with the risk (Slovic et al., 2002).

2.8.7.1 Trust in Institutions

Trust has been identified as a key factor that influences environmental risk perception. It is a fact that higher levels of trust lead to lower perceptions of risk (Siegrist et al., 2000). Trust in government agencies, in particular, has been shown to be an important component of social trust in relation to risk perception (Bord and O'Connor, 1992; Flynn, Burns, Mertz, & Slovic, 1992). For example, trust in government agencies is found to be a key factor in public risk perception (Bord and O'Connor, 1992; Flynn, Burns, Mertz, & Slovic, 1992), pesticide use, nuclear power, and artificial sweeteners (Siegrist et al., 2000). Furthermore, trust is found to play a role in risk perception related to wildlife disease transmission (Vaske et al., 2004) and

prescribed burning (Vaske et al., 2007). Overall, trust is an important cognitive factor that can shape environmental risk perception.

Trust is defined in this study as the level of confidence that individuals have in the local assembly and the traditional authority to effectively manage and minimise risks associated with pollution of water. Trust is crucial because it is dependent on people's behaviour and attitudes towards risk, and understanding its role in decision-making and risk communication is essential (Poortinga & Pidgeon, 2003).

2.8.7.2 Environmental attitudes

Research has indicated that environmental attitudes play a significant role in determining individuals' perceptions of environmental risks. The New Ecological Paradigm (NEP) scale, developed by Dunlap and Van Liere (1978), is the most widely used measure of environmental attitudes. Studies have consistently shown that individuals with higher levels of environmental concern, as measured by the NEP, tend to perceive bigger environmental risks across various ecological hazards (Stern and Dietz, 1994; Slimak and Dietz, 2006). This is particularly true for climate change, as research has found that higher levels of environmental concern are associated with greater perceived risk to climate change (Kellstedt et al., 2008).

2.8.7.3 Risk salience

Additionally, demographic factors can also influence risk perception. For example, gender variations in environmental risk perception are found in several studies, with women generally perceiving greater risk than men (Finucane et al., 2000; Flynn, Slovic, & Mertz, 1994). Age

has also been a significant factor in risk perception, with older individuals generally perceiving greater risk than younger individuals (Slovic et al., 2000). Finally, education and socioeconomic status are also found to be important factors in environmental risk perception, with higher levels of education and income associated with lower perceived risk (Finucane et al., 2000; Flynn, Slovic, & Mertz, 1994).

2.9.8 Sociodemographic Factors Influencing Risk Perceptions

Many studies are in agreement on the potential influences of sociodemographic factors on risk perceptions. In terms of sociodemographic characteristics include factors that affect risk perception. However, only sex consistently predicts risk perception, with males perceiving risk as smaller and less problematic than females and ethnic minorities. This is known as the white male effect (WME), which has been observed in several studies (e.g., Saleh Safi et al. 2012; Slovic 2016; Flint et al., 2017). Researchers have proposed various explanations for this phenomenon. According to Slovic (2016), the WME may also be linked to gender roles, as men tend to work in fields that may be perceived as riskier. Additionally, females were more concerned about flooding, poor water quality, and how climate change would affect the availability of water, according to a 2014 survey conducted in northern Utah (Flint et al. 2017).

The perception of ecological risk is also affected by age, income, and education, in addition to sex. Typically, there is an inverse relationship between risk perception and education and income; as education and income increase, perception of risk decreases (de Franc, a Doria 2010; Slovic 2016). However, a study conducted in 2014 in Utah showed that the level of education did not command any significance related to concern about water shortages; respondents with

more formal education were less concerned about water quality and flooding but more concerned about the impact of climate change (Flint et al. 2017).

Studies show a direct relationship between age and risk perception, with older individuals experiencing increased risk perception. However, socioeconomic status, particularly among women and ethnic minorities, can explain this correlation, as lower SES leads to perceived lack of control (Finucane et al., 2000).

According to Larson, Ibes and White (2010), women expressed more concern about the safety of local drinking water than men, but both genders had similar perceptions regarding the causes of water scarcity. Age strongly correlates with concern about water risk, according to a 2017 study conducted in Utah by Flint et al. (2017), with older respondents expressing higher levels of concern. However, Pierce et al. (2009) did not find a difference in risk perception between genders in a survey on renewable energy conducted in Oregon, suggesting that the gender gap in risk perception may be decreasing. According to Slimak and Dietz (2006), risk perception is positively correlated with age, gender (female), and political liberalism, while it is negatively correlated with education and income.

Additional studies have demonstrated that the relationship between age and gender is complex and can affect environmental behaviour. For instance, Steel (1996) found that younger women tend to be more environmentally responsible and informed on environmental policy issues than older women. Flynn, Slovic, and Mertz (1994) suggested that the difference between males and females in risk perception may be related to their worldview and status, as white males are more likely to create, manage, control, and benefit from risky activities than women. However, these gender and age differences may not be as pronounced when it comes to water-related issues.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter encompasses the methodology used in the study. The chapter discusses the study areas, the study design, data collection/sampling strategies, conceptual and theoretical frameworks and then the empirical models underlying the study.

3.2 Study Areas

The study was carried out within two (2) important water basins in Ghana, namely, Pra and Densu.

3.2.1 Pra Basin

The Pra Basin is found in the central region of Ghana, spanning between Latitudes 5° N and 7° 30' N, as well as Longitudes 2° 30' W and 0° 0' 30' W (see Figure 3.1). It is characterised by the Pra River, together with its tributaries. It constitutes the largest river basin among the three main south-western basin systems in Ghana, namely the Ankobra, Tano, and Pra.

The Pra Basin covers about 23,200 km², which spans across four regions in Ghana. Specifically, it covers approximately 55% of the Ashanti Region, 23% of the Eastern Region, 15% of the Central Region, and 7% of the Western Region.

Figure 3.1: Map of Pra River Basin

3.2.2 Densu Basin

The Densu River runs through a densely populated area of Ghana, and despite its small size, it is one of the most heavily used rivers in the country. The basin is characterised by rapidly deteriorating land and water quality, as well as occasional water shortages in an otherwise permanent river system, owing, among other things, to the fast population growth due to its closeness to Accra.

The Densu River Basin is located between 5°30'N and 6°17'N latitudes and 0°10'W and 0°37'W longitudes (Figure 3.2). The Odaw and Volta basins, respectively, border the basin to the east

and north. The Biriasin shares a boundary to the northwest, and the Ayensu and Okrudu basins share a boundary to the west.

Figure 3.2: Map of Densu River Basin

3.3 Sources and Types of Data

The study made use of cross-sectional primary and secondary data on sociodemographic, spiritual beliefs, perceptions, and willingness to pay (WTP) for water-related ecosystem services in the two basins. The secondary data used was the National Population and Housing Census data 2021, published by the Ghana Statistical Service. This was used in determining the number of districts to be selected, as well as the number of respondents from each district. The data was also useful in determining the number of respondents to select from rural and urban communities in each district, as well as the male-female distribution of the respondents.

3.4 Sampling and Sample Size

Multistage sampling was used in selecting respondents from the two basins. In the first stage, Densu and Pra basins were purposively selected due to evidence of deterioration of the river basins as well as the environmental and health implications on rural and urban households. In the second stage, each of the basins were stratified based on the regional administrative boundaries. The Densu basin runs through three administrative regions (Greater Accra, Eastern and Central), and the Pra basin runs across five administrative regions (Ashanti, Central, Eastern, Western, and Western North regions).

In the third stage, districts were selected from each region using simple random sampling. The *Raosoft* online sample size calculator was used to derive the number of districts to select from each region using a 90% confidence level and a 10% margin of error were applied, resulting in the selection of 15 districts out of 18 districts and 36 out of the 68 districts in the Densu and Pra basins respectively (see Table 3.1).

Table 3.1: Summary of Sample Size across Basins

Basin	No. of Administrative Regions	No. of Districts	Districts sampled	Household population
Densu	3	18	15	2,821,976
Pra	5	68	36	7,556,438
	8	86	51	10,378,414.00

Source: GSS, 2021

In the fourth stage, respondents were randomly selected from each of the sampled districts. In order to conform to budgetary and time constraints and at the same time ensure that the sample size was enough to make generalisations about the population in the Pra and Densu basins, a sample size of 500 respondents from each basin was determined. In targeting the respondents,

550 respondents were targeted from each basin (with over sampling of 50 respondents) to ensure that the sample size is reached.

The 500 respondents targeted were distributed across the districts and reflected the gender and rural urban distributions in the districts. For example, in Table 3.2, in the Awutu Senya East Municipality, where the population 235,413 out of 2,667,112 (representing 8.827% of the population), 44 respondents were determined (representing 8.827% of the total sample size). Also, 228,587 of the population were in urban (representing 97.1% of the total population) and hence, 43 of the respondents were drawn from the urban community. Finally, the gender shows that 114,768 were male (representing 49% of the population) and hence, 21 of the respondents were male.

Table 3.2 shows the distribution in the Densu basin. In the Densu basin, out of the 500 respondents, 386 were in the urban communities while 114 were in the rural communities. In terms of gender, 245 were male while the remaining 255 were females. The distribution, as indicated earlier, was in line with the population distribution in the 2021 population census.

Table 3.2: Distribution of the sample in Densu Basin

Region	District	Total population	Male	Female	Urban	Rural	Sample Size	Urban Sample	Male In Urban	Female In Urban	Rural Sample	Male In Rural	Female In Rural	Male Sample	Female Sample
Central	Awutu Senya East Municipal	235,413	114,768	120,645	228,587	6,826	44	43	20	23	1	1	0	21	23
Central	Awutu Senya West	159,647	77,257	82,390	93,735	65,912	30	18	9	9	12	6	6	15	15
Central		395,060	192,025	203,035	322,322	72,738	74	61	29	32	13	7	6	36	38
	Akwapim North	85,404													
Eastern	Municipal Akwapim	69,460	41,560	43,844	68,990	16,414	18	9	5	5	9	4	5	9	9
Eastern	South	95,613	34,520	34,940	28,172	41,288	13	5	3	2	8	4	4	7	6
Eastern	Ayensuano New Juaben	71,817	45,743	49,870	49,455	46,158	18	5	3	3	13	6	7	9	9
Eastern	North New Juaben	93,640	36,066	35,751	26,560	45,257	16	13	6	6	3	2	1	8	8
Eastern	South Municipal Nsawam	85,001	46,617	47,023	26,984	66,656	23	23	11	12	0	0	0	11	12
Eastern	Adoagyiri Municipal Suhum	120,307	41,267	43,734	68,677	16,324	28	17	8	9	11	5	6	13	15
Eastern	Municipal Upper West	150,520	57,878	62,429	120,055	252	23	11	5	6	12	6	6	11	12
Eastern	Akim		72,291	78,229	91,599	58,921	17	5	2	3	12	6	6	8	9
Eastern		771,762	375,942	395,820	480,492	291,270	156	88	43	46	68	33	35	76	80
Greater Accra	Ga Central Municipal	92,414	45,116	47,298	27,605	64,809	62	62	30	32	0	0	0	30	32
Greater Accra	Ga North	987,857	480,796	507,061	565,103	422,754	44	44	22	22	0	0	0	22	22

Region	District	Total population	Male	Female	Urban	Rural	Sample Size	Urban Sample	Male In Urban	Female In Urban	Rural Sample	Male In Rural	Female In Rural	Male Sample	Female Sample
Greater Accra	Ga South	329,269	160,048	169,221	329,269	0	65	50	24	25	15	8	7	32	33
Greater Accra	Ga West	233,977	115,806	118,171	233,977	0	59	41	20	21	18	9	9	29	30
Greater Accra	Weija Gbawe Municipal	349,171	171,958	177,213	265,918	83,253	40	40	20	20	0	0	0	20	20
	Greater Accra	1,992,688	973,724	1,018,964	1,421,872	570,816	270	237	116	120	33	17	16	133	137
GRAND TOTAL		3,159,510	1,541,691	1,617,819	2,224,686	934,824	500	386	188	198	114	57	57	245	255

Table 3.3 show the distribution of the respondents in the Pra basin. The results show that, out of the total sample size of 500, 215 were from the urban communities while 285 were from the rural communities. There were also fewer male respondents than females (249 and 251 of the respondents were male and female respectively).

Thus, in line with nature of the basins, the Densu is more of an urban basin compared to the Pra basin. The Densu basin runs through largely the capital of Ghana while the Pra is largely the rural parts of the Ashanti region.

Table 3.3: Distribution of the sample in Pra Basin

Region	District	Total Population	Male	Female	Urban	Rural	Sample Size	Urban Sample	Male In Urban	Female In Urban	Rural Sample	Male In Rural	Female In Rural	Male Sample	Female Sample
Ashanti	Adansi South	83,823	41,929	41,894	17,648	66,175	12	3	2	1	9	4	5	6	6
Ashanti	Afigya Kwabre North	72,108	36,083	36,025	42,977	29,131	10	6	3	3	4	2	2	5	5
Ashanti	Ahafo Ano South East	63,291	31,992	31,299	15,452	47,839	9	2	1	1	7	3	4	4	5
Ashanti	Akrofuom	48,663	25,998	22,665	10,236	38,427	7	2	1	1	5	3	2	4	3
Ashanti	Amansie Central	92,241	48,022	44,219	11,974	80,267	13	2	1	1	11	6	5	7	6
Ashanti	Amansie South	115,264	60,820	54,444	21,182	94,082	16	3	2	1	13	6	7	8	8
Ashanti	Amansie West	108,139	55,472	52,667	39,311	68,828	15	5	3	2	10	5	5	8	7
Ashanti	Asante Akim Central Municipal	88,486	43,150	45,336	57,193	31,293	12	8	4	4	4	2	2	6	6
Ashanti	Asante Akim North	81,216	40,108	41,108	52,239	28,977	11	7	4	3	4	2	2	6	6
Ashanti	Asante Akim South	121,334	60,609	60,725	31,806	89,528	17	5	2	3	12	6	6	8	8
Ashanti	Asokwa Municipal	123,680	59,327	64,353	123,680	0	17	17	8	9	0	0	0	8	9
Ashanti	Atwima Kwanwoma	232,484	113,679	118,805	132,359	100,125	32	18	9	9	14	7	7	16	17
Ashanti	Atwima Mponua	153,187	79,387	73,800	23,641	129,546	21	3	2	1	18	9	9	11	10
Ashanti	Atwima Nwabiagya North	152,062	74,564	77,498	97,460	54,602	21	13	6	7	8	4	4	10	11
Ashanti	Atwima Nwabiagya South Municipal	158,176	76,693	81,483	102,987	55,189	22	14	7	7	8	4	4	11	11
Ashanti	Bekwai Municipal	132,019	64,176	67,843	45,399	86,620	18	6	3	3	12	6	6	9	9

Region	District	Total Population	Male	Female	Urban	Rural	Sample Size	Urban Sample	Male In Urban	Female In Urban	Rural Sample	Male In Rural	Female In Rural	Male Sample	Female Sample
Ashanti	Bosome Freho	61,625	31,082	30,543	-	61,625	9	0	0	0	9	4	5	4	4
Ashanti	Bosomtwi	160,723	78,604	82,119	88,355	72,368	22	12	6	6	10	5	5	11	11
Ashanti	Ejisu Juaben Municipal	175,178	85,127	90,051	74,794	100,384	24	10	5	5	14	7	7	12	13
Ashanti	Sekyere East	71,379	34,477	36,902	43,057	28,322	10	6	3	3	4	2	2	5	5
Ashanti	Total	2,295,078	1,141,299	1,153,779	1,031,750	1,263,328	318	142	72	70	176	87	89	159	160
Central	Assin North	78,925	39,693	39,232	19,518	59,407	12	3	2	1	9	4	5	6	6
Central	Assin South	103,410	50,995	52,415	-	103,410	16	0	0	0	16	8	8	8	8
Central	Twifo Ati Morkwa	98,776	49,368	49,408	25,657	73,119	15	4	2	2	11	5	6	7	8
Central	Twifo Heman Lower Denkyira	65,248	32,537	32,711	17,964	47,284	10	3	2	1	7	3	4	5	5
Central	Total	346,359	172,593	173,766	63,139	283,220	53	10	6	4	43	20	23	26	27
Eastern	Abuakwa North	85,404	41,560	43,844	68,990	16,414	12	10	5	5	2	1	1	6	6
Eastern	Abuakwa South Municipal	69,460	34,520	34,940	28,172	41,288	10	4	2	2	6	3	3	5	5
Eastern	Atiwa East	63,743	32,305	31,438	24,752	38,991	9	4	2	2	5	3	2	5	4
Eastern	Atiwa West	60,478	30,883	29,595	19,650	40,828	8	3	2	1	5	2	3	4	4
Eastern	Birim Central Municipal	71,379	34,149	37,230	69,029	2,350	10	10	5	5	0	0	0	5	5
Eastern	Birim North	79,941	40,174	39,767	24,998	54,943	11	3	2	1	8	4	4	6	5
Eastern	Birim South	33,955	16,631	17,324	13,743	20,212	5	2	1	1	3	1	2	2	3
Eastern	Fanteakwa South	53,122	26,931	26,191	22,665	30,457	7	3	2	1	4	2	2	4	3
Eastern	Kwaebibirem	119,763	59,235	60,528	51,333	68,430	17	7	3	4	10	5	5	8	9
Eastern	Total	637,245	316,388	320,857	323,332	313,913	89	46	24	22	43	21	22	45	44

Region	District	Total Population	Male	Female	Urban	Rural	Sample Size	Urban Sample	Male In Urban	Female In Urban	Rural Sample	Male In Rural	Female In Rural	Male Sample	Female Sample
Western	Shama	114,565	55,730	58,835	73,151	41,414	16	10	4	6	6	3	3	7	9
Western	Wassa East	98,841	50,778	48,063	14,077	84,764	13	2	1	1	11	6	5	7	6
Western	Total	213,406	106,508	106,898	87,228	126,178	29	12	5	7	17	9	8	14	15
W-North	Sefwi Bibiani Ahwiaso Bekwai	165,471	81,777	83,694	69,066	96,405	11	5	2	3	6	3	3	5	6
W-North	Total	165,471	81,777	83,694	69,066	96,405	11	5	2	3	6	3	3	5	6
GRAND	TOTALS	3,657,559	1,818,565	1,838,994	1,574,515	2,083,044	500	215	109	106	285	140	145	249	251

Responses received were 538 and 519 from Densu and Pra respectively, representing a response rate of 98 percent and 94 percent, respectively. After cleaning the data, a sample size of 500 responses was used for each basin. Even though the sample size was based largely on budgetary constraints, the *Raosoft* was used to check whether the sample size was enough. Based on the 2021 population and housing census data, the Densu basin had a household population of 2,821,976, while the Pra basin had a total population of 7,556,438. The sample size for both Densu and Pra basins corresponded to a confidence interval of 95 percent a margin of error of 3 percent using the corresponding population size for each of the basins¹.

3.5 Conceptual Framework Underlying the Valuation and Risk Perceptions of WES in the Pra and Densu Basins

The conceptual framework underlying this study is presented in Figure 3.3. The figure demonstrates how individual values affect environmental awareness (EA), which in turn affects willingness to pay for ecosystem services. The advantages of ecosystem services have a direct impact on willingness to pay. The advantages of ecosystem services, as well as willingness to pay, both influences how individuals perceive ecological risks. Another significant contextual variable that could have an impact on all of the other variables in the model is the social structural element.

Values that people hold, such as altruistic, egoistic and biospheric values play important role in determining environmental awareness of individuals (De Groot & Steg, 2007). According to Stern et al. (1999), their measurements were based on a condensed version of Schwartz's

¹ The 95% confidence interval and 3% margin of error was made possible by the Raosoft online sample size calculator

value scale (2003). The role of religious beliefs was tested using the religious affiliations of respondents. Data on affiliations to the common religious practices in Ghana, such as Christianity, Islam, Traditional religion, and other forms of religion, were taken (Dietz, Fitzgerald, & Shwom, 2005).

Sociodemographic variables included in this study were education, gender, income level, and trust in government institutions, which were hypothesised to have a significant influence on environmental awareness and risk perceptions (Slovic, 1999; Slovic, 2000; Flynn, Slovic, & Mertz, 1994). Therefore, it was important to consider those social structural factors when examining environmental risk perception.

Figure 3.3: Conceptual Framework Underlying the Study of the Two Basins

3.6 Theoretical Framework Underlying the Study of the Two Basins

The consumer demand theory formed the foundation for the economic valuation of ecosystem services adopted in this study. According to the utility hypothesis, the primary concern of consumers is how best to spend their limited resources in order to maximise utility.

The standard economic theory postulates that an individual's maximum utility, denoted as V , is a function of their income, I , the prevailing market prices, P , and the level of non-market good provision, Q . Additionally, the function is assumed to depend on other socio-economic characteristics of the individual, denoted as S . Therefore, the general form of the indirect utility function is expressed as:

$$V(I, P, S, Q) \quad [1]$$

In this framework, it is assumed that respondents evaluated their utility at two different levels of provision of a non-market good, namely Q_0 and Q_1 . As higher levels of provision typically correspond to greater utility, respondents are assumed to prefer Q_1 over Q_0 , and to be willing to pay up to a maximum amount of Y to achieve Q_1 . The maximum amount that a respondent is willing to pay, also known as the maximum willingness to pay (WTP), and it is the amount that would make the respondent indifferent between the utility they experience before and after the provision of the non-market good. Formally, this can be defined as:

$$V(I, P, S, Q_0) = V(I - Y, P, S, Q_1) \quad [2]$$

Y is called the compensating variation of a change in welfare. By re-arranging (2), Y can be defined as a function of the other parameters in the model without explicit knowledge of the indirect utility function V :

$$Y = Y(Q_0, Q_1, I, P, S) \quad [3]$$

The Multinomial Discrete Choice (MDC) models consist of models employed to analyse data with numerous unordered dependent variables.

Let the random utility function be defined as

$$U_{ij} = V_{ij} + \epsilon_{ij} \quad [4]$$

Where the subscript i represents an index for the individual, the subscript j for the index of alternative, V_{ij} is a nonstochastic utility function, and ϵ_{ij} is the random component (error), which encompasses unobserved attributes of alternatives and/or individuals. The utility function in MDC is said to be linear, such that:

$$V_{ij} = X'_{ij}\beta + \varepsilon \quad [5]$$

In the conditional logit model, each ϵ_{ij} for all $j \in C$ is distributed independently and identically (iid) and distributed as Type I extreme-value distribution, also known as the Gumbel distribution.

The assumption of independence and identically distributed (iid) random terms in the utility function for different alternatives can be relaxed to avoid the limitations of the independence from irrelevant alternatives (IIA) property of the conditional logit model. This relaxation allows for more flexible replacements among different patterns of alternatives compared to the conditional logit model.

Mixed logit models are more flexible and can capture a wider range of preferences and heterogeneity in the population. They allow for individual-specific coefficients and account for correlation among unobserved factors affecting choices. Mixed logit models can also capture complex patterns of substitution among alternatives, which is particularly useful in modelling consumer choices where there may be multiple products with varying attributes and prices.

In the multinomial probit (MNP) model, the error terms, $(\epsilon_{i1}, \epsilon_{i2}, \epsilon_{i3}, \dots, \epsilon_{ij})$, are distributed as multivariate normal (MVN), allowing the model to take a variety of error structures.

The process of estimating using the multinomial probit model requires multidimensional integration, adding to its computational complexity in comparison to a group of multinomial choice models created from the utility function of the Gumbel distribution.

Furthermore, compared to previous multinomial choice models, the multinomial probit model requires more parameters. Consequently, the model is rarely used compared to the more restrictive random component models (nested and conditional).

The chance of making a choice, $\{y_i = j\}$, can be expressed as a random utility function

$$U_{ij} \geq \max_{k \in C_i, k \neq j} U_{ik} \quad [6]$$

where C_i is the choice set of individual i . The individual, i , chooses alternative j if and only if it provides a level of utility that is greater than or equal to that of any other alternative in his choice set. Then, the probability that individual i chooses alternative j (from among the n_i choices in his choice set C_i) is

$$P_i(j) = P_{ij} = P[X'_{ij}\beta + \epsilon_{ij} \geq \max_{k \in C_i} (X'_{ik}\beta + \epsilon_{ik})] \quad [7]$$

Multinomial logit model, where explanatory variables represent individual attributes, is defined as

$$P_i(j) = P_{ij} = \frac{\exp(X'_{ij}\beta_j)}{\sum_{k=0}^J \exp(X'_{ik}\beta_k)} \text{ for } j = 0, \dots, J \quad [8]$$

where y_i is the random choice variable, x_i represents a vector of individual (i th) characteristics, and β_j is a vector of coefficients for the j alternatives. Thus, this model deals with choice-specific coefficients, and the regressors consist of only individual-specific characteristics. $\beta_0 = 0$ is assumed for the model to be identified. Where the alternative (j) is binary ($j=1$), the multinomial logit model becomes the binary logit model.

The odds ratio of the choice probabilities for alternatives j and l is specified as:

$$\frac{P_{ij}}{P_{il}} = \frac{\frac{\exp(X'_i\beta_j)}{\sum_{k=0}^J \exp(X'_i\beta_k)}}{\frac{\exp(X'_i\beta_l)}{\sum_{k=0}^J \exp(X'_i\beta_k)}} = \exp[X'_i(\beta_j - \beta_l)] \quad [9]$$

The log-likelihood function is given as:

$$L = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=0}^J d_{ij} \ln P(y_i = j) \quad [10]$$

Where

$$d_{ij} = \int_0^1 \text{otherwise if individual } i \text{ chooses alternative } j$$

The estimated β coefficients in a choice experiment are used to calculate the marginal willingness to pay (MWTP) for each attribute included in the experiment. The MWTP is defined as the amount of money a person is willing to pay for a specific level of a given attribute. The MWTP can be estimated by dividing the estimated coefficient for an attribute by the price parameter and taking the negative of the result. This can be expressed mathematically as follows:

$$MWTP = -\frac{\beta_k}{p} \quad [11]$$

Where β_k is the estimated coefficient for attribute k and p is the price parameter.

The coefficient of marginal utility of income is often presumed as an estimated coefficient for the cost (Phillips, Maddala, & Johnson, 2010; Upton, Dhubháin, & Bullock, 2012). The Monte Carlo simulation technique developed by Krinsky and Robb (1986) was used to generate 95% confidence intervals for the MWTP (Han, Kwak, & Yoo, 2008; Sælen & Ericson, 2013).

3.6.1 Marginal willingness to pay (MWTP)

To estimate the marginal willingness to pay (MWTP) for different ecosystem attributes, the estimated coefficients (β) from the mixed logit (ML) model were used. Specifically, the MWTP

for attribute K was calculated as the negative ratio of the parameter k for that attribute and the price parameter p, with other variables held constant.

To determine the ideal model, some statistical criteria come in handy. The two common statistical criteria that are often used are the minimum Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) and the minimum Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) (Allenby 1990; Gupta & Chintagunta 1994). As the number of parameters increases, the model fits (BIC and AIC statistical measures) apply penalties to account for the increasing numbers (Boxall & Macnab 2000).

The literature on choice experiments primarily uses monetary cost as a measure of value, with the scarcity value of time often estimated as one-third of the wage rate (English, von Haefen, Herriges, Leggett, & Lupi et al., 2018). However, recent research has shown that the value of time is context-specific and may be higher than what was estimated, as found by Fezzi, Bateman, and Ferrini (2014). Some studies also report very little correlation between an individual's value of time and their wage rate, as shown by Lloyd-Smith and Adamowicz (2018). Gibson et al. (2016) review and extend a set of papers that use both willingness to pay (WTP) and willingness to work (WTW) hours to estimate value in stated preference valuation exercises. Their research showed that the ratio of average WTP to WTW was relatively close to the full market wage rate for the task presented in the choice experiment scenarios. However, recent studies cited in that review have used 1/3 of the wage rate to estimate the value of time that individuals are willing to contribute to public goods. The equivalent of equation (4) for the time cost treatment can be derived from this approach and stated marginal WTW (MWTW) to improve attribute k in units of time is:

$$MWTW = -\frac{\beta_k}{p} \quad [12]$$

3.7 Measurement of Variables

The study utilised various scales in measuring the risk perception and environmental awareness of respondents. Given the number of items measuring risk perception and environmental awareness, Cronbach's alpha was employed to measure the reliability and internal consistency of the multiple measures of the same construct.

The Cronbach alpha is given by:

$$\alpha = \frac{n\bar{r}}{1 + \bar{r}(n - 1)} \quad [13]$$

Where n is the number of items (questions) and the correlation between items is denoted by \bar{r} . High values of Cronbach alpha indicate high levels of item consistency and reliability, and the range is 0 to 1 (Lavrakas, 2008).

Factor analysis and structural equation model (SEM) were also used in analysing the risk perception and environmental awareness variables. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) of the ecocentric and ethnocentric factors of the NEP scales were performed while the Exploratory factor analysis was employed on the risk perceptions to determine the factors. SEM analysis was employed to examine the determinants of environmental awareness.

3.7.1 Risk perceptions and Environmental Awareness of Respondents

The assessment of risk perception (or awareness of consequences) involved the use of a Likert-style rating (1-5) scheme, in which respondents were asked to rank the overall importance of 11 risk items identified as being prominent in having potential impacts on the ecosystem services (ES) in the Densu and Pra basins. The respondents ranked these human activities

(pressors) as follows 1 – Not at all risky, 2 – Slightly risky, 3 – Neutral, 4 – very risky, and 5 – Extremely risky.

3.7.2 New Ecological Paradigm (NEP) Scales

The revised NEP Scale, consisting of 15 items, was used to assess the ecological worldview of participants (Dunlap et al., 1992). The odd-numbered items of the scale indicated NEP orientation, while even-numbered items reflected an anthropocentric Dominant Social Paradigm (DSP). The scale items underwent minor alterations to enhance comprehension and interpretation by the participants. A five-point Likert scale was used to rate items, and a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.70 indicated an acceptable level of reliability in the sample. Response options were combined, and percentages were calculated to represent the frequency distribution of agreement, disagreement, and uncertainty on NEP items. Mean item scores, mean NEP scores and overall NEP index scores were calculated, and a pro-ecological attitude was reflected by a mean NEP score of ≥ 3 . An anthropocentric worldview was indicated if the mean NEP were less than 3 (Ogunbode, 2013; Rideout et al., 2005). The questionnaire used in the study is available in Appendix A.

3.8 Research Design Adopted for this Study

In this study, an experimental design was used to develop a variety of hypothetical scenarios by identifying attributes and their levels and then combining them to create different alternatives. To achieve this, a fractional factorial design was adopted using the Ngene

software. By doing so, a good level of D-optimality was obtained in the design, which helped to maximise the precision and accuracy of the results.

In the final design, 15 paired choice profiles were randomly blocked into 8 and 7 choice tasks. Respondents were randomly assigned to one of the two blocks and were required to select the most favoured option in each choice task. Each choice task had three alternatives: A, B, and C, with A and B indicating the choice design generated while the option C indicated the baseline (or status quo) that depicted the conditions as they were without any interventions (see Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3: Example of Choice card (Money payments in GHS)

Attributes/Benefits	Card 2	Option A	Option B
Flood protection		 1 per 10 years Strong protection	
Erosion Control		 80% protected Strong protection	
Surface Water Quality		 Medium quality	
Biodiversity (Fish Species and Abundance)		 10-15 kg/8 hour Medium levels of fish	
Cultural Services (Recreation/ Tourism/ Religious services)		 Low level of opportunities	
Levy (GHS)		5.00	100.00

3.9 Design of the Choice Experiment

Designing the choice experiments required taking various steps such as attributes identification and level assignment, questionnaire development and generation of choice sets.

3.9.1 Identification and selection of Attributes and their Levels

The most daunting and difficult task in the choice experiment study is how to identify and describe the relevant attributes, including the levels to be used for each attribute (Hoyos, 2010). The attributes and levels in this study were identified through a literature review and consultation with experts in the field of renewable energy. The literature review helped to identify the most relevant attributes, while the experts assisted in selecting appropriate levels for each attribute. The identified attributes were flood protection, erosion control, surface water quality, fish abundance and species (fish biodiversity), and cultural services (religious practices/tourism). The payment vehicles used for this study were money (in GHS, per month per household for a period of 5 years) and labour days (time). For each attribute, three levels were identified based on the literature review and expert consultation. The three levels for each attribute were high, medium, and low. The cost attribute had five levels: 5, 20, 40, 80, and 100 Ghana cedis, while the labour days were 1, 2, 4, 6, and 8 days(see Table 3.3).

Table 3.3: Attributes and Level used in the choice experiment

S/N	ATTRIBUTE	LEVELS
1	Flood protection	Low, Medium, High
2	Erosion Control	Low, Medium, High
3	Surface water quality	Low, Medium, High
4	Biodiversity of fish	Low, Medium, High
5	Cultural services	Low, Medium, High
6	Money (GHS)	5.00, 20.00, 40.00, 80.00, and 100.00 per month per household
7	Time (Labour days)	1, 2, 4, 6, and 8 days per month per household

3.9.2 Questionnaire Development

The study employed a semi-structured questionnaire (Greiner, Bliemer, & Ballweg, 2014; Holmes, Adamowicz, & Carlsson, 2017). In all, four sub-sections were designated in the questionnaire. The first part was the consent statement, which required respondents to voluntarily agree to participate in the study (Hoyos, 2010). This section was followed by some questions needed to usher participants into the study and to guarantee their familiarity with the two basins and their services (Kløjgaard, Bech, & Sjøgaard, 2012). The third sub-section was on choice experiments (Hoyos, 2010), which had some debriefing questions aimed at establishing the reasoning behind the choices (Greiner et al., 2014). The fourth part of the questionnaire was on the sociodemographic characteristics of the participants (Holmes, Adamowicz, & Carlsson, 2017). The last part of the questionnaire was on risk perceptions, values of respondents and the environmental awareness questionnaires.

The questionnaire was deployed on the open-sourced KoboToolBox platform for data collection. The data was collected in person by well-trained enumerators and the language of communication was in the native language of the respondents. Enumerators were recruited locally at the district levels and therefore, understood the languages respondents were able to communicate effectively. However, on the choice experiment, respondents were given the tables to make their choices independently, with the support and guidance of the trained enumerators.

3.9.3 Generation of Choice Cards

Attribute and level combinations were generated to appear in choice cards after their selection (Owuor et al., 2019). To ensure the lowest possible standard errors during parameter

estimation, efficient designs were used (Walker et al., 2018). A pilot study was conducted to obtain Bayesian efficient design choice cards using the Ngene software package, and 50 respondents were interviewed (n = 50). The final design consisted of 15 choice cards which were assigned to the respondents. Respondents were randomly assigned into a group of two, in each group, each respondent was handed a total of 15 cards (combination of cards with monetary and time payments; see Figure 3.3 and 3.4 for samples of the choice cards with money and time payments respectively).

Figure 3.4: Example of Choice card (Time payments in Labour days)

Card 12		Option A	Option B	
Flood protection	 3 per 10 years	Medium protection		
Erosion Control	 20% protected	Low protection		
Surface Water Quality	 Medium quality	Medium water quality		
Biodiversity (Fish Species and Abundance)	 10-15 kg/8 hour	Medium levels of fish		
Cultural Services (Recreation/ Tourism/ Religious services)	 ○○○	Medium level of opportunities		
Time (Days)		8 days every month	1 day every month	

3.10 Data Analysis

Data obtained was cleaned, recoded and exported as csv files using the Stata version 17. Then, two types of random utility models, namely the multinomial logit and mixed logit models, were used to answer the third and fourth objectives, which is to determine the household's preferences and willingness to pay for ecosystem services for the ecosystem resources. The “*logitr*” package in the open-source R programming was used for the analysis of the choice experiment data after the data was cleaned using the Stata version 17. Frequency distribution tables were estimated using Stata version 17.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the results and discussions based on the underlying objectives, research questions and hypothesis set. The chapter begins by presenting the sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents. The results are then presented based on the objectives, starting from environmental awareness and then through to the preference and willingness to pay or work to conserve water-related ecosystem services.

4.2 Sociodemographic Profile of Respondents

The descriptive characteristics of respondents are shown in Table 4.1. The aggregated data from the Pra and Densu basins show that most of the respondents were in the Ashanti region (32%), followed by the greater Accra region (27%), Eastern region (24%), Central region (13%) and the least from the Western North region (3%) and then Western region (1%). In the Densu basin, the majority of respondents were in the Greater Accra region (54%), followed by the Eastern (31%) and then the Central region (19%). On the other hand, in the Pra basin, the majority of the respondents were in the Ashanti region (64%), followed by the Eastern region (18%), Central region (11%), Western region (6%) and then Western North region (6%). In terms of gender distribution, the aggregated data of the respondents showed that there were 51 percent males, and the remaining 49 percent were females. In both Densu and Pra, more males were represented (50% and 52%, respectively) than there were females (50% and 48% respectively).

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics of respondents

Sociodemographic Characteristics	Categories (N=1000)	Pooled		Densu		Pra	
		Freq.	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Region	Ashanti	320	32.0			320	64.0
	Central	127	12.7	74	14.8	53	10.6
	Eastern	244	24.4	156	31.2	88	17.6
	Western	29	2.9			29	5.8
	Western North	10	1.0			10	2.0
	Greater Accra	270	27.0	270	54.0		
Gender	Female	490	49.0	249	49.8	241	48.2
	Male	510	51.0	251	50.2	259	51.8
Marital Status	Married	560	56.0	292	58.4	268	53.6
	Consensual union	17	1.7	8	1.6	9	1.8
	Separated	51	5.1	23	4.6	28	5.6
	Divorced	52	5.2	27	5.4	25	5.0
	Widowed	126	12.6	74	14.8	52	10.4
	Single/Never married	136	13.6	63	12.6	73	14.6
	Living together/union	58	5.8	13	2.6	45	9.0
Occupation	Farmer	204	20.4	74	14.8	130	26.0
	Mining	49	4.9	20	4.0	29	5.8
	Private/Other	498	49.8	288	57.6	210	42.0
	Public/Civil	147	14.7	53	10.6	94	18.8
	Unemployed	102	10.2	65	13.0	37	7.4
Household size	1-5	730	73.0	372	74.4	358	71.6
	6-10	254	25.4	121	24.2	133	26.6
	11+	16	1.6	7	1.4	9	1.8
Age	21-30	83	8.3	37	7.4	46	9.2
	31-40	290	29.0	135	27.0	155	31.0
	41-50	244	24.4	138	27.6	106	21.2
	51-60	212	21.2	106	21.2	106	21.2
	61+	171	17.1	84	16.8	87	17.4
Household Income	Below Average	556	55.6	305	61.0	251	50.2
	Average	130	13.0	61	12.2	69	13.8
	Above	314	31.4	134	26.8	180	36.0
Educational Level	None	198	19.8	112	22.4	86	17.2
	Basic	262	26.2	142	28.4	120	24.0
	SHS/Voc	334	33.4	145	29.0	189	37.8
	Post-SHS	206	20.6	101	20.2	105	21.0
Religion	None	71	7.1	22	4.4	49	9.8
	Chris	750	75.0	371	74.2	379	75.8
	Islam	147	14.7	89	17.8	58	11.6
	Traditional	17	1.7	8	1.6	9	1.8
	Other	5	0.5	3	0.6	2	0.4
	Not Disclosed	10	1.0	7	1.4	3	0.6
Trust in Institution	Yes	473	47.3	208	41.6	265	53.0
	No	527	52.7	292	58.4	235	47.0

Source: Author's estimation, 2023

The gender and regional distributions represented the distribution of the household populations in the districts selected for this study and the overall gender and regional distribution in the study areas (GSS, 2021).

The aggregated results also show that the majority of the respondents were married (56%), with a higher proportion of the respondents being married in Densu (58%) than the proportion of the respondents who were married in Pra (54%). The distribution of the household size in the aggregated data showed that the majority of the households maintained a size between 1 and 5 (73%). In the Densu and Pra basins, 74 and 72 percent of the households maintained sizes between 1 and 5, respectively. On the other hand, aggregated data showed that only 2 percent of the respondents maintained a household size of 11 or above. In Densu and Pra, the proportion of the respondents that maintained a household size of 11 and above were 1 percent and 2 percent, respectively. The results showed that overall, the majority of the households maintained small household sizes.

The age distribution of the aggregated data showed that 29 percent of the respondents were between the ages of 31 – 40 years, followed by those between the age bracket 41 – 50 years (24%), and then 51 – 60 years (21.2%). On the other hand, only 8 percent of the respondents are between the age bracket 21 – 30 years in the pooled data. The Pra basin showed a similar distribution as the pooled data with 31 percent, 21 percent and 21 percent in the age bracket of 31 – 40 years, 41 – 50 years, and 51 – 60 years, respectively. On the other hand, only 7 percent of respondents were in the age bracket of 21 – 30 years. In the Densu basin, however, 28 percent of the respondents were in the age bracket of 41 – 50 years, 27 percent were also in the age bracket of 31 – 40 years, and then 21 percent of the respondents were in the age bracket of 51 – 60 years. The results also showed that only 9 percent of respondents in the Pra basin are in the age group of 21 – 30 years.

Household incomes of the respondents in the aggregated data showed that 56 percent of the respondents earn below the average of GHS 30,000 per annum, followed by 31 percent of them who earn above the average, and the remaining 13 percent earn around the average. In the Pra basin, the income distribution showed that 50 percent of the respondents earned below the average income, followed by 36 percent of them who earned above average, and then 14 percent earned about the average income. On the other hand, in Densu, the results showed that 61 percent of the respondents earned above the average income, 27 percent earned below the average and then 12 percent earned about the average. The results further showed that most of the respondents have some level of education. The aggregate data showed that only 20 percent of the households do not have any form of education while the remaining 80 percent have varying degrees of education qualifications. In the Densu and Pra basins, the households that did not have any form of educational qualification were 22 percent and 17 percent, respectively.

The aggregated results for the religious affiliations of respondents indicate that only 7 percent of the households were not affiliated with any religion. In comparison, the remaining 93 percent belonged to the different religions. The aggregated data further showed that 75 percent of respondents indicated that they belonged to the Christian faith, while 15 percent were Muslims. In the Densu and Pra basins, 4 percent and 10 percent were not affiliated with any religion, respectively. Of those who belonged to the various religions in Densu and Pra basins, those who indicated they were Christians were 74 percent and 76 percent, respectively. On the other hand, 18 percent and 12 percent indicated that they were Muslims in the Densu and Pra basins, respectively. The dominance of the Christian faith is consistent with the national distribution of religious affiliations (GSS, 2021).

Moreover, the aggregated results showed that 47 percent of the respondents do not trust the central government institutions in terms of their ability to manage the river basins. In the Densu,

also, 42 percent of the respondents do not have trust in the institutions, while in Pra, 53 percent of the respondents indicated their trust in the institutions.

4.3 Environmental Awareness of Respondents

The first objective was to explore the environmental awareness and view of respondents using the New Ecological Paradigm (NEP) scale by Dunlap et al. (2000). This section first uses frequency distribution tables and charts to show the distribution of the responses. Confirmatory analysis and SEM were then used to examine further the responses.

Table 4.2A shows the description of the items in the NEP scale. Each of the odd numbered items connote ecocentric views while the even numbered items depict anthropocentric views.

Table 4.2A Description of the revised NEP scale

CODE	NEPS ITEM
NEPS1	We are approaching the limit of the number of people the Earth can support.
NEPS2	Humans have the right to modify the natural environment to suit their needs.
NEPS3	When humans interfere with, nature it often produces disastrous consequences.
NEPS4	Human cleverness will ensure that we do not make the Earth not habitable anymore.
NEPS5	Humans are seriously abusing the environment.
NEPS6	The Earth has plenty of natural resources if we just learn how to develop them.
NEPS7	Plants and animals have as much right as humans to exist.
NEPS8	The stability of nature is strong enough to cope with the impacts of modern industrial nations.
NEPS9	Despite our special abilities, humans are still subject to the laws of nature.
NEPS10	The so-called “ecological crisis” facing humankind has been greatly exaggerated.
NEPS11	The Earth is like a spaceship with very limited room and resources.
NEPS12	Humans were meant to rule over the rest of nature.
NEPS13	The stability of nature is very delicate and easily upset.
NEPS14	Humans will eventually learn enough about how nature works to be able to control it.
NEPS15	If things continue on their present course, we will soon experience a major ecological disaster.

4.3.1 Distribution of Environmental Awareness of Respondents

The revised 15 New Ecological Paradigm (NEP) scale proposed by Dunlap et al. (2000) was used in measuring the environmental assessment and view of respondents. Figure 4.1 presents the mean scores for the NEP scales in the pooled data. The results showed that the scores in all three samples were similar. The aggregate data showed that respondents scored the following NEP scales above the average score of 3: NEP 3, 5, 7, 8, 9, 13, and 15. On the other hand, mean scores for NEP scales 1, 2, 4, 6, 10, 11, 12 and 14 were below the average score.

The results indicated that respondents have general environmental awareness of the ecocentric subscales. The only anthropocentric subscale that the respondents have scored high marks on is the NEP 10 (“The so-called “ecological crisis” facing humankind has been greatly exaggerated”). The results indicated that the respondents were greatly aware of the imminent ecological crisis the world is confronted with. For environmental groups and officials, the respondents’ performance on NEP 10 is promising. It suggested that there was a willing audience for laws and programmes meant to deal with environmental concerns. Despite the fact that the majority of respondents did not think the ecological crisis is exaggerated, it is crucial to keep informing and involving the public about the gravity and urgency of environmental challenges. Stronger public support for environmental action can be maintained and built through effective communication and awareness efforts.

On the other hand, the average scores of respondents on the anthropocentric subscales of the NEP were rated as not adequate except for the NEP scale 10. In particular, they performed poorly on the NEP 6 (“The Earth has plenty of natural resources if we just learn how to develop them”). The majority of the respondents were, therefore, of the belief that the earth had an abundance of resources. The limitations of nature were not acknowledged by many, and this has consequences for the efficient use of resources.

Figure 4.1: Mean NEP Scores

According to López-Bonilla and López-Bonilla (2016), anthropocentrism and ecocentrism were essential to the conceptualisation of the NEP. In order to get quick replies without giving it much consideration, they underlined the significance of NEP scaling as an innovative and sophisticated instrument to quantify these conceptualisations in the form of Likert. The NEP scale was said to have two main directions: ecocentric and anthropocentric views (López-Bonilla & López-Bonilla, 2016). In contrast to an anthropocentric perspective, which assumed that humans have the capacity to manage nature and lessen the negative effects of development on it, an ecocentric viewpoint was predicated on the idea that nature had intrinsic value and that people were aware of the importance of protecting it as a common good.

Figure 4.2 presents the scores on the ecocentric subscales, and Figure 4.3 presents the distribution of the responses on the anthropocentric subscales. The scales were rated from 1 –

5 to 1 – 3, indicating levels of agreement as: 1 – agree/ strongly agree (A//SA), 2 – neutral and 3 – disagree/strongly disagree (D/SD).

The results obtained showed that the ecocentric variable with the highest agreement from the respondents was NEP scale 7 (“Plants and animals have as much right as humans to exist.”) with an agreement of 83.5 percent of respondents, followed by 79.3 percent agreement of respondents for NEP 9 (“Despite our special abilities, humans are still subject to the laws of nature.”) and 77.6 percent agreement of respondents for NEP 5 (“Humans are seriously abusing the environment.”). These were indications that the respondents acknowledged nature’s rights and the degradation resulting from human activities.

On the other hand, ecocentric variables such as NEP 1 (“We are approaching the limit of the number of people the Earth can support.”) and NEP 11 (“The Earth is like a spaceship with very limited room and resources.”) received very low agreement ratings from respondents. The results indicated that the respondents had little appreciation for the limits of nature based on the NEP scales.

Figure 4.2: NEP Scores for Eco-centric Variables

Where A=Agree, SA= Strongly Agree, D= Disagree, SD= Strongly Disagree

On anthropocentric views of respondents, the results showed that the variable that received the highest disagreement is the NEP 10 (“The so-called “ecological crisis” facing humankind has been greatly exaggerated.”). The result is an indication that 46 percent of respondents are aware of the ecological crisis facing humankind. On the other hand, the results show that the respondents showed low levels of disagreement with most of the anthropocentric variables and hence, have low levels of awareness regarding the anthropocentric issues. In particular, there was low level of awareness on NEP 6, 12, 14 and 2 where disagreements were only 5.3 percent, 7 percent, 12.9 percent, and 15 percent, respectively. The majority of respondents have a low awareness of NEP 6 (“The Earth has plenty of natural resources if we just learn how to develop them.”) and NEP 12 (“Humans were meant to rule over the rest of nature.”). The results indicate that the respondents had little appreciation of the view that humans should not rule over nature.

Figure 4.3: NEP Scores for Anthropocentric Variables

Where A=Agree, SA= Strongly Agree, D= Disagree, SD= Strongly Disagree

Table 4.2.B presents the frequency distribution of agreements as well as mean scores of environmental awareness across the study areas. The mean scores showed a minimum of 1.2 and a maximum of 2.3. The ratings were from 1 – 3, indicating levels of agreement where 1 indicated agreement/strong agreement, 2 indicated neutral, and 3 indicated disagreement/strong disagreement). In the ecocentric variables, 2 and above represented low awareness, and in the anthropocentric variables, the same score indicated high disagreement and, hence, high environmental awareness of respondents.

The results showed that in the Densu basin, respondents had very high awareness of NEP 9, 7, and 5, with agreement scores of 84 percent, 83 percent, and 82 percent, respectively. However, the respondents had low awareness of NEP 1 and 11, with an agreement level of 43 percent and 35 percent, respectively. In the Pra basin, the respondents had very high ecocentric awareness in NEP 7, 9, and 15 with an agreement level of 84 percent, 74 percent and 74 percent,

respectively. The respondents had low awareness in NEP 1 and 11 as well, with an agreement of 33 percent and 36 percent, respectively. The results implied that in both basins, the level of awareness was high for NEP 5 and 7, with low awareness for NEP 1 and 11.

In terms of anthropocentric awareness, a high mean score indicated disagreement and implied high awareness. The results showed that in the Densu basin, the highest awareness level was in NEP 10 where 59% of the respondents were in disagreement, followed by 30 of the respondents that were in disagreement with NEP 8, and then 28 percent were also in disagreement with NEP 4. On the other hand, low awareness in the Densu basin was in NEP 6, NEP 12 and NEP 14, where respondents had disagreements of 6 percent, 7 percent and 20 percent, respectively. In Pra, the highest level of awareness was in NEP 10, with a disagreement of 35 percent. On the other hand, there were low awareness levels and views in NEP 6, NEP 14, and NEP 12, with a disagreement of 5 percent, 6 percent and 7 percent, respectively.

Table 4.2.B: Frequency distribution and mean NEP scores per basin

Ecocentric Variables	Densu				Pra			
	A/SA	Neutral	D/SD	Mean	A/SA	Neutral	D/SD	Mean
NEP 1	42.6	14.4	43.0	2.0	33.2	34.2	32.6	2.0
NEP 3	66.2	13.4	20.4	1.5	61.0	24.2	14.8	1.5
NEP 5	82.0	10.2	7.8	1.3	73.2	19.0	7.8	1.3
NEP 7	83.0	10.8	6.2	1.2	84.0	6.2	9.8	1.3
NEP 9	84.2	9.2	6.6	1.2	74.4	19.0	6.6	1.3
NEP 11	34.8	17.0	48.2	2.1	35.6	24.6	39.8	2.0
NEP 13	54.0	12.6	33.4	1.8	50.0	31.0	19.0	1.7
NEP 15	75.8	8.0	16.2	1.4	74.0	20.0	6.0	1.3
Anthropocentric Variables	A/SA	Neutral	D/SD	Mean	A/SA	Neutral	D/SD	Mean
NEP 2	69.4	9.6	21.0	1.5	65.2	25.8	9.0	1.4
NEP 4	61.0	10.8	28.2	1.7	56.2	25.4	18.4	1.6
NEP 6	85.2	9.0	5.8	1.2	73.0	22.2	4.8	1.3
NEP 8	53.8	16.0	30.2	1.8	60.8	25.0	14.2	1.5
NEP 10	28.2	13.0	58.8	2.3	42.2	22.8	35.0	1.9
NEP 12	84.0	9.0	7.0	1.2	73.4	19.6	7.0	1.3
NEP 14	65.2	14.6	20.2	1.6	70.4	24.0	5.6	1.4

Where A=Agree, SA= Strongly Agree, D= Disagree, SD= Strongly Disagree

Source: *Author's estimation, 2023*

4.3.2 Determinants of Environmental Awareness

Based on the initial result, the raw alpha was 0.67 for all items which was below the cut-off of 0.70 for acceptable internal consistency, and enters into the realm of what is considered to be of “questionable” internal consistency. Taking a look at the reliability if item is dropped indicated that dropping NEP 7 while retaining all other variables will improve the alpha score to 0.70. The NEP 7 was then dropped and the Cronbach alpha was re-estimated (see Appendix D).

After removing the NEP 7, Cronbach's alpha was more than 0.70, and removing any one item will not cause the Cronbach's alpha for the NEP scale to rise. It was, therefore, appropriate for further analysis and to develop an overall scale score based on the total or mean of the remaining items since, from an empirical standpoint, there is certainty that the remaining items are internally consistent with one another.

Table 4.2.C shows the results of the confirmatory factor analysis of the NEP scale. The results show strong very strong fit indices with Comparative Fit Index (CFI) = 0.976, Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) = 0.968, Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) = 0.054, and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) = 0.073. Loadings for all the item variances ranged between 0.488 and 0.784. Also, as expected, the covariance between the anthropocentric and ecocentric constructs was negative (-0.238) and significant.

Table 4.2.C: Results of Confirmatory Factor Analysis

ANTHRO	Estimate	Std. Err	z-value	P(> z)	Std.lv	Std. all
NEP 2	1.000				0.533	0.533
NEP 4	1.073	0.058	18.481	0.000	0.572	0.572

ANTHRO	Estimate	Std. Err	z-value	P(> z)	Std.lv	Std. all
NEP 6	1.321	0.070	18.965	0.000	0.704	0.704
NEP 8	1.040	0.057	18.098	0.000	0.554	0.554
NEP 14	1.119	0.061	18.291	0.000	0.596	0.596
ECO						
NEP 3	1.000				0.585	0.585
NEP 5	1.223	0.050	24.617	0.000	0.715	0.715
NEP 9	1.207	0.051	23.738	0.000	0.706	0.706
NEP 13	0.795	0.043	18.539	0.000	0.465	0.465
NEP 15	1.211	0.050	24.322	0.000	0.709	0.709
Covariance						
ANTHRO vrs ECO	-0.238	0.017	-13.665	0.000	-0.765	-0.765
Variiances						
NEP 2	0.716				0.716	0.716
NEP 4	0.673				0.673	0.673
NEP 6	0.505				0.505	0.505
NEP 8	0.693				0.693	0.693
NEP 14	0.644				0.644	0.644
NEP 3	0.658				0.658	0.658
NEP 5	0.488				0.488	0.488
NEP 9	0.502				0.502	0.502
NEP 13	0.784				0.784	0.784
NEP 15	0.498				0.498	0.498
ANTHRO	0.284	0.026	10.819	0.000	1.000	1.000
ECO	0.342	0.024	14.054	0.000	1.000	1.000
					Standard	Scaled
Test statistic					7450.192***	
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)					0.976	0.923
Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI)					0.968	0.898
Robust Comparative Fit Index (CFI)						0.888
Robust Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI)						852
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)					0.073	0.092
Robust RMSEA						0.095
Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR)					0.054	0.054

Source: *Author's estimation, 2023*

The results of the determinants of the NEP are presented in Table 4.2.D. The results indicated that gender, income, age, religion, and marital status were the sociodemographic factors influencing the environmental views of respondents. Being male increases awareness levels by

7.5% higher than being female. On the other hand, earning high income decreases anthropocentric awareness by 22.7% less than low-income earners. Therefore, the first null hypothesis that “respondents’ sociodemographic characteristics do not influence their environmental awareness” is rejected.

, while income, age, and married persons were negatively related to anthropocentric views.

Table 4.2.D: Determinants of Environmental Awareness (NEP)

Regression Variables	Anthropocentric			Ecocentric		
	Estimate		Std.Err	Estimate		Std.Err
Altruist	0.091		0.085	0.018		0.088
Egoistic	-0.287	***	0.068	0.228	***	0.070
Gender (Male)	0.075	**	0.038	-0.060		0.040
Income (High)	-0.227	***	0.041	0.138	***	0.042
Educated	0.008		0.046	-0.009		0.049
Age	-0.005	***	0.002	0.011	***	0.002
Basin (Pra)	-0.134	***	0.037	0.049		0.038
Religion (Yes)	0.061		0.070	0.142	*	0.075
Household size	0.006		0.010	-0.009		0.010
Married	-0.069	*	0.039	0.103	***	0.042

Source: Author’s estimation, 2023

4.4 Respondents’ Perceptions of Risk Items

The respondents’ perceptions of risks were examined by first looking at the distribution, and then a factor analysis was performed to determine the broad categories of the risk perceptions.

4.4.1 Distribution of Respondents’ Perceptions of Risk Items

Table 4.3.A shows the mean scores for riskiness of selected human activities, difficulty in controlling the effects of the activities/events and availability of alternative forms of the activities. The aggregated results showed that illegal mining had the highest average mean score of 4.4. This was followed by improper waste disposal, improper use of agrochemicals, cutting down of trees, bush burning, and construction close to the river banks, with a mean score of 4.1, 4.0, 3.8, 3.7, and 3.4, respectively. On the other hand, the pressure ranked below average was drawdown agriculture, with an average score of 2.8.

In the Densu basin, the pressures ranked the highest were improper waste disposal, illegal mining, improper use of agrochemicals, and cutting down of trees, with mean scores of 4.4, 4.2, and 4.2, respectively. On the other hand, in the Pra basin, the highest mean scores on riskiness were illegal mining, bush burning, improper waste disposal, improper use of agrochemicals and cutting down of trees, with mean rankings of 4.6, 3.9, 3.9, 3.8 and 3.8, respectively. Farming at the river banks and construction close to the river banks were perceived to pose a low risk to the water in the Densu basin, while drawdown agriculture and the influx of people to the river sites were the human activities ranked the least risky in the Pra basin.

Table 4.3.A: Mean Risk Scores

Risk Pressures	Riskiness			Difficulty			Availability of alternatives		
	Pooled (SD)	Densu (SD)	Pra (SD)	Pooled (SD)	Densu (SD)	Pra (SD)	Pooled (SD)	Densu (SD)	Pra (SD)
Destructive fishing methods	3.5 (1.36)	3.4 (1.55)	3.5 (1.14)	3.4 (1.70)	2.3 (1.03)	4.5 (1.40)	2.4 (1.16)	2.1 (1.09)	2.7 (1.18)
Farming at the riverbanks	3.4 (1.43)	3.2 (1.67)	3.6 (1.10)	3.2 (1.75)	2.1 (1.24)	4.3 (1.41)	2.5 (1.17)	2.2 (1.10)	2.8 (1.17)
Draw-down agriculture	2.8 (1.57)	2.6 (1.76)	3.1 (1.31)	3.5 (1.80)	2.3 (1.16)	4.8 (1.40)	1.9 (0.99)	1.7 (0.95)	2.0 (1.01)
Improper use of agro-chemicals and fertilisers close to riverbanks	4.0 (1.08)	4.2 (1.11)	3.8 (1.02)	3.3 (1.81)	2.1 (1.35)	4.4 (1.39)	2.8 (1.24)	2.6 (1.25)	2.9 (1.21)
Cutting down of trees close to the riverbanks	3.8 (1.19)	3.8 (1.38)	3.8 (0.97)	3.4 (1.76)	2.4 (1.45)	4.4 (1.40)	2.8 (1.25)	2.6 (1.29)	2.9 (1.19)
Improper waste disposal	4.1 (0.97)	4.4 (0.96)	3.9 (0.93)	3.2 (1.74)	2.3 (1.47)	4.1 (1.51)	3.2 (1.36)	3.2 (1.51)	3.1 (1.19)
Illegal mining practices	4.4 (1.09)	4.2 (1.32)	4.6 (0.74)	3.4 (2.15)	1.6 (1.01)	5.1 (1.42)	2.5 (1.34)	2.3 (1.34)	2.7 (1.31)
Sand-winning from the riverbanks	3.6 (1.32)	3.5 (1.53)	3.7 (1.06)	3.4 (1.74)	2.4 (1.34)	4.5 (1.47)	2.5 (1.16)	2.2 (1.05)	2.7 (1.20)
Construction close to the river banks	3.4 (1.39)	3.3 (1.62)	3.6 (1.09)	3.4 (1.74)	2.3 (1.29)	4.5 (1.44)	2.4 (1.24)	2.1 (1.12)	2.7 (1.28)
Influx of people to this locality	3.3 (1.45)	3.4 (1.58)	3.2 (1.31)	3.2 (1.88)	2.0 (1.19)	4.5 (1.53)	2.3 (1.23)	2.1 (1.10)	2.6 (1.29)
Bush burning	3.7 (1.29)	3.5 (1.48)	3.9 (1.04)	3.5 (1.82)	2.5 (1.47)	4.5 (1.52)	2.4 (1.18)	2.3 (1.18)	2.5 (1.18)

SD= Standard Deviation.

Source: *Author's estimation, 2023*

The distribution of respondents' perception of risk is presented in Table 4.3.B. Destructive fishing method was perceived by most of the respondents as extremely risky by 28 percent of the respondents, followed by 25 percent of the respondents who perceived destructive fishing methods as very risky. Farming at the river banks was perceived by 31 percent of the respondents as extremely risky, followed by 24 percent of the respondents who perceived it as moderately risky. Draw-down agriculture was perceived by 32 percent of the respondents as not all risky, followed by 24 percent who perceived it as extremely risky. In terms of respondents' perception of improper use of agrochemicals and fertilisers, 41 percent of the respondents perceived it as extremely risky, followed by 31 percent of the respondents who perceived it as very risky.

Cutting down of trees close to the river was perceived by 37 percent of the respondents as extremely risky, followed by 25 percent who perceived it as very risky. Improper waste disposal was perceived by 46 percent of the respondents as extremely risky, followed by 31 percent of the respondents who perceived it as very risky. The majority of the respondents (66%) perceived illegal mining as extremely risky, followed by 21 percent of the respondents who perceived it as very risky, while the remaining perceived it as less risky. Sand-winning was perceived by 32 percent and 29 percent of the respondents as extremely risky and very risky, respectively, while the least proportion of the sample perceived the activity as slightly risky (7%). Construction close to river banks was perceived by the respondents as extremely risky, moderately risky and very risky by 29 percent, 25 percent and 24 percent of the respondents, respectively. The influx of people was also perceived by the respondents as extremely risky, very risky and slightly risky by 30 percent, 21 percent and 17 percent of the respondents, respectively. Finally, bush burning was perceived by the respondents as extremely risky, moderately risky and very risky by 38 percent, 23 percent and 22 percent of the respondents, respectively.

Table 4.3.B: Distribution of Risk Perception Scores

Risk Pressures	Not at all risky		Slightly risky		Moderately risky		Very risky		Extremely risky	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Destructive fishing methods	145	14.5	81	8.1	237	23.7	253	25.3	284	28.4
Farming at the riverbanks	166	16.6	83	8.3	238	23.8	195	19.5	318	31.8
Draw-down agriculture	319	31.9	147	14.7	162	16.2	136	13.6	236	23.6
Improper use of agro-chemicals and fertilisers close to riverbanks	37	3.7	59	5.9	183	18.3	310	31.0	411	41.1
Cutting down of trees close to the riverbanks	58	5.8	82	8.2	235	23.5	252	25.2	373	37.3
Improper waste disposal	17	1.7	43	4.3	174	17.4	306	30.6	460	46.0
Illegal mining practices	59	5.9	20	2.0	58	5.8	208	20.8	655	65.5
Sand-winning from the riverbanks	120	12.0	73	7.3	197	19.7	293	29.3	317	31.7
Construction close to the river banks	160	16.0	68	6.8	245	24.5	236	23.6	291	29.1
Influx of people to this locality	158	15.8	168	16.8	161	16.1	212	21.2	301	30.1
Bush burning	90	9.0	84	8.4	225	22.5	220	22.0	381	38.1

Source: *Author's estimation, 2023*

The results showed that the null hypothesis that “respondents do not have high perceptions of risky activities” could not be accepted in favour of the alternative hypothesis that “respondents have high perceptions of risky activities”

4.4.2 Factor Analysis of Respondents’ Perception of Risks

Table 4.4 shows the results of the factor analysis on the risk perception of respondents. The Cronbach’s alpha test was performed to determine the reliability and consistency of the items. Two of the human activities—bush burning and destructive fishing methods—were dropped for poor loading and an indication of inconsistency. The final alpha after dropping these two was greater than the 0.7 acceptable value. The factor analysis was therefore performed on the nine items remaining.

Three factors were deemed the minimum number of factors appropriate for the data (see Appendix D2 for results of the test to determine the appropriate number of factors). The three factors were named "Agricultural Practices", "Urban Development and Population Pressure", and "Environmental Degradation" activities.

Agricultural Practices: This factor concentrates on detrimental agricultural practices, such as farming and draw-down agriculture that occur close to riverbanks. The term "Agricultural Practices" highlights how agricultural activities affects water bodies.

Urban Development and Population Pressure: This factor includes activities associated with urbanisation and an increase in human population near riverbanks, which can endanger water bodies. Illegal mining, construction, sand-winning, and an influx of people are all part of it.

Environmental Degradation: This factor represents actions that damage the environment close to riverbanks, such as improper waste disposal, tree-cutting, and the misuse of fertilisers and agrochemicals. The term "Environmental Degradation" draws attention to its detrimental effects on the environment.

Table 4.4: Results of Factor Analysis

Risk Pressers	Agricultural Practices	Urban Development and Population Pressure	Environmental Degradation	h2	u2	com
Farming at the riverbanks	0.88			0.78	0.22	1.00
Draw-down agriculture	0.45			0.46	0.54	1.90
illegal mining practices		0.53		0.24	0.76	1.10
Sand-winning from the riverbanks		0.70		0.48	0.52	1.00
Construction close to the river banks		0.57		0.47	0.53	1.30
Influx of people to this locality		0.61		0.42	0.58	1.10
Improper use of agro-chemicals and fertilisers close to riverbanks			0.63	0.42	0.58	1.00
Cutting down of trees close to the riverbanks			0.47	0.39	0.61	1.60
Improper waste disposal			0.56	0.32	0.68	1.20

Source: *Author's estimation, 2023*

4.5 Preference and willingness to pay for water-related ecosystem services

The preference and willingness to pay results are presented in Table 4.5. The multinomial logit model was considered for this data (see the appendix E1). However, the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) revealed that the random parameter logit model was a better fit for the data. The preference models from the pooled data and the two basins (Densu and Pra) produced AIC figures of 11536.5, 6032.2, and 5446.2, respectively. Similarly, BIC figures obtained were 11695.7, 6175.4, and 5589.5 respectively. The standard deviations of the parameters in random logit models are also presented in the appendix as E2.

The positive sign for the coefficients of all outcome attributes (such as high or medium levels of erosion control, flood control, surface water quality, fish biodiversity and cultural services) indicated incremental utility levels compared to base categories (such as low levels of erosion control, flood control, surface water quality, fish biodiversity and cultural services), and a negative sign associated with cost revealed disutility from higher utility bills.

Table 4.5 (A) Results of the Mixed Logit Model for Preference for Water-Related Ecosystem Services

Variables (Preference)	Model (1)			Model (2)			Model (3)		
	Pooled			Densu			Pra		
	Estimate		Std. Error	Estimate		Std. Error	Estimate		Std. Error
Cost	-0.008	***	0.000	-0.006	***	0.001	-0.010	***	0.001
Flood Protection (Medium)	0.683	***	0.051	0.650	***	0.072	0.730	***	0.075
Flood Protection (High)	0.791	***	0.052	0.706	***	0.075	0.937	***	0.078
Erosion Control (Medium)	0.495	***	0.044	0.607	***	0.065	0.388	***	0.062
Erosion Control (High)	0.859	***	0.057	0.867	***	0.082	0.800	***	0.079
Surface Water Quality (Medium)	0.658	***	0.053	0.614	***	0.074	0.727	***	0.079
Surface Water Quality (High)	1.131	***	0.075	1.069	***	0.103	1.296	***	0.120
Biodiversity of Fish (Medium)	0.488	***	0.055	0.526	***	0.080	0.454	***	0.078
Biodiversity of Fish (High)	0.638	***	0.053	0.707	***	0.077	0.617	***	0.077
Cultural Services (Medium)	0.255	***	0.047	0.176	**	0.066	0.364	***	0.068
Cultural Services (High)	0.211	***	0.045	0.230	***	0.064	0.224	***	0.065
ASC(Opt_Out)	-2.919	***	0.297	-2.206	***	0.360	-2.872	***	0.333
Log-Likelihood	-5745.267			-2993.105			-2700.113		
Null Log-Likelihood	-8230.803			-4109.909			-4120.895		
AIC	11536.534			6032.211			5446.227		
BIC	11695.730			6175.434			5589.512		
McFadden R ²	0.302			0.272			0.345		
Adj McFadden R ²	0.299			0.266			0.339		
Number of Observations	7492			3741			3751		

Significance codes: '****' 0.001 '***' 0.01 '**' 0.05 '.' 0.1

Source: Author's estimation, 2023

Table 4.5 (B) Results of the Mixed Logit Model for Willingness to pay for water-related ecosystem services

Variables (WTP)	MWTP (1)			MWTP (2)			MWTP (3)		
	Pooled			Densu			Pra		
	Estimate	***	Conf. Int.	Estimate	***	Conf. Int.	Estimate	***	Conf. Int.
Flood Protection (Medium)	87.605	***	[72.38, 103.39]	116.000	***	[81.32, 151.34]	71.897	***	8.155
Flood Protection (High)	104.630	***	[85.47, 118.11]	128.160	***	[92.02, 165.59]	92.433	***	8.537
Erosion Control (Medium)	64.454	***	[50.42, 76.54]	108.740	***	[76.31, 141.38]	38.218	***	6.558
Erosion Control (High)	98.055	***	[92.37, 128.15]	139.690	***	[100.62, 180.21]	78.876	***	8.835
Surface Water Quality (Medium)	87.509	***	[69.53, 99.43]	110.350	***	[77.02, 143.88]	71.727	***	7.911
Surface Water Quality (High)	151.610	***	[122.09, 168.14]	195.220	***	[142.19, 247.85]	127.840	***	12.494
Biodiversity of Fish (Medium)	57.487	***	[48.57, 76.87]	90.559	***	[58.80, 122.87]	44.760	***	7.649
Biodiversity of Fish (High)	85.004	***	[66.92, 96.89]	127.980	***	[90.93, 165.46]	60.786	***	7.797
Cultural Services (Medium)	35.315	***	[20.71, 44.93]	32.633	**	[8.57, 57.54]	35.922	***	6.872
Cultural Services (High)	29.165	***	[15.72, 38.47]	41.140	***	[17.85, 64.79]	22.059	***	6.326
ASC(Opt_Out)	-364.010	***	[-462.41, -285.52]	-317.000	***	[-451.63, -180.68]	-283.320	***	38.844
Log-Likelihood	-5755.142			-2991.812			-2700.114		
Null Log-Likelihood	-8230.803			-4109.909			-4120.895		
AIC	11556.284			6029.623			5446.228		
BIC	11715.481			6172.847			5589.513		
McFadden R ²	0.301			0.272			0.345		
Adj McFadden R ²	0.298			0.266			0.339		
Number of Observations	7492			3741			3751		

Significance codes: '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1

Source: Author's estimation, 2023

The negative and statistically significant coefficient of the ASC in all models reflected net positive utilities on any of the PES management options other than the status quo. The results showed that, on average, PES programs that enhanced flood control, erosion control, surface water quality, biodiversity (fish) and cultural services elicited a higher probability of respondents' participation over their corresponding status quo.

The results of the willingness to pay showed that overall, respondents were willing to pay between GHS 87.61 and GHS 104.63 per household per month for improvement in medium to high protection in flood; GHS 64.45 and GHS 98.06 per household per month for medium to high improvement in erosion control; GHS 87.51 and GHS 151.61 per household per month for improvements in surface water quality; GHS 57.49 and GHS 85.00 per household per month for medium to high improvements in fish biodiversity; and between GHS 35.32 and GHS 29.17 per household per month for medium to high improvements in the availability of cultural services compared to the low level of providing these services.

In the Densu basin, respondents were willing to pay between GHS 116.00 and GHS 128.16 for improvements in flood protection compared to the payment between GHS 71.90 and GHS 92.43 in the Pra basin for the same levels of improvements. Respondents in the Densu basin were also willing to pay GHS 108.74 and GHS 139.69 for improvements in erosion control, while in the Pra basin, respondents were willing to pay GHS 38.23 and GHS 78.88 for the same levels of improvements in erosion control. The results also showed that respondents in the Densu basin were willing to pay GHS 110.35 and GHS 195.22 for improvements in surface water quality compared to their counterparts in the Pra basin, who were willing to pay GHS 71.73 and GHS 127.84 for improvements in surface water quality. Respondents in the Densu basin were willing to pay GHS 90.56 and GHS 127.98 for improvements in fish biodiversity, while in the Pra basin, respondents were willing to pay GHS 44.76 and GHS 60.79 for

improvements in fish biodiversity. Finally, respondents in the Densu basin were willing to pay between GHS 32.63 and GHS 41.14 for improvements in opportunities for cultural services compared to their counterparts in the Pra basin, who were willing to pay between GHS 35.92 and GHS 22.06 for the same levels of improvements in cultural services.

The results show that a high level of improvement in surface water quality was the most important as willingness to pay was the highest in the Densu and Pra basins. Willingness to pay value for improvements in water quality was higher among respondents in the Densu basin than the value for the respondents in the Pra basin. Previous studies have found water quality to be the most important attribute in payments for ecosystem services. The functions of water ecosystems depend not only on the quantity but also on the quality of the water. Hence, improvements in water quality could also improve the availability and quality of other water-related ecosystem services. This proposition is supported by the positive and significant determinants reported in previous studies (Chaikaew et al., 2017; Beaumais, Briand, Millok, & Nauges, 2014; Wang, He, Kim, & Kamata, 2013; Hite, Hudson, & Intarapapong, 2002)). Othman, Lip, and Jafari (2014) obtained a WTP of \$13.3 biweekly per residence for an improvement in the water quality in Kajang, Malaysia. Similarly, a WTP of \$4.4 per home per two months was found by So-Yoon, Seung-Hoon, and Chang-Seob (2013) in research in Bosun, South Korea. Water quality is, thus, a prerequisite that cannot be negotiated. The capacity of water to carry out these tasks depends heavily on the quality of the water.

People are generally willing to pay a significant amount for improvements in water quality, according to research on willingness to pay for such improvements. For a five-year period, Chinese households were prepared to pay 74 Yuan (or US\$12.33 in 2012 prices) per household per month to achieve a particular degree of improved water quality (Wang, He, Kim, & Kamata, 2013).

Willingness to pay for improvements in flood protection was also found to be positive and statistically significant across the study areas. Willingness to pay for flood protection was higher among respondents in the Densu basin compared to values for respondents in the Pra basin. The positive and significant effect of flood protection was similar to the results found in past studies. The WTP for enhancing flood protection was consistent with the results of the study by Ryffel, Rid, and Grêt-Regamey (2014) in the Swiss Alps. They found that respondents would be prepared to give up much agricultural land in exchange for flood protection. In Polanand, Birol, Karousakis, and Koundouri (2009) similarly investigated the readiness of local people to pay for ecosystem services provided by wetlands. Their research showed that local people valued the specified ecological services, such as flood protection, highly.

Erosion control was also found to be positive and significant, indicating that any policy to improve erosion control will gain support from the residents in both Densu and Pra basins. Erosion is a major problem with land usage that has an effect on economic operations, including agriculture, recreational amenities, and urban growth. Effective management of erosion requires mobilising public support and creating value for controlling erosion. The results showed that respondents were willing to pay for high erosion control, with respondents in the Densu basin willing to pay more than those in the Pra basin. A study by Ardeshiri et al. (2019) of coastal preferences for soil erosion interventions in New South Wales revealed endorsement for various management strategies. Similarly, a study in New Zealand on erosion control and other management attributes revealed significant WTP values (Matthews, Scarpa, & Marsh, 2017).

Similar to previous studies, the current study found that respondents had high WTP values for improvements in fish biodiversity. Mamboleo and Adem (2023) found a very strong WTP for preserving biodiversity in Lake Victoria. Roy et al. (2023) also found that local fishing households in the Indian Sundarbans strongly favoured the conservation of biodiversity.

Finally, the study revealed that respondents were WTP for improvements in opportunities for cultural services. Massive endorsements and WTP for the enhancement of many cultural services, such as cultural heritage (Bertacchinia & Sultanb, 2019) and aesthetic values (Acharya, Maraseni, & Cockfield, 2021), have been found in the past. In Santander, Spain, research by Remoundou, Diaz-Simal, Koundouri, and Rulleau (2015) found that local people were prepared to pay to reduce the negative effects of erosion and flooding on their health and the environment. Birol, Karousakis, and Koundouri (2006) also found positive and significant values for biodiversity conservation in Poland.

The results implied that the null hypothesis that “respondents do not prefer improved levels of water-related ecosystem services (flood control, erosion control, surface water quality, fish abundance and species, and cultural services) and are not willing to pay (WTP) for them” could not be accepted

Table 4.6 presents the sociodemographic and environmental determinants of preference for water-related ecosystem services of respondents in the Densu and Pra basins. The results of the sociodemographic estimates for pooled, Densu and Pra showed that the AIC (11514.536, 6008.165, and 5434.351, respectively) and the BIC (11763.714, 6226.114, and 5652.393, respectively) are lower than their corresponding models without the interactions of the sociodemographic and environmental variables. This indicated that there was an improvement in the model and signifies that the sociodemographic characteristics were important predictors of the willingness to pay.

Table 4.6 Sociodemographic and Environmental Determinants of Preference for Water-Related Ecosystem Services

Variables	Model (4)			Model (5)			Model (6)		
	Pooled			Densu			Pra		
	Estimate	Std. Error		Estimate	Std. Error		Estimate	Std. Error	
Cost (GHS)	-0.008	***	0.000	-0.005	***	0.001	-0.010	***	0.001
Flood Protection (Medium)	0.635	***	0.055	0.503	***	0.080	0.753	***	0.078
Flood Protection (High)	0.786	***	0.057	0.593	***	0.083	1.008	***	0.079
Erosion Control (Medium)	0.468	***	0.046	0.549	***	0.067	0.414	***	0.064
Erosion Control (High)	0.819	***	0.057	0.717	***	0.076	0.795	***	0.078
Surface Water Quality (Medium)	0.650	***	0.054	0.571	***	0.076	0.730	***	0.076
Surface Water Quality (High)	1.115	***	0.077	1.059	***	0.105	1.209	***	0.114
Biodiversity of Fish (Medium)	0.494	***	0.055	0.527	***	0.077	0.444	***	0.077
Biodiversity of Fish (High)	0.642	***	0.054	0.715	***	0.076	0.623	***	0.079
Cultural Services (Medium)	0.257	***	0.046	0.189	**	0.065	0.338	***	0.067
Cultural Services (High)	0.212	***	0.044	0.248	***	0.063	0.198	**	0.065
ASC (Opt_Out)	-1.138	**	0.435	0.101		0.528	-2.798	***	0.684
ASC X Male	-0.244		0.273	-0.173		0.425	-0.033		0.386
ASC X Educated	-0.800	*	0.323	-2.207	***	0.586	0.456		0.528
ASC X Income	-0.330		0.313	-1.181	**	0.425	-0.405		0.431
ASC X Basin (Pra)	-1.231	***	0.274						
ASC X ProNEP	-0.462	.	0.268	-0.323		0.415	-1.254	***	0.374
FPM X Exp (Flooding)	0.192	.	0.110	0.413	**	0.136	-0.192		0.207
FPH X Exp (Flooding)	-0.008		0.113	0.362	*	0.141	-0.708	***	0.213
ECM X Exp (Erosion)	0.333	*	0.152	0.416	*	0.177	-0.331		0.315
ECH X Exp (Erosion)	0.362	*	0.183	0.438	*	0.206	0.120		0.416
SWQM X Exp (disease outbreak)	0.110		0.161	0.529	*	0.228	-0.279		0.226
SWQH X Exp (disease outbreak)	0.316		0.225	0.207		0.307	0.591	.	0.323
BIOM X Exp (Reduction in fish)	0.026		0.296	-0.501		0.383	0.647		0.445
BIOH X Exp (Reduction in fish)	0.065		0.280	-0.057		0.366	0.090		0.421
Log-Likelihood	-5721.268			-2969.083			-2682.175		
Null Log-Likelihood	-8230.803			-4109.909			-4120.895		
AIC	11514.536			6008.165			5434.351		
BIC	11763.714			6226.114			5652.393		
McFadden R2	0.305			0.278			0.349		
Adj McFadden R2	0.301			0.269			0.341		
Number of Observations	7492			3741			3751		

Significance codes: '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Source: *Author's estimation, 2023*

ASC – Alternative specific constant, FPM – Flood protection (medium), FPH – Flood protection (high), ECM – Erosion control (medium), ECH – Erosion control (high), SWQM – surface water quality (medium), SWQH – surface water quality (high), BIOM – biodiversity (medium), BIOH – biodiversity (high). Exp is whether a respondent experienced flooding, erosion, outbreak of disease and reduction in fish.

All the WES attributes were still positive and statistically significant, indicating that respondents were willing to participate in programmes that sought to improve flood protection, erosion control, surface water quality, fish biodiversity and cultural services. The cost variable was also negative and statistically significant, as expected. The interaction between the ASC and the sociodemographic variables was meant to measure the influence of the variables in influencing decisions to participate or otherwise in programmes that sought to ensure payments for WES.

The pooled data showed that the interactions between the ASC (opt_out) and education and Basin (Pra) were all significant and negative, indicating that being educated and being in the Pra basin all reduced the likelihood of opting out of a programme that sought to encourage payments towards conserving WES. In the Densu basin, educated respondents and those earning income above the average were the only significant sociodemographic characteristics, and they were both negative, as in the pooled sample.

The result obtained in this current study was similar to some studies in the literature. For instance, Beaumais, Briand, Millok, & Nauges (2014) discovered that there is a positive correlation between income, education, environmental concerns, and health and taste concerns with tap water and the willingness to pay for improved tap water quality.

On the other hand, other studies found a negative influence of sociodemographic characteristics on willingness to pay for ecological conservation. For instance, a study by Ogunniyi et al. (2011) found that household income had a negative and significant effect on consumers' willingness to pay for more readily available water.

Environmental variables also exhibited a significant relationship with WTP. The results indicated that an interaction between the ASC and Pro-NEP was negative in the pooled data and in Pra, indicating that Pro-NEP respondents were less likely to opt out of any programme

towards conservation or improving the WES in the basins. Also, an interaction between respondents who have experienced flooding, erosion, disease outbreaks relating to water, and reductions in fish biodiversity in the past and their corresponding attribute levels indicated that those who had negative experiences in the past had a higher preference than those who did not. For example, in the pooled results, an interaction between experience of erosion in the past and preference for medium and high improvements in erosion control resulted in 0.333 and 0.362, respectively. Thus, respondents who experienced erosion in the past had a positive preference for medium and high levels of improvements in the programmes that seek to control erosion and are more likely to pay for or participate in those programmes

4.6 Effect of Change in the Payment Vehicle on Preference and Willingness to Pay

The results for the preference and willingness to volunteer labour days are presented in Table 4.7A and 4.7B. The multinomial logit model was considered for this data (see the appendix E1). However, the AIC and BIC showed that the random parameter logit model was a better fit for this data. The preference models from the pooled data and the basins (Densu and Pra) specific results showed AIC figures of 11500.8, 5973.8, and 5439.1, respectively. In addition, BIC figures obtained were 11701.5, 6148.2, and 5613.5 respectively. The standard deviations of the parameters in random logit models were also presented in the appendix as E2.

The positive signs for the coefficients of all outcome attributes (such as high or medium levels of erosion control, flood control, surface water quality, fish biodiversity and cultural services) indicated incremental utility levels as compared to base categories (low levels of erosion control, flood control, surface water quality, fish biodiversity and cultural services). The negative sign associated with cost (labour days) revealed disutility from higher utility bills in line with the theory of demand.

Table 4.7A: Results of the Mixed Logit Model for Preference for Water-Related Ecosystem Services (Time Payment)

Variables (Preference)	Model (7)			Model (8)			Model (9)		
	Pooled			Densu			Pra		
	Estimate		Std. Error	Estimate		Std. Error	Estimate		Std. Error
Cost	-0.039	***	0.005	-0.064	***	0.008	-0.018	*	0.008
Flood Protection (Medium)	0.548	***	0.041	0.631	***	0.060	0.551	***	0.066
Flood Protection (High)	0.721	***	0.050	0.903	***	0.077	0.599	***	0.070
Erosion Control (Medium)	0.327	***	0.042	0.287	***	0.063	0.430	***	0.063
Erosion Control (High)	0.496	***	0.041	0.468	***	0.061	0.599	***	0.062
Surface Water Quality (Medium)	0.472	***	0.046	0.195	**	0.068	0.816	***	0.073
Surface Water Quality (High)	0.870	***	0.066	0.532	***	0.101	1.277	***	0.103
Biodiversity of Fish (Medium)	0.337	***	0.043	0.231	***	0.065	0.469	***	0.063
Biodiversity of Fish (High)	0.403	***	0.049	0.185	*	0.076	0.675	***	0.080
Cultural Services (Medium)	0.247	***	0.042	0.211	***	0.063	0.355	***	0.066
Cultural Services (High)	0.156	***	0.040	0.155	**	0.059	0.163	**	0.058
ASC(Opt_Out)	-4.581	***	0.391	-4.109	***	0.481	-4.948	***	0.813
Log-Likelihood	-5766.984			-2874.322			-2825.613		
Null Log-Likelihood	-8248.381			-4129.684			-4118.697		
AIC	11579.969			5794.644			5697.225		
BIC	11739.215			5937.978			5840.498		
McFadden R ²	0.301			0.304			0.314		
Adj McFadden R ²	0.298			0.298			0.308		
Number of Observations	7508			3759			3749		

Significance codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1

Source: Author's estimation, 2023

Table 4.7B Results of the Mixed Logit Model for Willingness to work for water-related ecosystem services conservation

Variables	MWTW (7)			MWTW (8)			MWTW (9)		
	Pooled			Densu			Pra		
	Estimate	Conf. Int.		Estimate	Conf. Int.		Estimate	Conf. Int.	
Flood Protection (Medium)	14.102 ***	[9.64, 18.49]		9.808 ***	[0.025, 0.975]		29.863 *	[4.74, 55.68]	
Flood Protection (High)	18.566 ***	[13.05, 23.96]		14.026 ***	[6.82, 12.76]		32.408 *	[6.08, 59.27]	
Erosion Control (Medium)	8.440 ***	[5.40, 11.55]		4.465 ***	[10.10, 17.84]		23.330 *	[3.56, 43.12]	
Erosion Control (High)	12.753 ***	[8.86, 16.69]		7.268 ***	[2.29, 6.61]		32.487 *	[5.61, 59.40]	
Surface Water Quality (Medium)	12.159 ***	[8.34, 15.99]		3.030 **	[4.71, 9.77]		44.245 *	[7.48, 81.02]	
Surface Water Quality (High)	22.429 ***	[15.79, 29.01]		8.257 ***	[0.95, 5.12]		69.361 *	[12.45, 126.23]	
Biodiversity of Fish (Medium)	8.657 ***	[5.67, 11.69]		3.581 ***	[4.75, 11.66]		25.393 *	[4.33, 46.93]	
Biodiversity of Fish (High)	10.387 ***	[6.73, 14.00]		2.866 *	[1.52, 5.67]		36.534 *	[5.70, 67.23]	
Cultural Services (Medium)	6.393 ***	[3.71, 9.09]		3.270 **	[0.54, 5.21]		19.294 *	[2.24, 36.34]	
Cultural Services (High)	4.058 ***	[1.82, 6.26]		2.398 *	[1.22, 5.31]		8.943 .	[-0.44, 18.00]	
ASC(Opt_Out)	-117.570 ***	[-155.42, -80.13]		-63.894 ***	[0.53, 4.24]		-269.430 *	[-504.50, -31.73]	
Log-Likelihood	-5766.990			-2874.322			-2825.626		
Null Log-Likelihood	-8248.381			-4129.684			-4118.697		
AIC	11579.980			5794.644			5697.251		
BIC	11739.226			5937.978			5840.524		
McFadden R ²	0.301			0.304			0.314		
Adj McFadden R ²	0.298			0.298			0.308		
Number of Observations	7508			3759			3749		

Significance codes: 0 ‘***’ 0.001 ‘**’ 0.01 ‘*’ 0.05 ‘.’ 0.1

Source: Author’s estimation, 2023

The negative and statistically significant coefficient of the ASC in all the models reflected a net positive utility on any of the PES management options other than the status quo. The results showed that, on average, PES programmes that enhanced flood protection, erosion control, surface water quality, biodiversity (fish), and cultural services elicited a higher probability of respondents' participation over their corresponding status quo.

The results of the willingness to pay show that overall, respondents were willing to volunteer between 14 and 19 days per household per month for improvements in medium to high protection in flood, 8 and 13 days per household per month for medium to high improvements in erosion control, 12 and 22 days per household per month for improvements in surface water quality; 9 and 10 days per household per month for medium to high improvements in fish biodiversity; and between 6 and 4 days per household per month for medium to high improvements in the availability of cultural services compared to the low level of providing these services. In the Densu basin, respondents were willing to volunteer between 10 and 14 days for improvements in flood protection compared to their compatriots volunteering between 30 and 32 days in the Pra basin for the same levels of improvements. Respondents in the Densu basin were also willing to volunteer 4 and 7 days for improvements in erosion control, while in the Pra basin, respondents were willing to volunteer 23 and 32 days for the same levels of improvements in erosion control. The results showed that respondents in the Densu basin were willing to volunteer 3 and 8 days for improvements in surface water quality compared to those in the Pra basin, where respondents were willing to volunteer 44 and 69 days for improvements in surface water quality. Respondents in the Densu basin were willing to volunteer for 4 and 3 days for improvements in fish biodiversity. In contrast, in the Pra basin, respondents were willing to volunteer 25 and 36 days for improvements in fish biodiversity. Finally, respondents in the Densu were willing to volunteer 3 and 2 days for improvements in opportunities for

cultural services. In contrast, in the Pra basin, respondents were willing to volunteer 19 and 9 days for the same levels of improvements in cultural services.

Non-monetary contributions like volunteer labour are considered practical for low-income welfare measures, and hence, the positive and significant values for the improvements in the water-related ecosystem services could improve conservation decisions and encourage participation by all stakeholders (Ando, Cadavid, Netusil, & Parthum, 2020; Gibson, Rigby, & Polya, 2016; Lankia, Neuvonen, Pouta, & Sievänen, 2014).

Based on the results as discussed above, the null hypothesis that “using labour days will not result in higher WTP for water-related ecosystem services (WES)” could not be accepted.

Table 4.8 presents the monetised equivalent of the willingness to donate labour. In order to establish a measure of value, the choice experiment literature predominately presents cost in terms of money. Although practice and scarcity value estimates differ greatly, one-third of the wage rate is frequently employed as an estimate of the scarcity value of time for this reason (English et al., 2018). According to recent studies on the value of time, such as that by Fezzi, Bateman, and Ferrini (2014), the value of time is context-dependent and may exceed one-third of the pay rate. Some even discover that the wage and the worth of a person's time have virtually little in common.

The table presents the monetised value of time using the conventional one-third of the minimum wage rate in Ghana, which is GHS 14.88 (English et al., 2018). The results of the monetised models from the pooled data, as well as data on the respondents in the Densu and Pra basins, showed AIC figures of 11578.5, 5794.6, and 5697.2, respectively, and BIC figures of 11737.7, 5937.9, and 5840.4 respectively. These figures were compared to their corresponding values from the model estimated with time (labour days).

Table 4.8: Monetised Equivalence of Time

Variables	Model (10)			Model (11)			Model (12)		
	Pooled			Densu			Pra		
	Estimate		Std. Error	Estimate		Std. Error	Estimate		Std. Error
Cost	-0.008	***	0.001	-0.013	***	0.002	-0.004	*	0.002
Flood Protection (Medium)	0.553	***	0.042	0.632	***	0.060	0.551	***	0.066
Flood Protection (High)	0.725	***	0.051	0.903	***	0.077	0.599	***	0.070
Erosion Control (Medium)	0.324	***	0.042	0.288	***	0.063	0.430	***	0.063
Erosion Control (High)	0.497	***	0.041	0.468	***	0.061	0.599	***	0.062
Surface Water Quality (Medium)	0.470	***	0.046	0.195	**	0.068	0.816	***	0.073
Surface Water Quality (High)	0.869	***	0.066	0.532	***	0.101	1.277	***	0.103
Biodiversity of Fish (Medium)	0.338	***	0.043	0.231	***	0.065	0.469	***	0.063
Biodiversity of Fish (High)	0.404	***	0.049	0.185	*	0.076	0.675	***	0.080
Cultural Services (Medium)	0.248	***	0.042	0.211	***	0.063	0.355	***	0.066
Cultural Services (High)	0.156	***	0.040	0.155	**	0.059	0.163	**	0.058
ASC(Opt_Out)	-4.559	***	0.392	-4.107	***	0.481	-4.951	***	0.814
Log-Likelihood	-5766.242			-2874.297			-2825.578		
Null Log-Likelihood	-8248.381			-4129.684			-4118.697		
AIC	11578.483			5794.595			5697.157		
BIC	11737.729			5937.928			5840.430		
McFadden R ²	0.301			0.304			0.314		
Adj McFadden R ²	0.298			0.298			0.308		
Number of Observations	7508			3759			3749		

Significance codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1

Source: Author's estimation, 2023

The results showed that the models for the pooled and Pra show AIC and BIC that are lower than the corresponding values for the model where time (labour days) was used to estimate, indicating that the monetised models were better fitted. On the other hand, the models for the respondents in the Densu basin showed that using one-third of the wage rate to monetise the time (labour days) was not appropriate. The results of this study were similar to the findings of Ando et al. (2020), who found that people are willing to donate their time for stormwater management programmes that were worth only a third of the typical income.

To further assess the application of the conventional monetisation of time across all study areas, the shadow wage rate was estimated and presented in Table 4.9. The results were obtained by dividing the WTP (equations 1 – 3) estimates by the WTW (models 7 – 9) estimates for each of the WES. One-third of the minimum wage rate of GHS 4.96 was used to monetise labour days. The results showed that while the estimates for the pooled data and the Pra estimates were within the range of the conventional monetisation, results for the Densu basin showed a shadow wage rate that was greater than the wage rate. The shadow wage rate in Densu ranged from GHS 9.14 to GHS 44.65.

Gibson et al.'s 2016 research indicated a WTP to WTW ratio close to the full market wage rate for actual task contribution in choice experiment scenarios. Densu basin is largely urbanised compared to the Pra basin. The results further indicated that in rural areas where budgets are tight and incomes are low, households were willing to donate time equivalent to one-third of the wage rate. In contrast, in the urban areas where incomes were high, households valued their time close to or above the market wage rate.

Table 4.9: Shadow Wage Rate of Respondents in the Basins

	Model 1/7	Model 2/8	Model 3/9
Variables (WTP/WTW)	Pooled	Densu	Pra
Flood Protection (Medium)	6.21	11.83	2.41
Flood Protection (High)	5.64	9.14	2.85
Erosion Control (Medium)	7.64	24.35	1.64
Erosion Control (High)	7.69	19.22	2.43
Surface Water Quality (Medium)	7.20	36.42	1.62
Surface Water Quality (High)	6.76	23.64	1.84
Biodiversity of Fish (Medium)	6.64	25.29	1.76
Biodiversity of Fish (High)	8.18	44.65	1.66
Cultural Services (Medium)	5.52	9.98	1.86
Cultural Services (High)	7.19	17.16	2.47
Mean	6.52	20.60	1.96
Standard Error	0.43	3.64	0.16
Median	6.76	19.22	1.84
Standard Deviation	1.41	12.06	0.52
Kurtosis	2.79	0.12	-0.30
Skewness	-1.47	0.75	0.13
t-test of difference (Densu – Pra)	18.64***		5.1214

Source: *Author's estimation, 2023*

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Major Findings

The Densu and Pra basins in Ghana are crucial for providing ecosystem services that support socioeconomic and cultural growth. However, no study has examined the economic value of water-related ecosystem services in Ghana. This study, therefore, examined the value of water-related ecosystem services and the risk perceptions of households in the basins.

The general objective of this study was to determine the economic value of water-related ecosystem services associated with the Pra and Densu river basins in Ghana, as well as the perception of risks by households in both basins. The specific objectives were: explore the environmental awareness and views of respondents; examine the respondent's perception of the risks of human activities to the water environment; estimate the preference for and value of prioritised water-related ecosystem services (flood control, erosion control, surface water quality, fish abundance and species, and cultural services); and examine the change in preference and value as a result of the change in payment vehicle for ecosystem services.

Multistage sampling was used in selecting respondents from the two basins. In the first stage, Densu and Pra basins were chosen due to river basin deterioration and environmental and health impacts on rural and urban households. In the second stage, the Densu and Pra basins were stratified based on regional administrative boundaries, with the Densu basin spanning Greater Accra, Eastern, and Central regions, and the Pra basin spanning Ashanti, Central, Eastern, Western, and Western North regions. The third stage involved selecting districts from each region using simple random sampling, using Raosoft's online sample size calculator, resulting in 15 out of 18 districts and 36 out of 68 districts in Densu and Pra basins respectively.

In the fourth stage, two communities were randomly selected from each district. One rural and another urban community were selected in districts that were not 100 percent rural or urban. The respondents from each community were then selected randomly from each of the sampled communities. In targeting the 500-sample size, 550 respondents were targeted from each basin (with over sampling of 50 respondents) to ensure that the sample size is reached.

The revised NEP Scale, consisting of 15 items, was used to assess the environmental awareness and ecological worldview of participants. The odd-numbered items of the scale indicated NEP orientation (ecocentric variables), while even-numbered items reflected an anthropocentric Dominant Social Paradigm (DSP). The scale items underwent minor alterations to enhance comprehension and interpretation by the participants. A five-point Likert scale was used to rate items, and a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.70 indicated an acceptable level of reliability in the sample. The assessment of risk perception involved the use of a Likert-style rating (1-5) scheme, in which respondents were asked to rank the overall riskiness of 11 risk items identified as being prominent in having potential impacts on the ecosystem services (ES) in the Densu and Pra basins.

Values that people hold, such as altruistic, egoistic and biospheric values, were gathered from De Groot and Steg (2007). Data on affiliations to the common religious practices in Ghana, such as Christianity, Islam, Traditional religion, and other forms of religion, were taken. Social structural variables included in this study were education, gender, income level, and trust in government institutions, which were hypothesised to have a significant influence on environmental awareness and risk perceptions. To achieve objectives one and two, frequency distributions and means scores of responses were estimated. Objectives three and four were analysed using random parameter logit models.

The major findings of the study are as follows:

- The highest awareness levels in anthropocentric variables were found in NEP 10 (“The so-called “ecological crisis” facing humankind has been greatly exaggerated.”), followed by NEP 8 (“The stability of nature is strong enough to cope with the impacts of modern industrial nations.”) and NEP 4, with agreement levels of 59 percent, 30 percent, and 28 percent, respectively. In Densu and Pra, high awareness levels were found in NEP 10 (58% and 35% respectively).
- The study found that respondents agreed with the concept of nature's rights and the degradation caused by human activities, with NEP 7 (“Plants and animals have as much right as humans to exist.”) receiving the highest agreement (83.5%).
- However, NEP 1 (“We are approaching the limit of the number of people the Earth can support.”) and NEP 11 (“The Earth is like a spaceship with very limited room and resources.”) received low agreement ratings, suggesting that respondents did not appreciate the limits of nature.
- The results indicated that gender, income, age, religion, and marital status were the sociodemographic factors influencing the environmental views of respondents. Gender (being a male) was positively related to anthropocentric views, while income, age, and married persons were negatively related to anthropocentric views.
- The aggregated results showed that illegal mining, improper waste disposal, agrochemical use, tree cutting, bush burning, and construction near river banks were identified as the most prevalent issues, with a mean score of 4.1, 4.0, 3.8, 3.7, and 3.4, respectively. On the other hand, the pressure ranked below average was drawdown agriculture, with an average score of 2.8.
- The Densu basin faces significant pressures such as improper waste disposal, illegal mining, improper use of agrochemicals, and tree cutting, with mean scores of 4.4, 4.2, and 4.2 respectively. On the other hand, the Pra basin exhibited the highest riskiness

scores for illegal mining, bush burning, improper waste disposal, agrochemical use, and tree cutting, with mean rankings of 4.6, 3.9, 3.9, 3.8, and 3.8 respectively.

- Farming at the river banks and construction close to the river banks were perceived to pose a low risk to the water in the Densu basin, while drawdown agriculture and the influx of people to the river sites were the human activities ranked the least risky in the Pra basin.
- The willingness to pay results indicated that, overall, respondents were willing to pay between GHS 87.61 and GHS 104.63 household⁻¹ month⁻¹ for improvements in medium to high flood protection; between GHS 65.45 and GHS 98.06 household⁻¹ month⁻¹ for improvements in erosion control; between GHS 87.51 and GHS 151.61 household⁻¹ month⁻¹ for improvements in surface water quality; between GHS 57.49 and GHS 85.00 household⁻¹ month⁻¹ for improvements in fish biodiversity; and between GHS 35.32 and GHS 29.17 household⁻¹ month⁻¹ for medium to high improvements in the availability of cultural services relative to the low level of providing these services.
- The results of the willingness to pay showed that overall, respondents were willing to pay a minimum of GHS 29.17 (equivalent to US \$ 2.43) and a maximum of GHS 151.61 (equivalent to US \$ 12.63) per household per month in order to get improvements in water-related ecosystem services such as flood protection, erosion control, surface water quality, fish biodiversity and cultural services.
 - In the Densu basin, respondents were willing to pay a minimum of GHS 32.63 (equivalent to US \$ 2.72) and a maximum of GHS 195.22 (US \$ 16.27) for improvements in WES (medium level of improvement in cultural services and high improvement in surface water quality respectively). On the other hand, results from the Pra basin showed that households were willing to pay a minimum of GHS 22.06 (US \$ 1.84) and a maximum of GHS 127.84 (US \$

10.65) for medium improvements in cultural services and a high level of improvements in surface water quality respectively.

- The sociodemographic models for the Pooled, Densu basin, and Pra basin showed that sociodemographic characteristics were important predictors of willingness to pay for programmes aimed at improving flood protection, erosion control, surface water quality, fish biodiversity, and cultural services. The interaction between ASC (opt_out) and sociodemographic variables, such as education, income, and basin (Pra) dwelling, was significant and negative, reducing the likelihood of opting out of programmes that promote payments for WES conservation.
- The interaction between the Pro-NEP scores and the ASC was negative, indicating that respondents who were environmentally aware were less likely to opt out of any programme that seeks to conserve water-related ecosystem services.
- Using labour days, the results indicated a significant improvement in willingness to pay/work especially in the more rural Pra basin.
- The willingness to pay results indicate that, on average, respondents were willing to volunteer for 14–19 days household⁻¹ month⁻¹ to improve medium–high flood protection; 8–13 days household⁻¹ month⁻¹ to improve medium–high erosion control; 12–22 days household⁻¹ month⁻¹ to improve surface water quality; 9–10 days household⁻¹ month⁻¹ to improve medium–high fish biodiversity; and 6–4 days household⁻¹ month⁻¹ to improve medium–high availability of cultural services in comparison to the low level of providing these services.
- Compared to their fellow countrymen who volunteered between 30 and 32 days in the Pra basin for improvements in flood protection, respondents in the Densu basin were willing to devote between 10 and 14 days for the same levels of improvements. While respondents in the Pra basin were willing to volunteer 23 and 32 days for improvements

in erosion control, those in the Densu basin were also willing to volunteer 4 and 7 days for the same levels of improvements.

- The findings demonstrated that, in contrast to respondents in the Pra basin, who were willing to volunteer 44 and 69 days for improvements in surface water quality, respondents in the Densu basin were willing to volunteer 3 and 8 days. In order to increase fish biodiversity, respondents from the Densu basin expressed a willingness to volunteer for four or three days. On the other hand, respondents in the Pra basin expressed a willingness to donate 25 and 36 days in exchange for increased fish biodiversity.
- Lastly, in order to increase the opportunities for cultural services, respondents in the Densu were willing to volunteer three and two days, respectively. On the other hand, for the same degrees of improvements in cultural services, respondents in the Pra basin were willing to volunteer 19 and 9 days, respectively.
 - While the estimates for the pooled data and the Pra estimates fell within the traditional monetisation range, the Densu basin results revealed a shadow wage rate that exceeded the wage rate. In Densu, the shadow wage rate varied between GHS 9.14 and GHS 44.65.

5.2 Conclusions of the study

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

- The examination of the respondents' environmental awareness revealed that respondents believed that the earth has plenty of natural resources. As a result, most respondents in Pra and Densu had low levels of environmental awareness based on the NEP scales,

particularly when it came to understanding the limits of nature. Thus, the majority of respondents did not believe in the limits of nature in terms of its ability to meet growing demands.

- The respondents were highly appreciative of the risks posed by illegal mining, as it was perceived as the human activity with the highest risk rating, especially in Pra, where illegal mining is prominent.
- Programmes towards payments for water-related ecosystem services will yield positive results in the two basins as willingness to pay was high in both basins.
- In the Densu basin, respondents were willing to pay more in monetary value compared to the respondents in the Pra basin. On the other hand, respondents in the Pra were willing to work more in conserving the ecosystem services compared to their compatriots in the Densu basin.
- Improving education and income levels will lead to acceptance and participation in programmes aimed at conserving the water bodies, as educated households and respondents with high income levels were less likely to opt out of programmes aimed at paying for ecosystem service conservation.
- Finally, improving environmental awareness will lead to an improvement in willingness to pay for ecosystem services, as Pro-NEP respondents had a lower probability of opting out of programmes aimed at conserving ecosystem services.

5.3 Recommendations of the study

The study provided important policy recommendations that could contribute to improving the environmental awareness of the populace in the two basins.

They are as follows:

- The public and private education systems should invigorate households in the two basins by addressing environmental awareness levels. In particular, the National Commission for Civic Education (NCCE) should take charge of educating the general public on the limits of nature. The education on the fact that the earth is a spaceship and reaching the limits of the number of people it could contain should be emphasised among the respondents. Also, households should be educated on the need to ensure sustainability and patronise renewable resources by addressing the fact that the earth has limited natural resources, which should be explored sustainably.
- As farming and non-farming activities in the two basins are affected by illegal mining and other human activities, alternative livelihood projects aimed at providing alternative sources of income for communities that rely on mining should be instituted by government agencies such as the Microfinance and Small Loans Centre (MASLOC). These projects can include training programmes, microfinance initiatives, and support for small businesses.
- The Ministry of Food and Agriculture (MOFA) should also ensure that extension services are provided to farmers to ensure they adopt sustainable agricultural practices, such as the use of organic fertilisers as opposed to inorganic fertilisers. Farming along the river banks should also be discouraged.
- The local assembly, in collaboration with the traditional authorities, should take steps to impose levies and employ the labour efforts of households in conserving water-related ecosystem services in the two basins. Targeting the educated, the aged, and the high-income earners could improve participation in such programmes.

5.4 Suggestions for Further Studies

This study aimed to evaluate the water-related ecosystem services in the Densu and Pra basins, as well as the risk perceptions of households. Future studies could:

1. Expand the number of ecosystem services being valued. This current study examined the ecosystem services that were prioritised by the households in the two basins. It would be interesting to value the ecosystem services that were not prioritised to understand how preference and willingness to pay for such services differ.
2. The environmental awareness and risk perceptions of other stakeholders, such as students, experts and traditional leaders, could be examined in future studies to observe how they differ and determine if the education should be expanded to cover all stakeholders.

REFERENCES

- Abebe, S.T., Dagneu, A.B., Zeleke, V.G., Eshetu, G.Z., & Cirella, G.T. (2019). Willingness to Pay for Watershed Management. Resources.
- Abebe, T., Seyoum, A., & Feyssa, D. H. (2014). Benefits of wetland conservation interventions to local households in South-western Ethiopia: empirical evidence from attributes-based valuation. *Journal of Environmental Science and Water Resources*, 3(3), 60–68.
- Abramson, A., Becker, N., Garb, Y., & Lazarovitch, N. (2011). Willingness to pay, borrow, and work for rural water service improvements in developing countries. *Water Resources Research*, 47. doi:doi:10.1029/2010WR010147
- Acharya, R., Maraseni, T., & Cockfield, G. (2021). Estimating the willingness to pay for regulating and cultural ecosystem services from forested Siwalik landscapes: perspectives of disaggregated users. *Annals of Forest Science*, 78(51). doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/s13595-021-01046-3
- Adjei, F., Adjei, K.A., Obuobie, E., & Odai, S.N. (2019). Trends in land use/land cover changes in the Densu River basin and its impact on the Weija reservoirs and the Densu Delta (Sakumo I lagoon) in Ghana. *Journal of Geography and Regional Planning*, 12, 76-89.
- Aguilar, F.X., Obeng, E.A., Obeng, E.A., & Cai, Z. (2018). Water quality improvements elicit consistent willingness-to-pay for the enhancement of forested watershed ecosystem services. *Ecosystem services*, 30, 158-171.
- Ahlheim, M., Frör, O., Heinke, A., Duc, N.M., & Dinh, P.V. (2010). Labour as a utility measure in contingent valuation studies: how good is it really? (FZID Discussion Paper No. 13); Centre for Research on Innovation and Services, University of Hohenheim : Stuttgart, Germany.
- Akurugu, B.A., Obuobie, E., Yidana, S.M., Stisen, S., Seidenfaden, I.K., & Chegbeleh, L.P. (2022). Groundwater resources assessment in the Densu Basin: A review. *Journal of Hydrology: Regional Studies*.
- Alam, K., (2006). Valuing the environment in developing countries: Problems and potentials. *Asia Pac. J. Environ. Dev.* 13, 27 – 44.
- Allenby, G. (1990), 'Hypothesis Testing with Scanner Data: The Advantage of Bayesian Methods', *Journal of Marketing Research* 27, 379–389.
- Amare, D., Mekuria, W., T/wold, T., Belay, B., Teshome, A., Yitaferu, B., & Tegegn, B. (2016). Perception of local community and the willingness to pay to restore church forests: The Case of Dera District, Northwestern Ethiopia. *For. Trees Livelihoods*, 25, 173–186.
- Amoako, J., Karikari, A. Y., Ansa-Asare, O. D., & Adu-Ofori, E. (2010). Water quality characteristics of Densu river basin in south-east Ghana. *Water Science and Technology*, 61(6), 1467–1477. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2010.012>.

- Andersson, R., Wänseth, F., Cuellar, M., & Mitzlaff, U. V. (2006). Pangani Falls Redevelopment Project in Tanzania. SIDA evaluation 06/09. Stockholm: SIDA, Department for Infrastructure and Economic Cooperation: ISBN 91-586-8373-9 ISSN 1401— 0402.
- Ando, A.W., Cadavid, C.L., Netusil, N.R., & Parthum, B. (2020). Willingness-to-Volunteer and Stability of Preferences between Cities: Estimating the Benefits of Stormwater Management. *J. Environ. Econ. Manag.* 99, 102-274.
- Anornu, G. K., Kabo-bah, A. T., & Anim-Gyampo, M. (2012). Evaluation of groundwater vulnerability in the Densu river Basin of Ghana. *American Journal of Human Ecology*, 1(3), 79–86.
- Antwi-Agyakwa, K. T. (2014). Assessing the effect of land use land cover change on Weija catchment. Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology.
- Ardeshiri, A., Swait, J., Heagney, E. C., & Kovac, M. (2019). Willingness-to-pay for coastline protection in New South Wales: Beach preservation management and decision making. *Ocean and Coastal Management*, 178. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.05.007>
- Armah, F.A., Luginaah, I.N., Taabazuing, J., & Odoi, J.O. (2013). Artisanal Gold Mining and Surface Water Pollution in Ghana: Have the Foreign Invaders Come to Stay? *Environmental Justice*, 6, 94-102.
- Atav, E., Altunoğlu, B. D., & Sönmez, S. (2015). The determination of the environmental attitudes of secondary education students.
- Attua, E.M., Ayamga, J., & Pabi, O. (2014). Relating land use and land cover to surface water quality in the Densu River basin, Ghana. *International Journal of River Basin Management*, 12, 57 - 68.
- Ayertey, M. (2013). Water quality and its effects on ecosystem services of the Densu Delta Wetland, Accra, Ghana. Delft : Unesco-IHE.
- Bansah, K. J., Yalley, A. B., & Dumakor-Dupey, N. (2016). The hazardous nature of small scale underground mining in Ghana. *Journal of sustainable mining*, 15: 8 – 25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsm.2016.04.004>
- Bateman, I. J., Carson, R. T., Day, B., Hanemann, W. M., Hanley, N. D., Hett, T., Jones-Lee, M. W., Loomes, G., Mourato, S., Özdemiroglu, E., Pearce, D. W., Sugden, R., & Swanson, J. (2002). *Economic Valuation with Stated Preference Techniques*. Edward Elgar, Northampton, MA: pp. ISBN: 978 1 84064 919 2
- Baudron, F., & Giller, K. (2014). Agriculture and nature: trouble and strife? *Biological Conservation*, 170(C), 232–245.
- Baumol, W. J. (1972). John R. Hicks' contribution to economics. *The Swedish Journal of Economics*, 74(4), 503-527.

- Beaumais, O., Briand, A., Millok, K., & Nauges, C. (2014). What are Households Willing to Pay for Better Tap Water Quality? A Cross-Country Valuation Study. *SRPN: Water Pollution (Pollution)*.
- Bechtel, R. B., Corral-Verdugo, V., & Pinheiro, J. Q. (1999). Environmental belief systems: United States, Brazil, and Mexico. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 30(1), 122–128. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022022199030001008>.
- Bekkers, R. (2002). Giving Time and/or Money: Trade-off or Spill-over?
- Bell, A.R., Matthews, N., & Zhang, W. (2016). Opportunities for improved promotion of ecosystem services in agriculture under the Water-Energy-Food Nexus. *Journal of Environmental Studies and Sciences*, 6, 183-191.
- Bennett, J. & Blamey, R. (2001). *The Choice Modelling Approach to Environmental Valuation*. Edward Elgar Publishers, Cheltenham, UK. ISSN 1327-8231.
- Bertacchinia, E., & Sultanb, R. (2019). Valuing Urban Cultural Heritage in African Countries: A Contingent Valuation Study of Historic Buildings in Port Louis, Mauritius. *Journal of African Economies*, 1–22. doi:doi: 10.1093/jae/ejz010
- Bessah, E., Raji, A.O., Taiwo, O.J., Agodzo, S.K., Ololade, O.O., Strapasson, A., & Donkor, E. (2021). Assessment of surface waters and pollution impacts in Southern Ghana. *Hydrology Research*.
- Birol, E., & Das, S. (2010). Estimating the value of improved wastewater treatment: the case of river Ganga, India. *J Environ Manage* 91:2163–71.
- Birol, E., Karousakis, K., & Koundouri, P. (2006) Using choice experiment to account for preference heterogeneity in wetland attributes: the case of Cheimaditita wetland in Greece. *Ecol Econ* ;60:145–56.
- Birol, E., Karousakis, K., & Koundouri, P. (2006). Using economic valuation techniques to inform water resource management: a survey and critical appraisal of available techniques and an application. *Sci. Total Environ.* 365(1 – 3):105– 122.
- Birol, E., Koundouri, P., & Kountouris, Y. (2009). Using the Choice Experiment Method to Inform Flood Risk Reduction Policies in the Upper Silesia Region of Poland. *Munich Personal*. Retrieved August 10, 2022, from https://mpra.ub.unimuenchen.de/38426/1/MPRA_paper_38426.pdf
- Birol, E., Koundouri, P., & Kountouris, Y., (2010). Assessing the economic viability of alternative water resources in water-scarce regions: combining economic valuation, cost–benefit analysis and discounting. *Ecol Econ* ;69:839–47
- Blesia, J. U., Iek, M., Ratang, W., & Hutajulu, H. (2021). Developing an entrepreneurship model to increase students’ entre-preneurial skills: An action research project in a higher education institution in Indonesia. *Syst. Pract. Action Res.* 34, 53–70.

- Boateng, I. (2012). An application of GIS and coastal geomorphology for large scale assessment of coastal erosion and management: a case study of Ghana. *Journal of Coastal Conservation*, 16(3), 383–397. doi:10.1007/s11852-012-0209-0
- Bord, R. J. O., & Connor, R. E. (1992). Determinants of risk perceptions of a hazardous waste site. *Risk Analysis* 12, 411e416
- Boxall, P. C., & B. MacNab (2000), 'Exploring The Preferences of Wildlife Recreationists for Features of Boreal Forest Management: A Choice Experiment Approach', *Canadian Journal of Forest Research* 30, 1931–1941.
- Brauman, K. A., Daily, G. C., Duarte, T. K., & Mooney, H. A. (2007). The nature and value of ecosystem services: an overview highlighting hydrologic services. *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.* 32, 67–98. doi:10.1146/annurev.energy.32.031306.102758
- Brennan, L., Binney, W., Aleti, T., & Parker, L. (2014). Why validation is important: An example using the NEP Scales. *Mark. Soc. Res.* 22, 15–31.
- Brooks, E. G., Smith, K. G., Holland, R. A., Poppy, G. M., & Eigenbrod, F. (2014). Effects of methodology and stakeholder disaggregation on ecosystem service valuation. *Ecology and Society*, 19(3).
- Brouwer, R., Akter, S., Brander, L., & Haque, E. (2009) Economic Valuation of Flood Risk Exposure and Reduction in a Severely Flood Prone Developing Country. *Environ. Dev. Econ.* 14, 397–417.
- Brouwer, R., Akter, S., Brander, L., & Haque, E. (2009). Economic valuation of flood risk exposure and reduction in a severely flood prone developing country. *Environment and Development Economics*, 14, 397 - 417.
- Buttel, F. H., & Flinn, W. L. (1978). Social class and mass environmental beliefs: A Reconsideration. *Environment and Behaviour*, 10(3), 433–450. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013916578103008>
- Cantor, K.P. (1997). Drinking water and cancer. *Cancer Causes & Control*, 8, 292-308.
- Carpenter, S. R., Mooney, H. A., Agard, J., Capistrano, D., Defries, R. S., Díaz, S., Dietz, T., Duraiappah, A. K., Oteng-Yeboah, A., Pereira, H. M., Perrings, C., Reid, W. V, Sarukhan, J., Scholes, R. J., & Whyte, A. (2009). Science for managing ecosystem services: beyond the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 106, 1305–1312. doi:10.1073/pnas.0808772106
- Carson, R. T., & Groves, T. (2007). Incentive and informational properties of preference questions. *Environmental and resource economics*, 37, 181-210.
- Carson, R. T., & Mitchell, R. C. (1993). The issue of scope in contingent valuation studies. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 75(5), 1263-1267.
- Chaikaew, P., Hodges, A.W., & Grunwald, S. (2017). Estimating the value of ecosystem services in a mixed-use watershed: A choice experiment approach. *Ecosystem services*, 23, 228-237.

- Champ, P. A., Boyle, K., & Brow, T. C., (2017). *A Primer on Nonmarket Valuation*, second ed. Springer, Netherlands.
- Chen, H., Han, J., & Wright, D. (2020). An Investigation of Lecturers' Teaching through English Medium of Instruction—A Case of Higher Education in China. *Sustainability* 12, 40-46.
- Chepkwony, G. C., Ipara, H., & Odwori, P. O. (2020). Total Economic Value of Kingwal Wetland to the Surrounding Community, Nandi County, Kenya. *Africa Environmental Review Journal*, 3(2), 70-76.
- Chiluwe, Q., & Nkhata, B. (2014). Analysis of water governance in Malawi: Towards a favourable enabling environment. *J. Water Sanit. Hyg. Dev.* 4, 313–323.
- CICES, (2018). *Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES; V5.1, 01/01/2018)*.
- Coates, D., Pert, P., Barron, J., Muthuri, C., Nguyen-Khoa, S., Boelee, E., & Jarvis, D. (2013). Water-related ecosystem services and food security. *Manag Water Agroecosystems Food Security*, 10, 29.
- Collins, M., Knutti, R., Arblaster, J., Dufresne, J. L., Fichet, T., Friedlingstein, P., Gao, X., Gutowski, W. J., Johns, T., Krinner, G., Shongwe, M., Tebaldi, C., Weaver, A. J., & Wehner, M., (2013). Long-term climate change: projections, commitments and irreversibility, in: Stocker, & climate change. *The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge (United Kingdom) and New York (USA).
- Corraliza, J. A., Collado, S., & Bethelmy, L. (2013). Spanish version of the new ecological paradigm scale for children. *The Spanish Journal of Psychology*, 16, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1017/sjp.2013.46>.
- Costanza, R., D'Arge, R., de Groot, R.S., Farber, S. C., Grasso, M., Hannon, B., Limburg, K., Naeem, S., O'Neill, R. V., Paruelo, J., Raskin, R. G., Sutton, P., & van den Belt, M. (2017). The value of the world's ecosystem services and natural capital. *Nature* 387, 253–260.
- Crouch, E.A., Wilson, R., & Zeise, L. (1983). The risks of drinking water. *Water Resources Research*, 19, 1359-1375.
- Cusens, J., Barraclough, A.D., & Måren, I.E. (2023). Integration matters: Combining socio-cultural and biophysical methods for mapping ecosystem service bundles. *Ambio*, 52, 1004 - 1021.
- Czajkowski, M., Zagórska, K., Letki, N., Tryjanowski, P., & Wąs, A. (2019). Drivers of farmers' willingness to adopt extensive farming practices in a globally important bird area. *Land Use Policy*, 104223.
- Daly, A.J., Baetens, J.M., & De Baets, B. (2018). *Ecological Diversity: Measuring the Unmeasurable. Mathematics*.
- Dannenber, A. A., & Estola, M. (2018). Willingness to pay in the theory of a consumer. *Hyperion International Journal of Econophysics & New Economy*, 11(1), 49-70.

- Darko, H. F., Karikari, A. Y., Duah, A. A., Akurugu, B. A., Mante, V., & Teye, F. O. (2023) Effect of small-scale illegal mining on surface water and sediment quality in Ghana, *International Journal of River Basin Management*, 21:3, 375-386, DOI: [10.1080/15715124.2021.2002345](https://doi.org/10.1080/15715124.2021.2002345)
- Darko, H.F., Karikari, A.Y., Duah, A.A., Akurugu, B.A., Mante, V., & Teye, F.O. (2021). Effect of small-scale illegal mining on surface water and sediment quality in Ghana. *International Journal of River Basin Management*, 21, 375 - 386.
- Darvill, R., & Lindo, Z. (2016). The inclusion of stakeholders and cultural ecosystem services in land management trade-off decisions using an ecosystem services approach. *Landscape Ecology*, 31: 533–545. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-015-0260-y>
- Davivongs, V., Yokohari, M., & Hara, Y. (2012) Neglected canals: Deterioration of indigenous irrigation system by urbanisation in the West Peri-Urban area of Bangkok. *Water*, 4: 12–27.
- Day, B., Bateman I. J., Carson, R. T., Dupont, D., Louviere, J. J., Morimoto, S. et al . (2012) Ordering effects and choice set awareness in repeat-response stated preference studies. *J Environ Econ Manag*. 63:73–91.
- de Bekker-Grob, E. W., Ryan, M., & Gerard, K. (2012). Discrete choice experiments in health economics: a review of the literature. *Health economics*, 21(2), 145-172.
- De França Doria, M. (2010). Factors influencing public perception of drinking water quality. *Water Policy*. 12, 1–19.
- De Groot, J. I., & Steg, L. (2007). Value orientations and environmental beliefs in five countries: Validity of an instrument to measure egoistic, altruistic and biospheric value orientations. *Journal of cross-cultural psychology*, 38(3), 318-332.
- De Groot, R., Fisher, B., Christie, M., Aronson, J., Braat, L., Gowdy, J., & Neuvill, A. (2010). Integrating the ecological and economic dimensions in biodiversity and ecosystem service valuation. In *The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity (TEEB)*. London: Earth scan.
- Denis, H. D., & Pereira, L. N. (2014). Measuring the level of endorsement of the New Environmental Paradigm: A transnational study. *Dos Algarves: A Multidisciplinary e-Journal*, 23, 1–26.
- Diamantopoulos, A., Schlegelmilch, B. B., Sinkovics, R. R., & Bohlen, G. M. (2003). Can socio-demographics still play a role in profiling green consumers? A review of the evidence and an empirical investigation. *Journal of Business Research*, 56(6), 465-480. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963\(01\)00241-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963(01)00241-7)
- Dietz, T., Fitzgerald, A., & Shwom, R. (2005). Environmental values. *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.*, 30, 335-372.
- Dizon, J. P. M., Enoch-Stevens, T., & Huerta, A. H. (2022). Carcerality and Education: Toward a Relational Theory of Risk in Educational Institutions. *Am. Behav. Sci*. 66, 1319–1341.
- Dlamini, N. M. (2015). Households' Water Use Demand and Willingness to Pay for Improved Water Services: A Case Study of Semi-Urban Areas in the Lubombo and Lowveld Regions of Swaziland: pp.132

- Dobbie, M. F., & Brown, R. R. (2014). A framework for understanding risk perception, explored from the perspective of the water practitioner. *Risk Anal.* 34, 294–308.
- Drupp, M.A., Hänsel, M.C., Fenichel, E.P., Freeman, M., Gollier, C., Groom, B., Heal, G.M., Howard, P.H., Millner, A., Moore, F.C., Nesje, F., Quaas, M.F., Smulders, S., Sterner, T., Traeger, C., & Venmans, F. (2024). Accounting for the increasing benefits from scarce ecosystems. *Science*, 383, 1062 - 1064.
- Duijndam, S., Pieter van B., Hanna F., Anne M., & Mark K. (2020). Valuing a Caribbean coastal lagoon using the choice experiment method: The case of the Simpson Bay Lagoon, Saint Martin. *Journal for Nature Conservation*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnc.2020.125845>.
- Duncan, A.E., Oti, J.O., & Potakey, M.E. (2019). Impacts of Human Activities on the Quality of River Water: A Case Study of River Densu in Nsawam Adoagyiri of the Akwapim South District, Eastern Region of Ghana. OALib.
- Dunlap, R. (2008). The new environmental paradigm scale: From marginality to worldwide use. *J. Environ. Educ.* 40, 3–18.
- Dunlap, R. E. (2008). The new environmental paradigm scale: From marginality to worldwide use. *The Journal of Environmental Education*, 40(1), 3–18. <https://doi.org/10.3200/JOEE.40.1.3-18>.
- Dunlap, R. E., & Van Liere, K. D. (1978). The “new environmental paradigm”: a proposed measuring instrument and preliminary results. *Journal of Environmental Education* 9, 10e19.
- Dunlap, R. E., & Van Liere, K. D. (1978). The new environmental paradigm[^]. *Journal of Environmental Education*, 9, 10–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00958964.1978.10801875>.
- Dunlap, R. E., Van Liere, K. D., Mertig, A. G., & Jones, R. E. (2000). New trends in measuring environmental attitudes: Measuring endorsement of the new ecological paradigm: A revised NEP scale. *Journal of Social Issues*, 56(3), 425–442. <https://doi.org/10.1111/0022-4537.00176>.
- Dunlap, R., Van Liere, K., Mertig, A., & Jones, R. E. (2000). Measuring endorsement of the new ecological Paradigm: a revised NEP scale. *J. Soc. Issues* 56, 425–442. <https://doi.org/10.1111/0022-4537.00176>.
- Echessah, P. N., Swallow, B. M., Kamara, D. W., & Curry, J. J. (1997). Willingness to Contribute Labor and Money to Tsetse Control: Application of Contingent Valuation in Busia District, Kenya. *World Dev.* 25, 239–253.
- English, E., von Haefen, R. H., Herriges, J., Leggett, C., Lupi, F., McConnell, K., Welsh, M., Domanski, A., & Meade, N. (2018). Estimating the value of lost recreation days from the Deepwater Horizon oil spill. *J. Environ. Econ. Manag.* 91, 26e45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeem.2018.06.010>.
- Enming, R., Yi, X., Zhiyun, O., & Hua, Z. (2014). Changes in Ecosystem Service of Soil Conservation Between 2000 and 2010 and Its Driving Factors in Southwestern China. *Chinese Geographical Science*. doi:doi: 10.1007/s11769-015-0759-9

- Falk, A., & Fischbacher, U. (2006). A theory of reciprocity. *Games and economic behavior*, 54(2), 293-315.
- FAO, & UNEP. (2020). *The State of the Worlds' Forests: Forests Biodiversity and People*. Rome: Food and agriculture organization and United Nations Environmental programme. doi:10.4060/ca8642en
- Fezzi, C., Bateman, I. J., & Ferrini, S. (2014). Using revealed preferences to estimate the value of travel time to recreation sites. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 67(1), 58-70.
- Finucane M. L, Slovic P, Mertz C. K et al . (2000). Gender, race, and perceived risk: The 'white male' effect. *Health Risk Soc.* 2:159–72 doi: 10.1080/713670162.
- Fischhoff, B. (1985). Managing risk perceptions. *Issues in Science and Technology*, II(1), 83e96.
- Fischhoff, B., Slovic, P., Lichtenstein, S., Read, S., & Combs, B. (1978). How safe is safe enough? A psychometric study of attitudes toward technological risks and benefits. *Policy Sciences*, 9, 127e152
- Flint C. G., Dai, X., Jackson-Smith, D. et al . (2017). Social and geographic contexts of water concerns in Utah. *Soc Nat Res* 30:885–902 doi: 10.1080/08941920.2016.1264653.
- Flynn J, Slovic P, and Mertz C. K. (1994). Gender, race, and perception of environmental health risks. *Risk Anal* 14:1101–8. doi: 10.1111/j.1539-6924.1994.tb00082
- Flynn, J., Burns, W., Mertz, C. K., Slovic, P., (1992). Trust as a determinant of opposition to a high-level radioactive waste repository: analysis of a structural model. *Risk Analysis* 12, 417e429.
- Fontdecaba, S., Grima, P., Marco, L., Rodero, L., Sánchez-Espigares, J. A, Solé, I. et al . (2012) Methodology to model water demand based on the identification of homogenous client segments. Application to the city of Barcelona. *Water Resour Manag.* 26:499–516
- Freeman, A. M. (2003). *The Measurement of Environmental and Resource Values-Theory and Methods*. 2nd Ed. Washington DC: Resources for the Future: 22 pp.
- Freire, O., Quevedo-Silva, F., & Frederico, E. (2013). Measuring the consumer environmental concern: A comparative study between the NEP and ECCB scales. *Organicom*, 10(18), 244–263. <https://doi.org/10.11606/issn.2238-2593.organicom.2013.139182>
- Fuks, M., & Chatterjee, L.R. (2008). Estimating the Willingness to Pay for a Flood Control Project in Brazil Using the Contingent Valuation Method. *Journal of Urban Planning and Development-asce*, 134, 42-52.
- Gachoki, C. M. (2010). Application of choice experiment in non-use valuation of Lake Olbolosat in Kenya (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi, Kenya).
- Ghana Statistical Service, (GSS). (2021). *Ghana 2021 Population and Housing Census General Report Volume 3A*. Ghana Statistical Service.

- Gibson, J. M., Rigby, D., Polya, D. A., & Russell, N. (2016). Discrete Choice Experiments in Developing Countries: Willingness to Pay Versus Willingness to Work. *Environ Resource Economics*, 65, 697–721. doi: DOI 10.1007/s10640-015-9919-8.
- Gibson, J.W., Rigby, D., Polya, D.A., & Russell, N.P. (2016). Discrete Choice Experiments in Developing Countries: Willingness to Pay Versus Willingness to Work. *Environmental and Resource Economics*, 65, 697-721.
- Gorbunov, V. (2021). The Holistic Theory of the Consumer Market Demand. In E. Popov, V. Barkhatov, V. D. Pham, & D. Pletnev (Eds.), *Competitiveness and the Development of Socio-Economic Systems*, vol 105. *European Proceedings of Social and Behavioural Sciences* (pp. 476-485). European Publisher. <https://doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2021.04.52>
- Gosain, A. K.; Sandhya, R.; & Debajit, B. (2006). Climate change impact assessment on the hydrology of Indian river basins. *Current Science*, 90, 346–353.
- Gregg, P., Grout, P.A., Ratcliffe, A., Smith, S., & Windmeijer, F. (2008). The Centre for Market and Public Organisation How Important Is Pro-social Behaviour in the Delivery of Public Services? How Important Is Pro-social Behaviour in the Delivery of Public Services? Acknowledgements.
- Greiner, R., Bliemer, M., & Ballweg, J. (2014). Design considerations of a choice experiment to estimate likely participation by north Australian pastoralists in contractual biodiversity conservation. *Journal of choice modelling*, 10, 34-45.
- Grêt-Regamey, A., & Weibel, B. (2020). Global assessment of mountain ecosystem services using earth observation data. *Ecosystem services*, 46, 101213.
- Grizzetti, B., Lanza, D., Lique, C., Reynaud, A., & Cardoso, A. (2016). Assessing water ecosystem services for water resource management. *Environmental Science and Policy*, 61, 194–203.
- Grůňová, M., Sané, M., Cincera, J., Kroufek, R., & Hejčmanová, P. (2018). Reliability of the new environmental paradigm for analysing the environmental attitudes of Senegalese pupils in the context of conservation education projects. *Environ. Educ. Res.*
- Grundig, B. (2006). Why is the share of women willing to work in East Germany larger than in West Germany? A logit model of extensive labour supply decision.
- Grůňová, M., Sané, M., Cincera, J., Kroufek, R., & Hejčmanová, P. (2019). Reliability of the new environmental paradigm for analysing the environmental attitudes of Senegalese pupils in the context of conservation education projects. *Environmental Education Research*, 25(2), 211-221.
- Guagnano, G. A. (2001). Altruism and market-like behaviour: An analysis of willingness to pay for recycled paper products. *Population and Environment*, Vol. 22 (7): pp.425-438.
- Guimaraes, J.R.D., Betancourt, O., Miranda, M.R., Barriga, R., Cueva, E., & Betancourt, S. (2011). Long-range effect of cyanide on mercury methylation in a gold mining area in southern Ecuador. *Sci. Total Environ*, 409, 5026–5033.

- Gupta, S., & P. K. Chintagunta (1994), 'On Using Demographic Variables to Determine Segment Membership in Logit Mixture Models', *Journal of Marketing Research* 31, 128–136.
- Haab, T. C., & McConnell, K. E. (2002). *Valuing Environmental and Natural Resources: The Econometrics of Non-market Valuation*. Cheltenham, UK, and Northampton, MA, USA: Edward Elgar: pp.517.
- Haines-Young, R., & Potschin, M. (2017). *Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) V5.1 and Guidance on the Application of the Revised Structure*. Barton, UK: Fabis Consulting Ltd.
- Halkos, G., & Matsiori, S. (2017). Environmental attitude, motivations and values for marine biodiversity protection. *Journal of Behavioural and Experimental Economics*, 69, 61–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socec.2017.05.009>
- Han, S. Y., Kwak, S. J., & Yoo, S. H. (2008). Valuing environmental impacts of large dam construction in Korea: An application of choice experiments. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 28(4-5), 256-266.
- Hanley, N., Mourato, S., & Wright, R. E. (2001). Choice modelling approaches: a superior alternative for environmental valuation? *J. Econ. Surv.* 15 (3), 435–462.
- Hanley, N., Shogren, J. & White, B. (2007). *Environmental Economics in Theory and Practice*. Mac Millan Limited, India. pp464.
- Hansen, J., & Hammann, M. (2017). Risk in Science Instruction. *Sci. Educ.* 26, 749–775.
- Harraway, J., Broughton-Ansin, F., Deaker, L., Jowett, T., & Shephard, K. (2012). Exploring the use of the revised new ecological paradigm scale (NEP) to monitor the development of students' ecological worldviews. *The Journal of Environmental Education*, 43(3), 177–191. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00958964.2011.634450>
- Hawcroft, L. J., & Milfont, T. L. (2010). The use (and abuse) of the new environmental paradigm scale over the last 30 years: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 30(2), 143–158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2009.10.003>.
- Helvoort-Postulart, D., Dirksen, C.D., Kessels, A., Engelshoven, J.M., & Myriam Hunink, M.G. (2009). A comparison between willingness to pay and willingness to give up time. *The European Journal of Health Economics*, 10, 81-91.
- Hensher D, Shore N, & Train K. (2006) Water supply security and willingness to pay to avoid drought restrictions. *Econ Rec* 82, 56–66
- Hensher, D., Shore, N., & Train, K. (2005). Households' willingness to pay for water service attributes. *Environmental Recourse Econ.* 32,509–31.
- Hilson, G., & Murck, B. (2000). Sustainable development in the mining industry: clarifying the corporate perspective. *Resources Policy*, 26, 227–238.

- Hite, D., Hudson, D.M., & Intarapapong, W. (2002). Willingness to Pay for Water Quality Improvements: The Case of Precision Application Technology. *Journal of Agricultural and Resource Economics*, 27(3), 433-449.
- Holmes, T. P., Adamowicz, W. L., & Carlsson, F. (2017). Choice experiments. A primer on nonmarket valuation, 133-186.
- Hope, R. A. (2006). Evaluating water policy scenarios against the priorities of the rural poor. *World Development Journal*, Vol. 34(1): pp.167-179.
- Hosseinnezhad, F. (2017). A Study of the new environmental paradigm scale in the context of Iran. *European Journal of Sustainable Development Research*, 1(2), 14. <https://doi.org/10.20897/ejosdr.201714>
- Hoyos, D. (2010). The state of the art of environmental valuation with discrete choice experiments. *Ecological economics*, 69(8), 1595-1603.
- Hung, L. T., Loomis, J. B., & Thinh, V. T. (2007). Comparing money and labour payment in contingent valuation: the case of forest fire prevention in Vietnamese context. *Journal of International Development*, 19(2), 173-185.
- Hurlimann, A. C., & McKay, J. M. (2006). What attributes of recycled water make it fit for residential purposes? The Mawson Lakes experience. *Desalination*. 187, 167–77.
- Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES). (2012). UNEP/IPBES. MI/2/9: report of the second session of the plenary meeting to determine modalities and institutional arrangements for an intergovernmental science-policy platform on biodiversity and ecosystem services. Panama: IPBES-2.
- Janmaimool, P., & Watanabe, T. (2014). Evaluating determinants of environmental risk perception for risk management in contaminated sites. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*. 11, 6291–6313.
- Jonah, F. E., Adams, O., Aheto, D. W., Jonah, R. E., & Mensah, E. A. (2017). Coastal zone management challenges in Ghana: issues associated with coastal sediment mining. *Journal of Coastal Conservation*, 21(3), 343–353. doi:10.1007/s11852-017-0511-y
- Jonah, F. E., Adjei-Boateng, D., Agbo, N. W., Mensah, E. A., & Edziyie, R. E. (2015). Assessment of sand and stone mining along the coastline of Cape Coast, Ghana. *Annals of GIS*, 21(3), 223–231. doi:10.1080/19475683.2015.1007894
- Kadekodi, G. K. (2001). Valuation of Natural Resources: What have we learned from Indian experience? *Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, Vol. 56(3): pp.286-312.
- Karabulut, A., Egoh, B. N., Lanzanova, D., Grizzetti, B., Bidoglio, G., Pagliero, L., Bouraoui, F., Aloe, A., Reynaud, A., Maes, J., Vandecasteele, I., & Mubareka, S. (2016). Mapping water provisioning services to support the ecosystem-water-food-energy nexus in the Danube river basin. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 17, 278–292. doi:10.1016/j.ecoser.2015.08.002.
- Karikari, A. Y. & Ansa-Asare, O. D. (2006). Physico-chemical and microbial water quality assessment of Densu river of Ghana. *West Afr. J. Appl. Ecol.* 12, 87–100

- Kassahun, H., Jacobsen, J., & Nicholson, C. (2020). Revisiting Money and Labor for Valuing Environmental Goods and Services in Developing Countries. *Ecological Economics*, 177, 106771.
- Kataria M, Bateman I, Christensen T, Dubgaard A, Hasler B, Hime S et al . (2012). Scenario realism and welfare estimates in choice experiments — A non-market valuation study on the European Water Framework Directive. *J Environ Manage.* 94, 25–33.
- Kataria M. (2009). Willingness to pay for environmental improvements in hydropower regulated rivers. *Energy Econ.* 31,69–76.
- Kazapoe, R.W., Arhin, E., & Amuah, E.E. (2021). Known and anticipated medical geology issues in Ghana.
- Keeler, B. L., Polasky, S., Brauman, K. A., Johnson, K. A., Finlay, J. C., O’Neill, A., Kovacs, K., & Dalzell, B. (2012). Linking water quality and wellbeing for improved assessment and valuation of ecosystem services. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 109, 18619–18624. doi:10.1073/pnas.1215991109.
- Kellstedt, P. M., Zahran, S., & Vedlitz, A. (2008). Personal efficacy, the information environment, and attitudes toward global warming and climate change in the United States. *Risk Analysis* 28, 113e126.
- Kervankıran, İ., Dziwornu, M.G., & Temurçin, K. (2016). Illegal Mining as Threat to Sustainable Development in Ghana: A Political Ecology Approach. *ZfWT*, 3(8), 173 – 191.
- Kløjgaard, M. E., Bech, M., & Søgaaard, R. (2012). Designing a stated choice experiment: the value of a qualitative process. *Journal of Choice Modelling*, 5(2), 1-18.
- Krinsky, I., & Robb, A. L. (1986). On approximating the statistical properties of elasticities. *The review of economics and statistics*, 715-719.
- La Trobe, H. L., & Acott, T. G. (2000). A modified NEP/DSP environmental attitudes scale. *The Journal of Environmental Education*, 32(1), 12–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00958960009598667>
- Lankia, T., Neuvonen, M., Pouta, E., & Sievänen, T. (2014). Willingness to Contribute to the Management of Recreational Quality on Private Lands in Finland. *J. For. Econ.* 20, 141–160.
- Larkin, C., Lucey, B. M., & Mulholland, M. (2013). Risk tolerance and demographic characteristics: Preliminary Irish evidence. *J. Financ. Serv. Rev.* 22, 77–91.
- Larson K. L, Ibes D, & White D. (2010). Gendered perspectives on water scarcity and resource governance: A tripartite conceptual approach. *Environ Behav* 43, 415-438 doi:10.1177/0013916510365253.
- Larson, S., Stoeckl, N., Neil, B., & Welters, R. (2013) Using resident perceptions of values associated with the Australian tropical rivers to identify policy and management priorities. *Ecol. Econ.* 94, 9–18.

- Lautenbach, S., Maes, J., Kattwinkel, M., Seppelt, R., Strauch, M., Scholz, M., Schulz-Zunkel, C., Volk, M., Weinert, J., & Dormann, C. F. (2012). Mapping water quality-related ecosystem services: concepts and applications for nitrogen retention and pesticide risk reduction. *Int. J. Biodivers. Sci. Ecosyst. Serv. Manag.* iFirst, 1–15. doi:10.1080/21513732.2011.631940
- Lavrakas, P.J., *Encyclopedia of survey research methods*. SAGE Publications, Thousand Oaks, 2008
- Lazo, J. K., Kinnell, J. C., & Fisher, A. (2000). Expert and layperson perceptions of ecosystem risk. *Risk Analysis*, 20(2), 179e193.
- Le Lay, Y. F., Piégay, H., & Rivière-Honegger, A. (2013) Perception of braided river landscapes: Implications for public participation and sustainable management. *J. Environ. Manag.* 2013, 119, 1–12.
- Leemans, R., & Kleidon, A. (2002). Regional and global assessment of the dimensions of desertification, in: Reynolds, J.F., Stafford Smith, D.M. (Eds.), *Global Desertification: Do Humans Cause Deserts?* Dahlem University Press, Brighton (United Kingdom), pp. 215– 231
- Leiserowitz, A. (2006). Climate change risk perception and policy preferences: The role of affect, imagery, and values. *Climatic Change* 77, 45e72.
- Lepesteur, M., Wegner, A., Moore, S. A., & McComb, A. (2008). Importance of public information and perception for managing recreational activities in the peel-harvey estuary, western Australia. *J. Environ. Manag.* 87, 389–395.
- Leynes, P. A., Marsh, R. L., Hicks, J. L., Allen, J. D., & Mayhorn, C. B. (2003). Investigating the encoding and retrieval of intentions with event-related potentials. *Consciousness and Cognition*, 12(1), 1-18.
- Li, Y., Zhang, Z., & Shi, M. (2019). Restrictive Effects of Water Scarcity on Urban Economic Development in the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei City Region. *Sustainability* 11, 2452.
- Lienhoop, N., & Völker, M. (2016). Preference Refinement in Deliberative Choice Experiments for Ecosystem Service Valuation. *Land Economics*, 92, 555 - 577.
- Liu, J., Liu, R., Zhang, Z., Cai, Y., & Zhang, L. (2019). A Bayesian Network-based risk dynamic simulation model for accidental water pollution discharge of mine tailings ponds at watershed-scale. *Journal of environmental management*, 246, 821-831.
- Liu, W., & Aaker, J.L. (2008). The Happiness of Giving: The Time-Ask Effect. *Behavioural Marketing*.
- Lloyd-Smith, P., & Adamowicz, W. (2018). Can stated measures of willingness-to-accept be valid? Evidence from laboratory experiments. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 91, 133-149.
- López-Bonilla, L. M. & López-Bonilla, J. M. (2016). From the new environmental paradigm to the brief ecological paradigm: A revised scale in golf tourism. *Anatolia* 27, 227–236.
- Luo, Y., & Deng, J. (2008). The new environmental paradigm and nature-based tourism motivation. *J. Travel Res.* 46, 392–402.

- Lusardi, J., Sunderland, T.J., Crowe, A., Jackson, B., & Jones, G. (2020). Can process-based modelling and economic valuation of ecosystem services inform land management policy at a catchment scale? *Land Use Policy*, 96, 104636.
- Ma, S., Swinton, S. M., Lupi, F. & Jolejole-Foreman, C. (2012). Farmers' willingness to participate in payment-for-environmental-services programmes. *Journal of Agricultural Economics* 63(3): 604 – 626.
- Mamboleo, M., & Adem, A. (2023). Factors influencing willingness to pay for wetland ecosystems conservation: a contingent valuation study of lake Victoria Ecosystem in Kenya. *Knowl. Manag. Aquat. Ecosyst.*, 424(11). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1051/kmae/2023007>
- Manoli, C. C., Johnson, B., & Dunlap, R. E. (2007). Assessing children's environmental worldviews: Modifying and validating the new ecological paradigm scale for use with children. *Journal of Environmental Education*, 38, 3–13. <https://doi.org/10.3200/JOEE.38.4.3-13>.
- Markandya, A., Harou, P., Bellù, L. G. & Cistulli, V. (2002). *Environmental Economics for Sustainable Growth. A Handbook for Practitioners*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar: pp.47
- Martinez-Alier, J. (2002). *The Environmentalism of the Poor: A Study of Ecological Conflicts and Valuation*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Martínez-Valderrama, J., Olcina, J., Delacámara, G., Guirado, E., & Maestre, F.T. (2023). Complex Policy Mixes are Needed to Cope with Agricultural Water Demands Under Climate Change. *Water Resources Management*, 37, 2805-2834.
- Martin-Ortega, J., Ferrier, R. C., & Gordon, I. J. (2015). Water ecosystem services: A global perspective. *Global Water Forum*. Retrieved from <https://globalwaterforum.org/2015/07/28/water-ecosystem-services-a-global-perspective/>
- Mas-Colell, A., Whinston, M. D., & Green, J. R. (1995). *Microeconomic theory* (Vol. 1). New York: Oxford university press.
- Matos, C., Teixeira, C. A., Bento, R., Varajão J., & Bentes I. (2014). An exploratory study on the influence of socio-demographic characteristics on water end uses inside buildings. *Sci Total Environ* 466, 467–74
- Matthews, Y., Scarpa, R., & Marsh, D. (2017). Stability of willingness-to-pay for coastal management: A choice experiment across three time periods. *Ecological Economics*, 138, 64-73.
- Matthews, Y., Scarpa, R., & Marsh, D. (2017). Using virtual environments to improve the realism of choice experiments: A case study about coastal erosion management. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 81, 93-208. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeem.2016.08.001>.
- McDaniels, T. L., Axelrod, L. J., & Slovic, P. (1995). Characterising perception of ecological risk. *Risk Analysis*, 15(5), 575e588.
- McDaniels, T. L., Axelrod, L. J., Cavanagh, N. S., & Slovic, P. (1997). Perception of ecological risk to water environments. *Risk Analysis*, 17(3), 341e352.

- Menbere, I. P., & Menbere, T. P. (2018). Wetland ecosystems in Ethiopia and their implications in ecotourism and biodiversity conservation. *Journal of Ecology and Natural Environment*, 10(6), 80–96.
- Menegaki, A. N., Hanley, N., & Tsagarakis, K. P. (2007). The social acceptability and valuation of recycled water in Crete: a study of consumers' and farmers' attitudes. *Ecol Econ* 62, 7–18.
- Mensah, A.K., Mahiri, I.O., Owusu, O., Mireku, O.D., Wireko, I., & Kissi, E.A. (2015). *Environmental Impacts of Mining: A Study of Mining Communities in Ghana*.
- Metcalf, P. J., Baker, W., Andrews, K., Atkinson, G., Bateman, I. J., Butler, S. et al. (2012). An assessment of the nonmarket benefits of the water framework directive for households in England and Wales. *Water Resour Res* 48, W03526.
- Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, (MEA). (2005). *Ecosystems and human wellbeing: synthesis*. Washington, DC: Island.
- Molles Jr., M. C. (2008). *Ecology: concepts & applications*, 4th ed. McGraw-Hill, New York (USA).
- Morris, R.D. (1995). Drinking water and cancer. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 103, 225 - 231.
- Moyano-Diaz, E., & Palomo-Vélez, G. (2014). Psychometric properties of the new ecological paradigm scale (NEP-R) in Chilean population]. *Psico*, 45(3), 415– 423. <https://doi.org/10.15448/1980-8623.2014.3.17276>.
- Navrud, S., & Vondolia, G. (2020). Farmers' Preferences for Reductions in Flood Risk Under Monetary and Non-Monetary Payment Modes. *Water Resource Economics*, 30, 100151.
- Navrud, S., Lindhjem, H., & Magnussen, K. (2017). Valuing marine ecosystem services loss from oil spills for use in cost-benefit analysis of preventive measures. *Handbook on the economics and management of sustainable oceans*, 124-137.
- Navrud, S., Tuan, T.H., & Tinh, B.D. (2012). Estimating the welfare loss to households from natural disasters in developing countries: a contingent valuation study of flooding in Vietnam. *Global Health Action*, 5.
- Ndetewio, P. I., Mwakaje, A. G., Mujwahuzi, M. & Ngana, J. (2013). Factors influencing willingness to pay for watershed services in lower Moshi, Pangani Basin, Tanzania. *International Journal of Agriculture and Environmental* 2: 57 – 75.
- Nicholson, W., & Snyder, C. (2008). *Microeconomic Theory. Basic Principles and Extensions* 10th Ed. Mason, OH, USA: Thomson South-Western: pp.122
- Noblet, C. L., Anderson, M., & Teisl, M. F. (2013). An empirical test of anchoring the NEP scale in environmental ethics. *Environ. Educ. Res.* 19, 540–551. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2012.704899>.
- Nti, E.K., Kranjac-Berisavljevic, G., Doke, D.A., Wongnaa, C.A., Attafuah, E.E., & Gyan, M.A. (2023). The impact of artisanal gold mining on the sustainability of Ghana's river basins: The case of the Pra basin. *Environmental and Sustainability Indicators*.

- O'Garra, T. (2009). Bequest Values for Marine Resources: How Important for Indigenous Communities in Less-Developed Economies? *Environ. Resour. Econ.* 44, 179–202.
- Obeng, E. A., & Aguilar, F. X. (2018). Value orientation and payment for ecosystem services: Perceived detrimental consequences lead to willingness-to-pay for ecosystem services. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 458-471. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.10.059>
- Oduor, F. O., Raburu, P. O., & Mwakubo, S. (2016). Estimation of willingness to pay for conservation of Nyando wetlands, Kenya: A contingent valuation approach. *Adv. Ecol. Environ. Res*, 1, 1-16.
- Ogunbode, C. A. (2013). The NEP scale: Measuring ecological attitudes/ worldviews in an African context. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 15(6), 1477–1494. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-013-9446-0>.
- Ogunniyi, L. T., Wasiu, A. S. |& Ayinde A. E. (2011). Determinants of rural household willingness to pay for safe water in Kwara State, Nigeria. *International Journal of the Bioflux Society* 4(5): 660 – 669.
- Oliveira, S., & Lígia M. Costa Pinto (2020) Choice experiments to elicit the users' preferences for coastal erosion management: the case of Praia da Amorosa. *Environment, Development and Sustainability* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-020-00768-0>.
- Othman, J., Lip, G. H., & Jafari, Y. (2014). Benefits valuation of potable water quality improvement in Malaysia: The case of Kajang Municipality. *International Journal of Water Resources Development*, 30, 621–34.
- Owuor, M. A., Mulwa, R., Otieno, P., Icely, J., & Newton, A. (2019). Valuing mangrove biodiversity and ecosystem services: A deliberative choice experiment in Mida Creek, Kenya. *Ecosystem Services*, 40, 101040.
- Pandya, A.B., & Sharma, S. (2020). Rethinking water policy reforms. *Irrigation and Drainage*, 69, 967 - 970.
- Park, E., Lee, S. J., Lee, C. K., Kim, J. S., Kim, N. J. (2018). An integrated model of travelers' pro-environmental decision-making process: The role of the New Environmental Paradigm. *Asia Pac. J. Tour. Res.* 23, 935–948.
- Pearce, D.W. (1992). Economic valuation and the natural world. *World Development Report*, WPS 988.
- Pelyukh, O., & Zahvoyska, L. (2017). CHOICE EXPERIMENT METHOD IN FOREST ECOSYSTEM SERVICES VALUATION. *Scientific Bulletin of UNFU*, 27, 46-52.
- Perman, R., & Stern, D. I. (2003). Evidence from panel unit root and cointegration tests that the environmental Kuznets curve does not exist. *Australian Journal of Agricultural and Resource Economics*, 47(3), 325-347.

- Phillips, K. A., Maddala, T., & Johnson, F. R. (2002). Measuring preferences for health care interventions using conjoint analysis: an application to HIV testing. *Health services research*, 37(6), 1681-1705.
- Pienaar, E. F., Lew, D. K., & Wallmo, K. (2015). The importance of survey content: Testing for the context dependency of the new ecological paradigm scale. *Social Science Research*, 51, 338–349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssresearch.2014.09.005>
- Pierce, J., Steel, B., & Warner, R., (2009). Knowledge, culture, and public support for renewable energy policy. *Comp Tech Tran Soc* 7:270–86 doi:10.1353/ctt.0.0047
- Pires, P., Ribas Junior, R. C., Hora, G., Filgueiras, A., & Lopes, D. (2016). Psychometric properties for the Brazilian version of the new ecological paradigm: Revised. *Temas em Psicologia*, 24(4), 1407–1419. <https://doi.org/10.9788/TP2016.4-12>
- Poortinga, W., & Pidgeon, N. F. (2003). Exploring the dimensionality of trust in risk regulation. *Risk Anal. Int. J.* 23, 961–972.
- Putrawan, I. M. (2015). Measuring new environmental paradigm based on students' knowledge about ecosystem and locus of control. *Eurasia J. Math. Sci. Technol. Educ.* 11, 325–333.
- Rai, R. K., & Scarborough, H. (2015). Nonmarket Valuation in Developing Countries: Incorporating Labour Contributions in Environmental Benefits Estimates. *Aust. J. Agric. Resour. Econ.* 59, 479–498.
- Rai, R., & Scarborough, H. (2013). Economic value of mitigation of plant invaders in a subsistence economy: incorporating labour as a mode of payment. *Environ Dev Econ*, 18(2), 225–244.
- Rankinen, K., Butterfield, D., Faneca Sánchez, M., Grizzetti, B., Whitehead, P., Pitkänen, T., Uusi-Kämpä, J., & Leckie, H. (2016). The INCA-Pathogens model: an application to the Loimijoki river basin in Finland. *Sci. Total Environ.* 572, 1611–1621. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.05.043

References add

- Remoundou, K., Diaz-Simal, P., Koundouri, P., & Rulleau, B. (2015). Valuing climate change mitigation: A choice experiment on a coastal and marine ecosystem. *Ecosystem services*, 11, 87-94.
- Reyna, C., Bressán, E., Mola, D., Belaus, A., & Ortiz, M. V. (2018). Validating the structure of the new ecological paradigm scale among Argentine citizens through different approaches. *Pensamiento Psicológico*, 16(1), 107–118. <https://doi.org/10.11144/Javerianacali.PPSI16-1.vsn>
- Rideout, B. E., Hushen, K., McGinty, D., Perkins, S., & Tate, J. (2005). Endorsement of the new ecological paradigm in systematic and E-mail samples of college students. *The Journal of Environmental Education*, 36(2), 15–23. <https://doi.org/10.3200/JOEE.36.2.15-23>

- Rosa, C. D., Collado, S., & Profice, C. C. (2018). Measuring Brazilians' environmental attitudes: a systematic review and empirical analysis of the NEP scale. *Curr. Psychol.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-018-0061-y>.
- Roy, A., Naskar, M., Sinha, A., Manna, R. K., Sahu, S. K., Ekka, A., & Das, B. K. (2023). Determinants influencing fishermen's willingness-to-participate and willingness-to-pay for conservation of small indigenous fishes a model-based insight from Indian Sundarbans. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 7. doi:10.3389/fsufs.2023.1215091
- Ryffel, A. N., Rid, W., & Grêt-Regamey, A. (2014). Land use trade-offs for flood protection: A choice experiment with visualizations. *Ecosystem Services*, 10, 111-123.
- Saini, R., & Monga, A. (2007). How I Decide Depends on What I Spend: Use of Heuristics is Greater for Time than for Money. *Beh Mkt: Consumer Decision Making & Search (Topic)*.
- Saleh, S. A., James S. W. Jr., & Liu, Z. (2012). Rural Nevada and climate change: Vulnerability, beliefs, and risk perception. *Risk Anal* 32:1041–59 doi:10.1111/j.1539-6924.2012.01836.x
- Salman, M., & Martinez, A. (2015). The African quest under the lenses of an ecosystemservices-based approach. In J. Martin-Ortega, R. C. Ferrier, I. J. Gordon, & S. Khan, *Water Ecosystem Services. A Global Perspective*. Cambridge: University Printing House.
- Scarpa, R., Thiene, M., & Hensher, D. A. (2012). Preferences for tap water attributes within couples: an exploration of alternative mixed logit parameterizations. *Water Resour Res*, 48.
- Schep, S., Guzmán, A., Van Beukering, P., De Moel, H., Eiselin, M., Ayesu, S., & Ansah, K. B. (2016). The economics of the Atewa Forest Range, Ghana. Accra. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07349165.1995.9726076>
- Schultz, P. W., Gouveia, V. V., Cameron, L. D., Tankha, G., Schmuck, P., & Franěk, M. (2005). Values and their relationship to environmental concern and conservation behaviour. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 36(4), 457–475. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022022105275962>.
- Schwartz, S. H. (2003). A proposal for measuring value orientations across nations. *Questionnaire package of the European social survey*, 259(290), 261.
- Sehreen, F., Masud, M.M., Akhtar, R., & Masum, M.R. (2019). A contingent valuation approach to evaluating willingness to pay for an improved water pollution management system in Dhaka City, Bangladesh. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 191.
- Sharma, A.K., & Sharma, A. (2019). Impact of anthropogenic activities on Himalayan ecosystem services and their management/sustainability: A review. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 8, 361-365.
- Sharma, B., Rasul, G., & Chettri, N. (2015). The economic value of wetland ecosystem services: Evidence from the Koshi Tappu Wildlife Reserve, Nepal. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 12, 84–93.
- Siegrist, M., & Cvetkovich, G. (2000). Perception of hazards: The role of social trust and knowledge. *Risk Anal.* 20, 713–720.

- Siegrist, M., Cvetkovich, G., & Roth, C. (2000). Salient value similarity, social trust, and risk/benefit perception. *Risk Analysis* 20, 353e362.
- Sjöberg, L. (2000). Factors in risk perception. *Risk Anal.* 20, 1–12.
- Slimak, M. W., & Dietz, T. (2006). Personal values, beliefs, and ecological risk perception. *Risk Analysis*. 26:1689–705 doi: 10.1111/j.1539-6924.2006.00832.x.
- Slovic P. (2016). *The Perception of Risk*: Routledge, New York.
- Slovic, P. (1987). Perception of risk. *Science*, 236, 280e285.
- Slovic, P. (1992). Perception of risk: Reflections on the psychometric paradigm. In S. Krimsky, & D. Golding (Eds.), *Social theories of risk* (pp. 117e152). Westport, CT: Praeger.
- Slovic, P. (2000). *The perception of risk*. London: Earth scan Publications Ltd.
- Slovic, P., Finucane, M., Peters, E., & MacGregor, D. G. (2002). The affect heuristic. In: Gilovich, T., Griffin, D., Kahneman, D. (Eds.), *Heuristics and Biases: The Psychology of Intuitive Judgment*. Cambridge University Press, pp. 397e420.
- Slovic, P., Fischhoff, B., & Lichtenstein, S. (1985). Characterising perceived risk. In R. W. Kates, C. Hohenemser, & J. X. Kasperson (Eds.), *Perilous progress: Managing the hazards of technology* (pp. 91e125). Boulder, CO: Westview.
- Slovic, P., Fischhoff, B., & Lichtenstein, S. (1986). The psychometric study of risk perception. In V. T. Covello, J. Menkes, & J. Mumpower (Eds.), *Risk evaluation and management* (pp. 3e24). New York: Praeger.
- Smeenk, I.J. (1983). Drinking water contaminants. *Environmental science & technology*, 17 9, 394A.
- Soliño, M., Joyce, J., & Alvarez-Farizo, B. (2013). Improving water quality in England and Wales: local endowments and willingness to pay. *Int J Environ Res* 7:623–32.
- So-Yoon, K., Seung-Hoon, Y., & Chang-Seob, K. (2013). Measuring the Willingness to Pay for Tap Water Quality Improvements: Results of a Contingent Valuation Survey in Pusan. *Water*, 5, 1638-1652.
- Steel BS. (1996). Thinking globally and acting locally?: Environmental attitudes, behaviour and activism. *J Environ Manag* 47:27–36 doi:10.1006/jema.1996.0033.
- Stern, P. C. (2000). New environmental theories: toward a coherent theory of environmentally significant behavior. *Journal of social issues*, 56(3), 407-424.
- Stern, P. C., & Dietz, T. (1994). The value basis of environmental concern. *Journal of Social Issues* 50, 65e84.
- Street, D.J., & Viney, R. (2019). *Design of Discrete Choice Experiments*. Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Economics and Finance.
- Sukharomana, R., & Supalla, R.J. (1998). Effect of Risk Perception on Willingness to Pay for Improved Water Quality. *Economics, Environmental Science*

- Tadesse, M., Alfnes, F., Erenstein, O., & Holden, S. (2017). Demand for a Labor-based Drought Insurance Scheme in Ethiopia: A Stated Choice Experiment Approach. *Agricultural Economics*, 48, 501- 511.
- Tan, Y., Lv, D., Cheng, J., Wang, D., Mo, W., & Xiang, Y. (2018). Valuation of environmental improvements in coastal wetland restoration: A choice experiment approach. *Global Ecology and Conservation*, 15, e00440.
- Tarfasa, S., & Brouwer, R. (2013). Estimation of the public benefits of urban water supply improvements in Ethiopia: a choice experiment. *Appl Econ* 45:1099–108.
- Taskin, O. (2009). The environmental attitudes of Turkish senior high school students in the context of postmaterialism and the new environmental paradigm. *Int. J. Sci. Educ.* 31, 481–502.
- Troell, M., Joyce, A., Chopin, T., Neori, A., Buschmann, A. H., & Fang, J. G. (2009). Ecological engineering in aquaculture—potential for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) in marine off-shore systems. *Aquaculture*, 297:1–9.
- Tropp, H. (2015). MAKING WATER A PART OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: The economic benefits of improved water management and services.
- Turner, R. K., & Pearce, D. W. (1990). *The ethical foundations of sustainable economic development*. London, UK: International Institute for Environment and Development.
- Turner, R. K., & Pearce, D. W. (1990). *The ethical foundations of sustainable economic development*. London, UK: International Institute for Environment and Development.
- UN Committee of Experts on Environmental-Economic Accounting, (UNCEEA). (2014). *U. C.-E*. New York: United Nations.
- UNESCO (2012). *Managing Water under Uncertainty and Risk*. The United National World Water Development Report 4, Vol. 1, UNESCO. Paris.
- United Kingdom National Ecosystem Assessment. (2011). *The UK National Ecosystem Assessment: Synthesis of the Key Findings*. UNEPWCMC, Cambridge.
- United Nations World Water Assessment Programme (WWAP). UN-Water. (2018). *The United Nations World Water Development Report 2018: Nature-Based Solutions for Water*. Paris, UNESCO.
- Upton, V., Dhubháin, Á. N., & Bullock, C. (2012). Preferences and values for afforestation: The effects of location and respondent understanding on forest attributes in a labelled choice experiment. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 23, 17-27.
- Van Beukering, P., & Cesar, H. S. (2004). Ecological economic modeling of coral reefs: evaluating tourist overuse at Hanauma Bay and algae blooms at the Kihei Coast, Hawai'i. *Pac. Sci.* 58 (2), 243–260.
- Vaske, J. J., Absher, J. D., & Bright, A. D. (2007). Salient value similarity, social trust, and attitudes toward wildland fire management strategies. *Human Ecology Review* 14, 223e232.

- Vaske, J. J., Timmons, N. R., Beamon, J., & Petchenik, J. (2004). Chronic wasting disease in Wisconsin: hunter behaviour, perceived risk, and agency trust. *Human Dimensions of Wildlife*.
- Vásquez, W. (2014). Willingness to pay and willingness to work for improvements of municipal and community-managed water services. *Water Resources Research*, 50(10), 8002–8014. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/2014WR015913>
- Vigiak, O., Malagó, A., Bouraoui, F., Grizzetti, B., Weissteiner, C.J., & Pastori, M. (2016). Impact of current riparian land on sediment retention in the Danube River Basin. *Sustain. Water Qual. Ecol.* 8, 30–49. doi:10.1016/j.swaqe.2016.08.001
- Villasante, S., Pita, P., Rodrigues, J., Castelao, D., & Pita, C. (2020). Economic costs of marine litter for fisheries in NW Portugal and Galicia, Report N°3 - NetTag - “Tagging fishing gears and enhancing on board best-practices to promote waste free fish-eries” project, 25. Available from URL: <http://net-tag.eu/>
- Vondolia, G. K., & Navrud, S. (2019). Are Non-Monetary Payment Modes More Uncertain for Stated Preference Elicitation in Developing Countries? *J. Choice Model.* 30, 73–87.
- Vondolia, G., Eggert, H., Navrud, S., & Stage, J. (2017). What do Respondents Bring to Contingent Valuation? A Comparison of Monetary and Labour Payment Vehicles. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Policy*, 3, 253–267.
- Walker, J. L., Wang, Y., Thorhauge, M., & Ben-Akiva, M. (2018). D-efficient or deficient? A robustness analysis of stated choice experimental designs. *Theory and Decision*, 84, 215-238.
- Wang, H., He, J., Kim, Y., & Kamata, T. (2013). Willingness-to-pay for water quality improvements in Chinese rivers: an empirical test on the ordering effects of multiple-bounded discrete choices. *Journal of environmental management*, 131, 256-69 .
- Wasambo, J. (2011). *Water Governance and Sustainable Rural Livelihoods: The Case of Irrigation Reform at Wovwe, Malawi*. Ph.D. Thesis, Department of Science and Environmental Policy, Budapest, Central European University, Budapest, Hungary.
- Water Resource Commission (WRC). (2012). *PRA RIVER BASIN - Integrated Water Resources Management Plan*. Water Resources Commission.
- Water Resource Commission (WRC). (2014). *Water resources commission annual report 2013*. Water Resources Commission of Ghana.
- Water Resources Commission (WRC). (2003). *Raw Water Quality Criteria and Guidelines*. Report prepared for Ghana Water Resources Commission by CSIR Water Research Institute. WRI/CAR 133.
- Whitehead, P. G., Wilby, R. L., Battarbee, R. W., Kernan, M., & Wade, A. J. (2009). A review of the potential impacts of climate change on surface water quality. *Hydrol. Sci. J.* 54, 101–121. doi:10.1623/hysj.54.1.101

- Windle, J., Rolfe, J., & Brouwer, R. (2009). Public values for improved water security for domestic and environmental use. Environmental Economics Research Hub Research Reports. Num. 94818. Australian National University.
- Withanachchi, S., Kunchulia, I., Ghambashidze, G., Al Sidawi, R., Urushadze, T., & Ploeger, A. (2018). Farmers' perception of water quality and risks in the mashavera river basin, georgia: Analysing the vulnerability of the social-ecological system through community perceptions. Sustainability 10, 3062.
- World Water Assessment Programme. (2012). The United Nations World Water Development Report 4: Managing Water under Uncertainty and Risk; UNESCO: Paris, France.
- Xiao, C., & Buhrmann, J. (2017). The structure and coherence of the new environmental paradigm: Reconceptualising the dimensionality debate. Hum. Ecol. Rev. 23, 179–199.
- Yoshikawa, S., Cho, J., Yamada, H.G., Hanasaki, N., & Kanae, S. (2013). An assessment of global net irrigation water requirements from various water supply sources to sustain irrigation: rivers and reservoirs (1960–2050). Hydrology and Earth System Sciences, 18, 4289-4310.
- Young, R., & Loomis, J. (2014). Determining the Economic Value of Water: Concepts and Methods (2nd Edition ed.). New York, USA: RFF Press.
- Zakari, O. (2012). Assessing the impact of management activities on the Densu River Basin. Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology.
- Zhu, X., & Lu, C. (2017). Re-evaluation of the new ecological paradigm scale using item response theory. Journal of Environmental Psychology, 54, 79–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2017.10.005>.

**DEPARTMENT OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS AND AGRIBUSINESS
COLLEGE OF BASIC AND APPLIED SCIENCES**

**HOUSEHOLD QUESTIONNAIRE ON THE STUDY: ECONOMIC VALUATION AND RISK
PERCEPTIONS OF WATER-RELATED ECOSYSTEM SERVICES IN PRA AND DENSU RIVER
BASINS**

SURVEY INFORMATION

REGION:	DISTRICT.....
Community name.....	Community ID:
Household unique serial number:	
GPS COORDINATES:	
LOCALITY:	
Team:	
Supervisor:	
Enumerator:	
Date of interview:	

Section A: State and Frequency of Ecosystem Services

A01: What do you think about the state of the following?

Item	Coding
A01A: Number of fish species (varieties) in the river	
A01B: Actual catches of fish from the river	
A01C: Frequency of catastrophic flooding	
A01D: Soil erosion in my community	
A01E: Surface water quality	
A01F: Recreation opportunities close to the water bodies	
A01G: Suitability of performing religious activities at the river sites	

1- Excellent 2- Good 3 – Moderate 4 – Bad 5 – Very bad 6 – Don't know

A02: Events		A02A: Flooding	A02B: Erosion	A02C: Reduction in fish catch	A02D: Outbreak of water-related diseases (eg. Cholera, bilharzia, malaria)	A02E: Any other, specify
Has anyone in your household been affected by any of the following water related event in the past 10 years						
If yes, how many times did each event happen in the past 10 years?						
Does your household receive any warning(s) about any of the following event before it occur/occurs? If yes, what kind of warning?						
Did any member of the household loose his/her life due to any of the following events? if yes, please state number of persons						
Was any member of your household injured during any of the following events? if yes, please state number of persons						
Physical Property Loss	Value of property (GHC)					
Farm Produce	Value of property (GHC)					
Livestock (Cattle)	Value of property (GHC)					
Livestock (Sheep)	Value of property (GHC)					
Livestock (Goats)	Value of property (GHC)					

Poultry	Value of property (GHC)					
---------	-------------------------	--	--	--	--	--

Section B: Risks and Concern on Water-Related Ecosystem Services

[Threats attributable to human activities in the basin]

B01: Please respond to the following

Statement	1] Destructive fishing methods	2] Farming at the riverbanks	3] Draw-down agriculture	4] Improper use of agro-chemicals and fertilisers close to riverbanks	5] Cutting down of trees close to the riverbanks	6] Improper waste disposal	7] illegal mining practices	8] Sand-winning from the riverbanks	9] Construction close to the river banks	10] Influx of people to this locality	11] Bush burning
B01A] In your opinion, to what extent do each of these activities pose as risk or threat to the quality of river water? Code O (if Code O is 5 or 6) go to B and C											
B01B] In your opinion, how easy or difficult would it be to reduce the risks/threats from each of these activities on the quality of river water? Code P											
Please, to what extent is there alternative (s) to each of these activities											
B01C] To secure household incomes and livelihoods in your community, what alternative(s) do you think should be put in place to address each of the listed threats?											
Code O 1 - Not at all risky	Code P 1 – Very difficult 4 – Slightly easy					Code					

2 - Slightly risky 3 - Moderately risky 4 - Very risky 5 - Extremely risky 6 - Don't know	2 - Difficult 3 - Slightly difficult 7 - Don't know	5 - Easy 6 - Perfectly easy	1 Alternatives are never available 2 Alternatives are rarely available 3 Alternatives are sometimes available 4 Alternatives are very often available 5 Alternatives are always available
---	---	--------------------------------	---

B02: How concerned are you about the following in your community?

B02(A) Recreation opportunities close to the water bodies	B02(B) Fish catches from the water bodies	B02(C) Water quality in the water bodies	B02(D) Degradation and loss of different types of life forms (plants and animals)	B02(E) Flood events/occurrence	B02(F) Erosion
---	---	--	---	--------------------------------	----------------

[1 - Extremely concerned, 2 - Moderately concerned, 3 - Somewhat concerned, 4 - Slightly concerned, 5 - Not at all concerned]

B03: Risk reduction or regulation] To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

B03A: Local government must start to take actions to preserve and protect the river ecosystems	B03B: As a citizen, I am also responsible for contributing towards the protection and enhancement of the river ecosystems	B03C: Any human activity that adversely affects the health of water bodies and fish populations should be regulated	B03D: I do not trust in the capacity of government institutions to address water management challenges	B03E: Community leaders (such as chiefs, assemblymen, clan leaders, etc) can better manage the water bodies than government institutions
--	---	---	--	--

[1 - Strongly disagree, 2 - Disagree, 3 - Neither agree or disagree, 4 - Agree, 5 - Strongly agree]

Section C: Choice Experiment

You will now be presented with management scenarios in which you will have to make choices about potential future improvements to the water-related ecosystem services in the basin.

You will be presented with 8 and 7 separate choice cards with money and time payments, and choice between the various management options, A, B and C which are aimed at restoring the ecosystem services. Each of which should be considered individually (i.e., not in relation to the choices before or after).

In each choice, you should select and mark the box for: **Plan A or Plan B or Plan C or Status Quo**

Status Quo is the current situation with no changes

Take your time and make your decision for each choice carefully, selecting the option which best suits your household preferences and budget.

Scenario

Because of population growth and physical developments, pollution, illegal mining and fisheries and other issues in your locality, the flow and the quality of ecosystem services from the natural environment in and around your community are threatened. For this reason, interventions that aim to restore and protect the natural resource base by increasing their sizes and ensuring that they are clean are being proposed. For instance, land could be protected against erosion by restoring vegetation cover on riverbanks and within communities. Flash floods could be prevented or reduced by protecting riverbanks from agricultural activities and restore forests. Turbidity reduces surface water quality. When turbidity is very high, it is not possible or effective to treat water for drinking water. Illegal mining that leads to high turbidity in the water could be stopped. Fish populations could be restored by regulating fisheries and reduce overfishing. When water bodies are of good or high ecological quality, there will also be more possibility for recreation, tourism and religious practices. All these types of interventions can provide you and your community with increased benefits, depending on the level of ambition and amount of money available.

Such interventions need investments and support from local communities in order to be realised and maintained. Some parts of implementation and maintenance could be taken up by your community, in which case you and other community members would be asked to spend some days tending and restoring the environment each month and/or pay a levy to a local community fund, established just for this purpose and managed by your community leaders with the support of local government.

To examine the willingness of your community in restoring your local environment, we would like to ask you to make a number of choices. These choices are presented to you in the upcoming imaginary situations and contain trade-offs between your monthly levy or time contribution and changes in flood control, erosion control, water quality, fish abundance and recreation/tourism/cultural services. For each imaginary situation, please indicate which option you would prefer. While doing so, please keep in mind that the time you would spend getting involved in this activity or amount of money paid will not be available to be used for other purposes.

Now, consider these imaginary situations as I explain them and with the help of the associated diagrams, after which we will continue to the choices.

ENUMERATOR: [Reference to where they live] please emphasize that some of the benefits in the imaginary situations are long-term benefits and might not be observed immediately. Also, the respondents' contributions will also be for at least the 5 years.

Descriptions of the benefits that differ in each situation:

Flood control: deforestation increasingly leads to flooding downstream as infiltration rates are reduced. This is in particular a problem in the lower reaches of the Pra and Densu basins that experiences frequent catastrophic flash floods that take down bridges, farmlands, houses, properties, etc. Construction in flood plains, rubbish dumping in waterways; and poor drainage infrastructure contribute to the high damages experienced. Fortunately, it is possible to reduce flood risks through increased afforestation, construction and maintenance of dams and reservoirs and building alluviums.

There are three levels of ambition that you will be expected to decide based on these options and one status quo, where no actions are taken:

Strong protection against flooding: 1 catastrophic flooding event occurs in 10 years in cities and communities

Medium protection against flooding: 3 catastrophic flooding event occurs in 10 years in cities and communities

Low protection against flooding: 5 catastrophic flooding event occurs in 10 years in cities and communities

Status Quo - no protection against flooding: the number of flash floods experienced as at now will continue or increase if no action is taken.

Prevention of erosion: Erosion is an increasing problem in the Pra and Densu basins. In some places, buildings are getting exposed and left hanging as the topsoil is eroded and washed away during heavy rainfalls. Over time this also leads to reduced fertility of agricultural land. Fortunately, restoring vegetation cover at river and stream banks and within communities can reduce or even stop erosion. Also, vegetation cover of grasses, shrubs and trees on farm land can help reduce erosion. Other activities that will help reduce erosion includes regulating sand winning, placing a ban illegal mining, reducing deforestation, and improving husbandry practices. Canoes can continue to be anchored at the beach; trading activities can continue there, the road and other infrastructure will be protected. In addition, your households' property and that of others in your community will be safe against erosion events. These changes and the benefits associated with them are expected every year.

There are three levels of ambition for erosion control that you are expected to make a decision on and one status quo, where no further actions are taken:

Strong erosion control: there will be only a low surface soil erosion around community (80% of land is protected against soil erosion on lands cultivated by the community)

Medium erosion control: there will be some surface soil erosion around community (50% of land is protected against soil erosion on lands cultivated by the community)

Low erosion control: there will be significant surface soil erosion around community (20% of land is protected against soil erosion on lands cultivated by the community)

Status Quo - no protection against erosion: the level of erosion experienced as at now will continue or increase if no action is taken.

Surface water quality: A major problem for surface water quality is the level of turbidity. Turbidity is the measure of relative clarity of the water in rivers, streams and ponds. Turbidity is mainly due to illegal mining activities. High levels of turbidity make water treatment inefficient and risks destroying water treatment installation. In several instances, treatment plants have been known to close down because of high turbidity levels. When this happens, no drinking water for communal tap system or sachet water is produced. The cost of drinking water also increases when treatment plants have difficulties to treat water of poor water quality. Surface water quality is also important for other kinds of uses: irrigation of agricultural land, religious practices and recreation.

There are three levels of ambition for surface water quality that you expected to decide based on these options and one status quo, where no actions are taken:

High surface water quality: Surface water is drinkable. The water is very clear and doesn't smell. Turbidity levels are below 5 NTU.

Medium surface water quality: Surface water quality allows for some activities such as water for domestic use (cooking, washing), but not for drinking. Water is somewhat clear and a bit smelly. Turbidity levels are between 80 and 150 NTU.

Low surface water quality: Surface water is unsuitable for any usage. The water is very unclear and very smelly. Turbidity is above 150 NTU.

Status Quo - no additional action to improve surface water quality: the level of turbidity experienced as at now will continue or increase if no action is taken.

Fish abundance and richness: Fish stocks in the water bodies such as rivers, lakes and reservoirs are under immense pressure from overfishing and use of unorthodox methods of fishing (for instance prohibited gears, chemicals). Fortunately, it is possible to reverse this negative trend in fisheries development if communities regulate fisheries and local government provides support for alternative livelihood sources. In addition, restoring and protecting fisheries will help increase both the number of fish and the different types of different fish species for the benefit of both communities and the ecosystem.

There are three levels of ambition for fish abundance and richness that you are expected to make a decision based on these options and one status quo, where no actions are taken:

High levels of fish catches with many different species caught: >15kg of fish catch per 8-hour fishing per canoe and 16 different species expected

Medium levels of fish catches with only some different species caught: 10-15kg of fish catch per 8-hour fishing per canoe and 8 different species expected

Low levels of fish catches with only few different species caught: 5.5-10kg of fish catch per 8-hour fishing per canoe and 3 different species expected

Status Quo - no additional action to increase fish abundance and richness: less than 5kg per 8-hour fishing in canoe if no actions are taken

Recreation/Tourism/Religious practices: Cultural activities in relation to water bodies such as recreation (swimming, picnicking), tourism and religious practices are important for communities and households, but also serve to protect the water bodies. Water bodies are seen as deities with ceremonies and rituals are being held to worship and protect them. In some instances, taboos are in place to guide and regulate the use of water bodies. These include for instance dark colour prohibited to the water body or women in their menstrual cycle are not allowed near a water body. other religious practices connected to water bodies include immersion or baptism in rivers performed by Christians.

There are three levels of ambition for cultural services from water bodies that you are expected to made a decision based on these options and one status quo, where no actions are taken:

High level of opportunities for recreation, tourism and religious practices in your nearest water body

Medium level of opportunities for recreation, tourism and religious practices in your nearest water body

Low level of opportunities for recreation, tourism and religious practices in your nearest water body

Status Quo - no action to improve cultural services

Contribution to a community fund: A monthly monetary contribution of your household into a local fund earmarked for the management and maintenance of the facility and to be managed by your community leaders, with the support of the local government. Please note that this is *not* a one-time payment but a (relatively small) payment that is being made to the fund every month. This payment will need to be made for (at least) the next 5 years. The money collected into the fund will only be used to pay for the restoration and protection of the natural environment in and around your community. This includes paying someone to guard, protect and clean the immediate surroundings, build fences or lookouts, enforce regulations and to plant trees.

Time spent on tending and cleaning the natural environment: Time (in hours per week) you would be spending on tending, restoring and cleaning the natural areas in and around your community. This time is a donation that is unpaid and will be in place for (at least) the next 5 years. Activities include guarding, protecting, restoring and cleaning the natural areas, building fences or lookouts, enforcing regulations and planting trees. All households in your community will be asked to spend some time on these tasks, and the tasks will be managed by your community leaders with the support of the local government. Please keep in mind that the time spent engaging yourself in these activities cannot be spent on other activities.

The coming questions ask more detail about the choices you just made in the experiment.

C02. [Enumerator]: Only ask this question if the respondent has chosen the base scenario (Status quo) each time. You have chosen “No changes from today [Status quo]” in each card, can you explain why? Multiple answers possible.

Item	C02A: I am not responsible for protecting the natural areas	C02C: I don't have any money/time left to spend on protection of the natural areas	C02E: The presented choices are not realistic to me	C02G: I don't want to contribute money/time because I will not benefit from it	C02H: I don't trust that my contributions will be used for the right purpose	C02I: I think that the benefits will accrue later and I need my resources now	C02K: Other, specify	C02L: Don't know
------	---	---	---	--	--	--	----------------------	------------------

C03 [Enumerator]: Ask these to respondents who have chosen at least one of the options

STATEMENT	C03A: I trust that my money/time contributions will be effectively used for the protection of the natural areas only	C03B: Contributing money/time to the protection of the natural areas is acceptable to me	C03C: I am confident that all or most community members who can contribute money/time will also do so	C03D: It is not easy to convince all community members to contribute money/time	C03E: Other stakeholders (e.g. the national government/NGOs/CBOs/faith-based organisations/individuals, etc), are responsible for the protection and maintenance of the environment, not me
Coding					

1 – Strongly disagree 2 – Disagree 3 – Somewhat disagree 4 – Neither agree or disagree 5 – Somewhat agree 6 – Agree 7 – Strongly agree

C04: How much attention did you pay to each of the attributes while you were making the choices, on a scale from 0 (no attention) to 4 (full attention)?

0 – No attention, 1 – Little attention, 2- Medium attention, 3 – More attention, 4 – Full attention

	No attention				Full attention	Don't know (-99)
Attribute	0	1	2	3	4	

HOUSEHOLD I D	D04 Gender of HHH 0=Female 1=Male	D05 If other than HHH what is the relationship of (NAME) to head of household? Code A	D06 How old is (NAME)? [Years only]	D07 What is (NAME'S) present marital status? Code B	D08 What is your religious denomination? Code C	D09 To which ethnic group do you belong? Code D	D10 What is your settlement status? 0=Settler 1=Native	D11 How long have you stayed in this locality (years)?	D12 What is your highest level of education attained? Code E	D13 If the average income for a household in Ghana is 30,000 GHS per year. Would you rate your household's income as being? Code F	D14 What is the distance between your house and the nearest river/water body? km	D15 How long (time in minutes) does it take to get to the nearest river/water body (on foot)?	D16 How dependent is your household's livelihood/income on the river? Code G
---------------------	---	--	--	--	--	---	--	--	--	---	---	---	--

Code A 1 Head 2 Spouse (wife/husband) 3 Child (son/daughter) 4 Grandchild 5 Parent/parent-in-law 6 Son/daughter-in-law 7 Other relative 8 Adopted/foster/step child 9 House help (other relative) 10 House help (non-relative) 11 Non-relative 12 Other (specify)	Code B 1 Married 2 Consensual union 3 Separated 4 Divorced 5 Widowed 6 Never married 7 Living together/union 8 Single	Code C 1 No religion 2 Christianity 3 Islam 4 Traditionalist/Spiritualist 5 Atheist 6 Other (specify) 7 Don't want to state	Codes D 1 Ahafo 2 Akan 3 Bimoba 4 Bono 5 Grunsi 6 Hausa 7 Dagomba 8 Ewe 9 Frafra 10 Ga-Adangbe 11 Gonja 12 Other (spe.)	Code E 0 None 1 Kindergarten 2 Primary 3 JSS/JHS 4 Middle 5 SSS/SHS 6 Voc/Tech/Comm 7 Teacher, Agric/Nursing Training 8 Polytechnic 9 Univ.(Bachelor) 10 Uni. (postgrad.) 11 Professional 12 Don't know 13 Other (specify)	Code F 1. Much above average 2. Slightly above average 3. About average 4. Slightly below average 5. Much below average 6. Don't know	Code G 0 No at all Dependent 1 Slightly dependent 2 Somewhat Dependent 3 Moderately dependent 4 extremely dependent
--	--	---	--	---	--	---

Section E: Farming and Fishing Activities

E01 What is your main OR primary occupation? Code H	E02 What is your secondary occupation? (Multiple response) Code H	Details of farming activities <i>Answer if Answer to E01/02 has option 1/2 (in code)</i>										
		E03 What size of active agriculture land does the household own now? If Farming (code 1/2) in B01/02	E04 How far is your farm from the community? In m	E05 Does your farmland border a river? 0=No >> B07 1=Yes	E06 If yes, name of river	E07 Do you practice drawdown agriculture? 0=No >> Next Section 1=Yes	E08 What is the size of the drawdown farm?	E09 Do you apply agrochemic als?	E11 Quantity/o utput from this activity from last season/harv est?	E12 Did you sell the produce, or it was wholly consumed by the household?	E13 What is the total value of the output from this activity?	
		Area	Unit									1 Sold all 2 Sold part

F27 Do you have a bank account? 0=No >> C13 1=Yes	F28 What is the main reason why you do not have a bank account? Code K		F30 Did you apply for a loan to finance production last season? 0=No >> C17 1=Yes	F31 If yes, which source? (Please tick all that apply) Code L	F32 If yes, how much did you apply for last season?	F33 Do you have savings? (Bank/home savings, cash) Yes No
	Code K 1 Not necessary/interested (spec.) 2 Not aware of one 3 Process cumbersome 4 Financial institutions too far away 5 Don't have enough money or income 6 Don't have regular income 7 Other			Code L 1 Commercial Banks 2. Credit union 3. VSLAs 4. Family 5. Private (formal institutions) 6. Private (informal) 7. NGOs 8. Other		

Section G: Household Water Use and Sources

Sources and Nature of Water:

From which of the following water sources do you get water for your household use? (Multiple response)	G01 Distance to the source (Metres)	G02 Time spent to get water from source (Minutes per day)	G03 Nature of availability for source Code M
Borehole			
Pipe-born			
Stream/River			
Well			
Rain			
Dugout/Pond/Dam			
Spring			
Sachet water			
Bottle water			
Water tanker			
			Code M 1 Permanent 2. Seasonal

Water Use and values:

Water Use	G04 What is the major source of water for the following uses? (Only one source) Code N	G05 What other sources of water do you make use of for the following uses? (Multiple response) Code N	G06 What is the quantity/day for your household (Litres) NB: Probe and convert to litres	G07 What is the price per litre for the following uses? (GHC) NB: Probe and convert to litres	G08 What is your most preferred source of water for the following uses? Code N
Drinking					
Domestic (Washing and Bathing)					
Domestic (Cooking)					
Irrigation					
Livestock					
Processing (probe for water use in soap, beverages, and other small-scale production)					
Other					
Total					
	Code N 1 Borehole 2 Pipe-borne 3 Stream/river tank	4 Well 5 Rain-harvesting 6 Dugout/pond/dam	7 Spring 8 Sachet water 9 Bottle water 10 Water		

Section H: Risk Profile, Environmental Attitudes and Belief

Please select a statement in each question:

<p>H02 Imagine you have a choice between the following two options.</p> <p>OPTION 1: You receive 14 Ghana Cedis today.</p> <p>OPTION 2: You receive 42 Ghana Cedis in 1 month.</p> <p>Which option do you prefer?</p>	<p>H03 Imagine you have a choice between the following two options.</p> <p>OPTION 1: You receive GHS 14 Ghana Cedis today.</p> <p>OPTION 2: You receive 56 Ghana Cedis in 1 month.</p> <p>Which option do you prefer?</p>	<p>H04 Imagine you have a choice between the following two options.</p> <p>OPTION 1: You receive 7 Ghana Cedis for sure.</p> <p>OPTION 2: I flip a 1 Cedi Coin. If it shows the Shield, you get 14 Ghana Cedis. If it's the coat of arms, you get 1 Ghana Cedi.</p> <p>Which option do you prefer?</p>	<p>H05 Imagine you have a choice between the following two options.</p> <p>OPTION 1: You receive 7 Ghana Cedis for sure.</p> <p>OPTION 2: I flip a 1 GH Cedi Coin. If it shows the Shield, you get 21 Ghana Cedis. If it's the coat of arms, you get 1 Ghana Cedi.</p> <p>Which option do you prefer?</p>	<p>H06 Suppose you want to invest some money.</p> <p>OPTION 1: Investing in a business where I can't lose money but has low profits.</p> <p>OPTION 2: Investing in a business where there is a small chance I can lose money but potentially brings high profits.</p> <p>Which option do you prefer?</p>
---	---	--	---	--

Religious beliefs and the environment

H07: To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

Statement
H07A: God has given humans a role to perform as guardians/stewards to keep and protect water bodies/ rivers and the environment
H07B: God will not punish me for polluting the water bodies
H07C: God will create new and better water bodies if we destroy the current ones
H07D: Protecting the environment against pollution is an act of godliness and for which I will be rewarded

Response: 1 – Strongly disagree 2 – Disagree 3 – Neither agree or disagree 4 – Agree 5 – Strongly agree

Personal Values:

H08: Please read the following carefully and respond to how each statement resonates with you as a person. Rate your responses on a scale of 1-5, where '1' means 'very much like me,' and '5' implies 'not at all like me.'

H08A: Coming up with new ideas and being creative is important to me.	H08B: It is important for me to be rich and have a lot of money.	H08C: I believe that every person in the world should be treated equally.	H08D: It is important for me to show my abilities (I want other people to admire what I do).	H08E: It is important for me to live in a naturally safe and secure surrounding.	H08F: I believe that I should obey rules even when no one is around.	H08G: It is important for me to stay humble and modest.	H08H: Having a good time is important to me (I like to 'spoil' myself at times).	H08I: I like helping people around me.	H08J: I try to follow my traditional values and customs that my family and society have
---	--	---	--	--	--	---	--	--	---

Appendix B: Choice Experiment Design

Choice situation	alt1.flooding	alt1.erosioncontrol	alt1.surfacewaterquality	alt1.biodiversity	alt1.cultural services	alt1.cost	alt2.flooding	alt2.erosioncontrol	alt2.surfacewaterquality	alt2.biodiversity	alt2.cultural services	alt2.cost	Block
1	1	0	2	1	0	20	2	2	1	2	1	80	1
2	2	1	2	0	0	5	0	0	1	1	2	100	1
3	1	1	1	2	2	20	2	2	0	1	0	80	2
4	0	0	2	0	1	5	1	1	2	1	2	100	2
5	1	2	1	0	0	80	2	1	2	1	1	20	2
6	2	0	1	1	2	5	0	1	2	0	0	100	2
7	0	1	1	2	0	40	2	2	2	0	2	40	1
8	2	2	0	1	1	20	0	0	1	2	0	80	2
9	1	1	0	0	1	100	0	2	0	2	0	5	1
10	0	2	0	2	2	40	2	0	1	0	0	40	1
11	0	0	2	1	1	100	1	1	0	2	2	5	2
12	2	0	0	2	2	100	1	2	1	1	1	5	1
13	0	2	2	0	2	40	1	0	0	2	1	40	1
14	2	1	1	1	0	80	1	0	2	0	1	20	1
15	1	2	0	2	1	80	0	1	0	0	2	20	2

Appendix D: Supplementary Results of NEP Scale and Risk Perception Estimates

Table D1: Results of Cronbach's Alpha Estimates for NEP Scores

Variables	raw_alpha	std.alpha	G6(smc)	average_r	S/N	alpha_se	var.r	med.r
NEP 1	0.70	0.71	0.71	0.29	2.50	0.015	0.017	0.29
NEP 3	0.64	0.65	0.66	0.24	1.80	0.018	0.023	0.17
NEP 5	0.67	0.67	0.66	0.25	2.00	0.016	0.015	0.25
NEP 9	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.26	2.10	0.016	0.017	0.25
NEP 11	0.67	0.68	0.67	0.26	2.20	0.016	0.018	0.25
NEP 13	0.64	0.66	0.66	0.25	2.00	0.018	0.021	0.25
NEP 15	0.64	0.65	0.65	0.23	1.80	0.017	0.019	0.25
raw_alpha	std.alpha	G6(smc)	average_r	S/N	Ase	mean	sd	median_r
0.70	0.70	0.71	0.25	2.40	0.02	3.60	0.63	0.25
Variables	raw_alpha	std.alpha	G6(smc)	average_r	S/N	alpha_se	var.r	med.r
NEP 2	0.67	0.68	0.66	0.26	2.10	0.016	0.009	0.29
NEP 4	0.68	0.69	0.67	0.27	2.20	0.016	0.01	0.30
NEP 6	0.66	0.67	0.64	0.25	2.00	0.017	0.008	0.28
NEP 8	0.64	0.66	0.63	0.24	1.90	0.018	0.009	0.27
NEP 10	0.71	0.72	0.69	0.30	2.50	0.014	0.003	0.29
NEP 12	0.67	0.68	0.65	0.26	2.10	0.016	0.006	0.29
NEP 14	0.65	0.66	0.64	0.24	1.90	0.017	0.009	0.27
raw_alpha	std.alpha	G6(smc)	average_r	S/N	Ase	mean	sd	median_r
0.70	0.71	0.70	0.26	2.50	0.01	2.30	0.62	0.29

TABLE D2: STATISTICS IN DETERMINING THE NUMBER OF FACTORS

No. Factors	dof	Chisq	prob	RMSEA	BIC	SRMR
1	44.000	560.000	0.000	0.109	258.000	0.078
2	34.000	280.000	0.000	0.085	43.000	0.050

3	25.000	93.000	0.000	0.052	-80.000	0.025
4	17.000	45.000	0.000	0.040	-73.000	0.017
5	10.000	22.000	0.014	0.035	-47.000	0.011
6	4.000	8.100	0.087	0.032	-19.000	0.006
7	-1.000	0.021	NA	NA	NA	0.000
8	-5.000	0.000	NA	NA	NA	0.000

Appendix E: Supplementary Results of the Preference and Payments for WES

Table E1: Results of Multinomial Regression Results

Payment=Money		Pooled		Densu		Pra	
Variables	Estimate	Std. Error	Estimate	Std. Error	Estimate	Std. Error	
Cost (GHS)	-0.006	*** 0.000	-0.004	*** 0.001	-0.008	*** 0.001	
Flood Protection (Medium)	0.552	*** 0.039	0.540	*** 0.056	0.559	*** 0.055	
Flood Protection (High)	0.694	*** 0.041	0.609	*** 0.059	0.784	*** 0.059	
Erosion Control (Medium)	0.436	*** 0.039	0.518	*** 0.055	0.361	*** 0.054	
Erosion Control (High)	0.690	*** 0.038	0.685	*** 0.055	0.710	*** 0.054	
Surface Water Quality (Medium)	0.559	*** 0.043	0.538	*** 0.061	0.593	*** 0.062	
Surface Water Quality (High)	0.960	*** 0.057	0.896	*** 0.079	1.048	*** 0.083	
Biodiversity of Fish (Medium)	0.404	*** 0.042	0.422	*** 0.060	0.383	*** 0.058	
Biodiversity of Fish (High)	0.537	*** 0.044	0.575	*** 0.062	0.519	*** 0.063	
Cultural Services (Medium)	0.212	*** 0.040	0.163	** 0.056	0.274	*** 0.057	
Cultural Services (High)	0.204	*** 0.038	0.239	*** 0.054	0.168	** 0.053	
ASC (Opt_Out)	0.014	0.083	0.478	*** 0.115	-0.615	*** 0.124	
Log-Likelihood	-6576.823		-3529.468		-2947.391		
Null Log-Likelihood	-8230.803		-4109.909		-4120.895		
AIC	13177.646		7082.937		5918.781		
BIC	13260.706		7157.662		5993.539		
McFadden R2	0.201		0.141		0.285		
Adj McFadden R2	0.199		0.138		0.282		
Number of Observations	7492.000		3741.000		3751.000		
Payment = Time		Pooled		Densu		Pra	
Variables	Estimate	Std. Error	Estimate	Std. Error	Estimate	Std. Error	
Cost (Labour days)	-0.035	*** 0.005	-0.055	*** 0.007	-0.014	* 0.007	
Flood Protection (Medium)	0.500	*** 0.037	0.562	*** 0.054	0.454	*** 0.052	

Flood Protection (High)	0.651	***	0.039	0.784	***	0.056	0.529	***	0.056
Erosion Control (Medium)	0.275	***	0.037	0.229	***	0.052	0.335	***	0.053
Erosion Control (High)	0.444	***	0.036	0.400	***	0.051	0.503	***	0.051
Surface Water Quality (Medium)	0.398	***	0.041	0.130	*	0.059	0.668	***	0.058
Surface Water Quality (High)	0.710	***	0.055	0.400	***	0.077	1.032	***	0.079
Biodiversity of Fish (Medium)	0.299	***	0.039	0.214	***	0.057	0.387	***	0.054
Biodiversity of Fish (High)	0.337	***	0.042	0.157	**	0.060	0.522	***	0.060
Cultural Services (Medium)	0.206	***	0.037	0.150	**	0.053	0.269	***	0.053
Cultural Services (High)	0.148	***	0.036	0.137	**	0.051	0.157	**	0.051
ASC(Opt_Out)	-0.617	***	0.082	-0.722	***	0.113	-0.537	***	0.123
<hr/>									
Log-Likelihood	-6507.103			-3357.534			-3081.823		
Null Log-Likelihood	-8248.381			-4129.684			-4118.697		
AIC	13038.206			6739.067			6187.646		
BIC	13121.291			6813.850			6262.397		
McFadden R2	0.211			0.187			0.252		
Adj McFadden R2	0.210			0.184			0.249		
Number of Observations	7508.000			3759.000			3749.000		
<hr/>									

Table E2: Results of Random Parameter Model

Preference and WTP	Pooled			Densu			Pra		
Standard Deviations	Estimate	Std. Error							
Flood Protection (Medium)	0.394	***	0.102	0.345	.	0.186	-0.449	***	0.133
Flood Protection (High)	-0.550	***	0.078	-0.590	***	0.113	0.358	*	0.165
Erosion Control (Medium)	0.028		0.148	-0.095		0.259	0.211		0.138
Erosion Control (High)	0.794	***	0.077	0.755	***	0.117	-0.843	***	0.104
Surface Water Quality (Medium)	0.293	*	0.126	0.226		0.197	-0.224		0.228
Surface Water Quality (High)	-0.863	***	0.088	-0.778	***	0.130	1.159	***	0.135
Biodiversity of Fish (Medium)	0.667	***	0.076	0.769	***	0.109	-0.603	***	0.104
Biodiversity of Fish (High)	0.090		0.096	0.077		0.164	-0.092		0.122
Cultural Services (Medium)	0.127		0.112	0.075		0.149	-0.271	*	0.132
Cultural Services (High)	0.398	***	0.098	0.389	*	0.157	-0.415	***	0.119
ASC (Opt_Out)	-4.221	***	0.262	-4.102	***	0.326	-2.797	***	0.226
Standard Deviations									
Time_Pooled	Estimate	Std. Error							
Flood Protection (Medium)	0.282	**	0.095	0.179		0.138	0.516	***	0.112
Flood Protection (High)	-0.704	***	0.065	-0.751	***	0.091	-0.530	***	0.112
Erosion Control (Medium)	-0.289	**	0.092	-0.406	***	0.115	0.251		0.167
Erosion Control (High)	-0.158	.	0.092	-0.066		0.168	-0.265	*	0.114
Surface Water Quality (Medium)	0.048		0.096	-0.058		0.136	-0.084		0.124
Surface Water Quality (High)	0.504	***	0.098	-0.799	***	0.124	-0.323	*	0.157
Biodiversity of Fish (Medium)	0.030		0.086	0.050		0.165	0.079		0.107
Biodiversity of Fish (High)	-0.233	.	0.140	-0.389	**	0.134	0.524	***	0.115
Cultural Services (Medium)	0.215	.	0.113	0.191		0.146	-0.607	***	0.109
Cultural Services (High)	-0.114		0.121	0.225		0.155	-0.118		0.183
ASC(Opt_Out)	-4.304	***	0.296	-4.803	***	0.422	4.502	***	0.499

